

JOURNAL OF THE UNDERGRADUATE LINGUISTICS ASSOCIATION OF BRITAIN

Fig. 21. The apparatus used in recording eye movements.

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The *Journal of the Undergraduate Linguistics Association of Britain* (ISSN 2754-0820) was founded in July 2020 as a Subcommittee of the Undergraduate Linguistics Association of Britain. It is the only academic journal in the world taking submissions solely from undergraduates in any area of linguistics. The Journal exists to provide a forum for the publication of exceptional undergraduate research in linguistics for students across the globe and from any background. In so doing, it seeks to offer undergraduate students an introduction to academic publishing and standard practices in academia, including the opportunity for undergraduates to have their research reviewed. We aim to publish at least two issues per twelve-month period, with each volume corresponding to the Editorial Committee that oversees its production. Every manuscript is peer-reviewed over multiple rounds by two members of the Board of Reviewers, which consists of doctoral students in linguistics from a plethora of countries and institutions.

Contents

Front Matter	3
<i>Complexity and the Phonological Turing Machine</i> LOUIS VAN STEENE, UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	11
<i>Positioning Theory as a Tool for Analysing Working Class Identities: Angela Rayner in Interview</i> GEORGIA JUCKES, UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM	33
<i>Influence of Different Walking Speeds on Speech</i> ADELA BARTLICK SALCEDO, UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	60
<i>Fostering Second Language Acquisition of Canadian Primary School Children: A Critical Evaluation of Vygotsky's Learning Theory in the French Immersion Programme</i> FANGQIAN GUO, UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	92
<i>Expertise, Credibility, Trust and Advice in Veterinarian-Client-Pet Health Communication on Reality Television</i> ELEONORA KACL, UNIVERSITY OF BASEL	98
<i>The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: Does the Evidence Support its Existence?</i> NICHOLAS CHAVEZ, METROPOLITAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF DENVER	124
<i>Opaque Segholates Revisited: The Glottal Stop in Standard Modern Hebrew Phonology</i> MADELEINE KOSTANT-GREELEY, UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, LOS ANGELES	135
<i>Relative Clauses in Reading Schemes: How does Children's Comprehension Align?</i> REBECCA HUNT, UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX	157
<i>This Paper is Organized as Follows: Lexical Bundles in Computer Science Academic Texts Produced by Novice and Expert Writers</i> WESLEY HENRIQUE ACORINTI & ANA ELIZA PEREIRA BOCORNY, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF RIO GRANDE DO SUL	189
Back Matter	212

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Foreword from the Editor and the Head of the Board of Reviewers

We are extremely pleased to present the largest JoULAB issue to date: Volume 2, Issue 2. The Editorial Committee has been hugely busy reviewing, editing, and formatting the seven unique, brilliant articles featured in this issue, and we were happy to release Early Access versions of two of these articles in August and September.

Since the release of Volume 2 Issue 1 last January, we've been busy! We've recruited a wonderful all-new committee, full of fresh faces eager to make a difference in linguistics. We've also launched several initiatives, including a second workshop series which continues our mission to make academia accessible, and provide opportunities for undergraduates. Another of these initiatives is our podcast, [ANNOTATED](#). Featuring interviews with past authors, ANNOTATED endeavours to share personal stories and insight from those who have already been through the publication process, encouraging undergraduates to get their work out there. So far, we've released three episodes, with more to come: for now, check out our interviews with Nina Haket, T. R. Williamson, and Liv Peralta.

Last issue, we shared that our goal for the future was to broaden our scope and diversify the research published within JoULAB. We are happy to announce that we have achieved this goal! This issue's articles range from second language acquisition to critical discourse analysis to articulatory phonology, our most varied collection of subfields yet. We are also pleased to feature authors from around the world, their home institutions in the United Kingdom, United States, Brazil, and Switzerland.

Nine original articles are presented in this issue. Louis Van Steene's *Complexity and the Phonological Turing Machine* provides an evaluation of the most widespread phonological theories, considering the advantages each may have in linguistic theories aiming for explanatory adequacy from a computational and minimalist perspective. By advocating for the group of theories associated with Substance-Free Phonology, the author presents an approach that addresses properties related to complexity and economy in phonological derivations, through the introduction of a specific analysis method used in computer science. Georgia Juckes' paper, *Positioning Theory as a Tool for Analysing Working Class Identities: Angela Rayner in Interview*, by drawing on elements of Positioning Theory, examines how Angela Rayner, Deputy Leader of the Labour Party, uses narrative interaction to negotiate her identity. Unlike previous research, this article focuses on an underexplored aspect, which is how different levels interplay when constructing layered versions of the self.

Influence of Different Walking Speeds on Speech, written by Adela Bartlick Salcedo, shows how walking speed affects pause time, articulation rate and utterance time. The research findings suggest that there is an adjustment of speech to gait, although the changes that occur while speaking are less pronounced than those that happen while walking. In Fangoian Guo's article, *Fostering Second Language Acquisition of Canadian Primary School Children: A Critical Evaluation of Vygotsky's Learning Theory in the French Immersion Programme*, readers will find a review of the French as a Second Language immersion program designed and implemented in primary schools in Canada based on the methodological guidelines of Lev Vygotsky. The author's analysis shows the advantages and disadvantages of this approach, for example, when dealing with groups of students with different sociocultural backgrounds. Eleonora Kacil's *Expertise, Credibility, Trust and Advice in Veterinarian-Client-Pet Health Communication on Reality Television* analyses the different strategies that veterinarians use to gain the trust of clients, drawing data from three reality TV programs that focus on the work of veterinarians. Within the results observed, the author identifies three specific strategies used by professionals to demonstrate their expertise, appear credible, and trustworthy: directive speech acts, collaborative 'we', and the use of humour.

Nicholas Chavez, in *The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: Does the Evidence Support its Existence?*, provides a comprehensive evaluation of the Critical Period Hypothesis in language acquisition, which associates native-like fluency in a second language with a specific time frame during childhood. Chavez examines the main criticisms made of this theory, considering its methodology and understanding of what the "critical period" entails, and proposes that this period is related to the development of logical thinking. The author suggests the use of neuroimaging techniques to verify this hypothesis. *Opaque Segholates Revisited: The Glottal Stop in Standard Modern Hebrew Phonology*, by Madeleine Kostant-Greeley, examines the phonemic status of the glottal stop in the phonological inventory of Standard Modern Hebrew, as well as the underlying forms of glottal final nouns and verbs. Through an elicitation task with four native speakers, Kostant-Greeley presents evidence that final glottal stops are realized differently in nouns and verbs, while also maintaining their phonemic status. Rebecca Hunt's *Relative Clauses in Reading Schemes: How does Children's Comprehension Align?* examines how well the Oxford Reading Levels Scheme reflects children's comprehension of grammar in relation to relative clauses, focusing on embeddedness and focus. Results show that reading complexity increases with level, marked by more relative clauses and greater diversity at higher levels, and that there are differences in children's comprehension of relative clauses, with object-embedded, subject focus relative clauses being the most easily understood.

Lastly, Acorinti and Pereira Bocorny's paper, titled *This Paper is Organized as Follows: Lexical Bundles in Computer Science Academic Texts Produced by Novice and Expert Writers*, examines the use of common academic phrases, called lexical bundles, comparing texts written in English by Brazilian expert and novice writers in Computer Science. The findings suggest the need for tailored English for Academic Purposes materials, as lexical bundles were not utilized to their full potential by either group.

As well as being JoULAB's largest issue, Volume 2, Issue 2 marks Lydia's last issue as Editor. Some words from Lydia follow.

JoULAB has been a major part of my undergraduate life; I became an Associate Editor near the end of my first year at the University of Edinburgh, continuing that role during second year and assuming Editor for the remaining two. Now, as I am graduating, my time with JoULAB must also come to an end. Through the Journal, I have grown immensely, both personally and professionally, and have made lasting and meaningful connections with other undergraduate linguists, bonds which have extended beyond our shared context of JoULAB and into working together on research and co-authoring academic papers. But most of all, it has been my honour to platform the incredible undergraduates whose unique, innovative, and important work has ushered in a brilliant new generation of linguists. It brings me immense pride to present this final issue of JoULAB of my tenure. I must express my gratitude to all those who have been a part of this project throughout my time with JoULAB, including all members of both my Editorial Committees as well as the wider ULAB committee, both present and past. The Journal would not be possible without the incredible people who have made it up over the years; I could not have done it without the help and support of everyone on this team with me. I have no doubt that that the Journal will continue to thrive under new Editor Lucy Bartholomew's leadership, and I could not be more excited for JoULAB's future.

We extend huge thanks to the current Editorial Committee for their hard work this past year; this issue would not exist without them. We'd also like to thank the Advisory Board for their continued support, guidance, and encouragement. Thanks must, above all, go to you, for reading and supporting

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opportunities for undergraduate publication in linguistics. We hope you thoroughly enjoy Volume 2, Issue 2!

Lydia Wiernik

Editor, JoULAB

University of Edinburgh

Nicolás Arellano,

Head of the Board of Reviewers, JoULAB

University of Buenos Aires

Foreword from the National Chair of ULAB

Since its inception in the summer of 2020, JoULAB has gone from strength to strength. This issue is the largest and most diverse to date, showcasing nine phenomenal articles from undergraduate linguists across the globe.

This academic year has marked the release of JoULAB's podcast, ANNOTATED - featuring interviews with Nina Haket, T. R. Williamson, and Liv Peralta, authors who were published in the first ever issue of the Journal. Their fascinating discussions, insights, and experiences are all unique, yet all underpinned by the fact that there is no singular way to be an undergraduate linguist. Special calls for papers and reviewers in underrepresented areas shows that no area of linguistics is too niche. Additionally, JoULAB's workshop series continued with 'Finding Your Voice as a Linguist', highlighting a commitment to uplifting young linguists in their journey through academia.

During Lydia's two years as Editor, she has worked tirelessly and consistently; the positive difference that she has made is immeasurable. This effort is reflected in a strong Editorial Committee, a diverse and ever-expanding Board of Reviewers, a series of events and workshops for academics at every stage, and a set of articles copyedited to the highest standard. Thanks must also go to the JoULAB Advisory Board, whose help and support has been invaluable.

Our warmest wishes to the Journal's incoming Editor, Lucy, and the future Editorial Committee.

Ro Dhasmana,
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Complexity and the Phonological Turing Machine

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University of Cambridge

Abstract. Any scientific theory, including within linguistics, requires a coherent philosophical basis in order to evaluate and decode the relations between data, phenomena, and theory. Chomsky's (1964; 1965) identification of explanatory adequacy as one of the ultimate goals of a theory of I-language was a seminal step in this regard. This paper explores this term and its implications with special reference to phonological theory. In particular, four different groups of theories are evaluated on the metric of explanatory adequacy: Chomsky & Halle's (1968) Rule-Based Phonology, Stampe's (1979) Natural Phonology, Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky, 1993; McCarthy & Prince, 1993), and Substance-Free Phonology (SFP; Hale & Reiss, 2008; Samuels, 2009). SFP is found to be the most promising from a minimalist, computational perspective. This theoretical foundation is subsequently adapted into Watumull's (2012; 2015) Turing programme for linguistic theory. From this perspective, the mind is viewed as equivalent to a Turing machine – the universal model of computation. Framed as such, a novel approach emerges regarding computational complexity and economy in (phonological) derivations, which are issues otherwise often only nebulously invoked in the evaluation of theories. A method of analysis is introduced by adopting 'Big-O notation' as used for asymptotic analysis in computer science. This method is shown to highlight the importance of strongly defining the inventory of computational primitives and procedures within a theory. Specific suggestions regarding the nature of the most optimal theory under this analysis are made with respect to Samuels' (2009) explicitly Minimalist brand of SFP.

Plain English Abstract. The goal of a particular linguistic theory should be to make falsifiable predictions about what every human (excepting language disorders) knows about language and how they come to have this knowledge. Chomsky (1964) respectively labels these two goals as descriptive adequacy and explanatory adequacy. An important area of linguistic knowledge concerns phonology, the mental combination and manipulation of discrete, arbitrary symbols that are composed into words. These symbols are known as phonemes, for example /p/, /a/, /u/. In this paper, four theories of phonology are presented and evaluated against the goal of explanatory adequacy. This leads to Watumull's (2012) proposal that the various aspects of linguistic knowledge, including the phonological module, be considered as equivalent to a Turing machine, a device capable of performing any computable operation. In such an approach, it becomes apparent that consideration of the precise nature of the inventory of procedures available within a theory is crucial. It is further proposed that theories that take representations as prior to these procedures end up being more complex computationally. In this respect, something can be learned from the study of computational complexity within computer science, in particular the use of 'Big-O notation'. From all this, one theoretical contender emerges as most promising – namely, a version of Samuels' (2009) theory. It is clear, however, that the theory needs to be refined much further in line with these goals.

Keywords: Natural Phonology; Optimality Theory; computational complexity; Turing machine; phonological process; I-language

1 Introduction

When discussing the adequacy of theories, it is important to dissect exactly what one means by the term 'theory' in this context. One crucial element, following the Popperian tradition, is that a scientific theory must stipulate the evidence needed to falsify it (Thornton, 2019); this extends to linguistic theory. When considering exactly what 'evidence' is, difficulty can arise in distinguishing the three interactive levels of *data*, *phenomena*, and *theory*. Bogen & Woodward (1977) claim that 'phenomena' are separate both from data on the one hand, and theory on the other. A theory explains or predicts phenomena, and data are evidence for the existence of phenomena. To complicate matters, the theory itself can influence (the

collection of) the data which then inform the postulation of phenomena, which is an issue well-known in the philosophy of science (Kelly, 2016). Thus, there arises a tension here, between accounting for the data directly with the theory on the one hand, and accounting for the phenomena as they actually are on the other. This can be seen as a paraphrasing of the difference between descriptive adequacy, viz. making predictive, testable generalisations that account for the data, and explanatory adequacy, which requires the theory to account for the phenomenon of its acquisition (Chomsky, 1965).

In generative linguistics, the object of study is *I-language*, characterised as *internal, intensional* (generable intensionally, as opposed to being explicit and extensional) and *individual*. This is what gives language its essential creative aspect, corresponding to what Humboldt called the ‘infinite use of finite means’, discrete infinity – the ‘finite means’ in question is the I-language¹. The goal is to achieve a formal description of I-language which meets explanatory adequacy. Simplicity is the goal of any formal, scientific description, with the assumption being that the simplest theory is most likely to be right – and even if this ends up not being the case, such a theory would prove the best foundation for a reality that turns out to be more complex (Hale & Reiss, 2008). This is taken to its ultimate conclusion in the Minimalist programme (Chomsky, 1995), which approaches UG ‘from below’ in order to establish how little needs to be postulated to specify I-language sufficiently (see Chomsky, 2007). Formulating a metric for this end goal of simplicity, with specific reference to the phonological component of I-language, is the purpose of this paper.

The tension between description and explanation is the topic of Section 2, where the significance of different types of evidence in different theories is explored. In the framework I adopt, I argue that it is not a given that data from phonological acquisition can be taken as evidence for a phonological theory – if anything, any valid evidence that arises should be taken as an unexpected bonus, since the rapidly developing psychology of the child makes controlled delimiting of what is ‘phonological’ exceptionally difficult. Nonetheless, I conclude that, if treated cautiously, consideration of phonological acquisition is not only useful, but arguably essential to crafting an explanatory theory. In particular, *learnability* constraints are crucial in the domain of competence, whereas ‘third factor’ considerations like markedness are not directly required in the formal specification of theories of I-language². Following from this conclusion, in Section 3 I expound further on a specific theory of phonological architecture which builds on this epistemological foundation, centring around the Turing machine, an abstract model of computation (Turing, 1936). This is a direct expansion of Watumull’s (2012; 2015) Turing programme for linguistics, with expanded application to phonological computation, following the brief outline of Vaux & Watumull (2012). With this foundation in place, I look at a practical and novel application of the Turing computational framework, namely around the idea of ‘economy’, an oft-used but little-explained proposed constraint on language systems. By adopting measures of computational complexity typically reserved for the domain of computer science, various theories of phonology are evaluated within this novel framework.

¹ Note that Humboldt’s aphorism conflates *knowledge* of I-language (competence) with *use* of language (performance). This sidesteps the Aristotelian distinction between knowledge and use, as noted variously by Chomsky (see Chomsky 1986; 1995, p. 14; 2006, pp. ix, 15, 113; 2014, p. 4; 2021).

² Using the term ‘third factors’ in the sense of Chomsky (2005, p. 6): “[p]rinciples not specific to the faculty of language”, as opposed to the genetic endowment (first factor) and Primary Linguistic Data (the input; second factor). Whilst expressed most clearly by Chomsky (2005), it is worth noting that the interaction of the three factors is found in any biological system (Lewontin, 2000), noted for language at least as early as Chomsky (1965, p. 59).

2 Phonological Theory

Any theory of phonology attempts to resolve the tensions between competence and performance, description and explanation. This ultimately comes down to two fundamental questions, for which I set out to find an answer in this section: (i) what is a theory of phonology? and (ii) what makes said theory ‘explanatory’? The main focus will be on the developments relating Chomsky & Halle’s (1968) *SPE*-style rule-based phonology (RBP); Stampe’s (1979) Natural Phonology (NP); Optimality Theory (OT) as arbitrated by Prince & Smolensky (1993), McCarthy & Prince (1993), *inter alia*³; and Hale & Reiss’s (2008) Substance-Free Phonology (SFP).

To begin with, it is worth elaborating further upon the tension identified in the introduction between description and explanation: what would a non-explanatory yet perfectly descriptive theory, or analysis of a set of data, look like? As a foil, one might first identify what an analysis that is neither explanatory nor descriptive would look like. One could conceive of an ‘analysis’ that merely restates the data, quite literally, without any level of abstraction. This corresponds to the most basic level of theoretical adequacy identified by Chomsky (1964, p. 28f), *observational* adequacy. A theory that meets observational adequacy is hardly a theory at all, and barely worth attention except as a prerequisite for further, descriptive analysis. Chomsky (1964, fn. 1) does note, however, that this step is not entirely trivial: ‘the fact that a certain noise was produced, even intentionally, by an English speaker does not guarantee that it is a well-formed specimen of his language’. ‘[D]eviant utterances’, which may be entirely appropriate to the circumstance, must therefore be distinguished from ‘well-formed specimen[s]’. A significant factor in generating deviance is the volatility of *performance*, as distinguished from *competence* (Chomsky, 1986)⁴. This becomes particularly acute in the case of child language and as associated with learnability considerations, as will become evident in subsequent discussion.

Assuming that the level of observational adequacy can be met, the task is then to specify this data ‘in terms of significant generalizations that express underlying regularities in the language’ (Chomsky, 1964, p. 28); in other words, to provide a descriptive account. Two versions of a descriptive account for an elementary phenomenon of English phonology, the realisation of plural /-z/, are presented in (1) (courtesy of Vaux, p.c.), abbreviated in typical ways. Both contain generalisations and would predict the same typical observations of the phenomenon in question, and thus both appear to meet descriptive adequacy.

- (1) (a) /-z/ → [s] / { p t k ... } _
 /-z/ → [z] / { b d g ... } _
 /-z/ → [əz] / { s z ʒ ... } _
 (b) Epenthesis: Ø → [ə] / _ <C>#
 Voicing Assimilation: [-son] → [αvoice] / [-son, αvoice] _]_σ

Multiple questions then present themselves, all considered within the realm of *explanation*. They stem from the most fundamental: how does one select amongst extensionally equivalent descriptive theories?

³ For reasons of scope, discussion of extensions to the original OT model such as Stochastic OT (Boersma & Hayes, 2001) is mostly avoided, although see Section 4.

⁴ Another factor, more relevant to syntactic deviance, constitutes a major result of the Minimalist programme: deviance can be the result of an expression being well-formed at one syntactic interface but not the other. Confusion at the conceptual-intentional interface leads to nonsense sentences; confusion at the sensorimotor interface leads to ineffability. See Chomsky et al. (2019, p. 238). For a definition of the ‘interfaces’, which play only a limited role in the subsequent discussion, see Chomsky (2004, p. 106).

In turn, how do we account for the actual intuitions of the speaker? One means of narrowing the choices presented in (1) down would be to appeal to so-called *external* evidence (Kenstowicz & Kisseberth, 1979; Ohala, 1986). For example, one could perform an experiment with nonce words with non-English phonemes in word-final position to see how native English speakers choose to pluralise them – an extension of the ‘wug test’ (Berko, 1958). Another major consideration is that of *learnability*: a theory consisting of a large number of overly specific rules is evidently less learnable than a system in which the rules hang together in some reasonable way. One potential way of quantifying this is Minimum Description Length, viz. the fewer rules needed the better, a common metric within generative phonology, as will be discussed (cf. Kenstowicz, 1994). With all this in mind, (1b) appears to be the more explanatory account. Lastly, another consideration, brought to light in particular in the context of the Minimalist programme, is that of *evolvability*: UG should be as minimal as possible such that its rapid evolution appears plausible; in other words, the theoretical devices we are assuming to be instantiated biologically should be as limited as is viable. As Chomsky (2007) terms it, we should approach UG ‘from below’. Hence, the tension becomes apparent: with a descriptive account, the goal is to account for as large a proportion of the facts as possible; with an explanatory theory, a major driving force is to *reduce* the burden of this account to make it viable in the contexts of acquisition and evolution. An understanding of this tension proves critical in the evaluation of different theories that follows.

With this in place, I offer a brief overview of the central assumptions of the theories in question. The first eight chapters of Chomsky & Halle’s (1968) seminal rule-based analysis constitute the foundational document of the generative approach to phonology, which all the subsequent theories inherit from to at least some extent. The central hallmarks of the theory Chomsky & Halle (1968) present are as follows: (i) the grammar consists of rewrite rules which operate on sequences of phonemes, potentially transforming them into a different sequence; (ii) these rules apply cyclically; (iii) the input to the phonological component is a sequence of base forms known as *underlying representations*, originally stored in the lexicon and possibly manipulated by morphosyntactic processes⁵; (iv) the output of the phonological component is a *surface representation*, representing phonetic instructions of some sort. Of the other theories to be considered, SFP sticks most closely to this model, though with crucial differences that will become apparent. The case with NP is similar, although it introduces greater considerations of *markedness*, a concept that only features in the epilogue to *SPE*. Markedness, which has its roots in the traditional phonological study of the Prague School (Trubetzkoy, 1958 [1969]), is considered, in NP and in the epilogue of *SPE*, to be a potential source of evaluation between extensionally equivalent theories, and thus as a way of meeting explanatory adequacy. As Hume (2011) demonstrates, a universally applicable definition of ‘markedness’ is extremely difficult to parse from the literature, and the concept is perpetually confused, which makes it immediately problematic as an evaluation metric. Here, a somewhat vague definition, whereby something (a phoneme; a feature; a combination thereof) that is ‘marked’ is in some way less plausible or optimal than something unmarked, will suffice. As the final theory to be considered, OT makes a somewhat radical departure from assumption (i): the OT grammar does not consist of rewrite rules, but of *ranked constraints*. Instead of these being applied cyclically in sequence, as per assumption (ii), potential surface representations are rated against one another, based on how they fare against these constraints. This results in (depictions of) derivations taking on a unique, tabular format. I present a

⁵ Leaving aside the question of at exactly which point in the derivation phonological forms are introduced, cf. the Distributed Morphology literature (Halle & Marantz, 1993; Marantz, 1997).

simple example in (2), from Kager (1999, p. 15f), demonstrating how final devoicing of Dutch /bɛd/ ‘bed’ would be evaluated.

(2)

Candidates	*VOICED-CODA	IDENT-IO(voice)
a. [bɛt]		*
b. [bɛd]	*!	

Key: *VOICED-CODA can be read as ‘voiced obstruent in coda is marked; IDENT-IO(voice) means ‘corresponding input and output segments should match for [±voice]. The candidates are produced by GEN, the workings of which are not considered relevant for the evaluation (but cf. Section 4 below). Asterisks indicate violations of constraints. Candidates are in effect in a race: (b) loses, because *VOICED-CODA outranks IDENT-IO(voice), as indicated by the exclamation mark. See Kager (1999) for a comprehensive introduction to Classic OT.

Markedness considerations are even more tightly entwined with OT, as is evident from the nature of the constraints, and as will be critiqued below.

Returning now to the questions posed at the start of this section, it appears that question (i) (‘what is a theory of phonology?’) is perhaps a bit of a trick, seeing as there are two distinct yet interrelated answers, the result of an ambiguity which is made explicit at least by Chomsky (1965). The dichotomy is one of ontology versus epistemology, which can be paraphrased as ‘theory of a language’ versus ‘theory of language’. In order to be explanatory, a theory of language must explain how the learner acquires their theory of *a* language, the specific language acquired as triggered by the input. The stronger thesis, implied by the systematic ambiguity, is that these are identical (Chomsky, 1986, p. 3; cf. Miller et al., 2016). Acquiring an I-language is clearly a sizeable task for the learner; nevertheless, barring pathology, children acquire their native language with invariable success, rapidly, and on the basis of impoverished input (following the ‘poverty of the stimulus’ argument, Chomsky, 1986, p. 7). As part of their theory, all the theories discussed here include some innate, genetic component to aid the acquisition process, which will be referred to as Universal Grammar (UG), a traditional term adapted by Chomsky to a modern context (see Chomsky, 1964, p. 6; 1966). To tie this down to phonology specifically, it is assumed that phonology is a component of I-language, but as to where to draw the boundary with morphosyntax (as another part of I-language) on the one hand and phonetics (as an extra-grammatical domain) on the other remains initially ambiguous, as these boundary disputes are highly theory-dependent. For instance, RBP and SFP both necessitate a highly modular approach to I-phonology at least with respect to phonetics, especially the latter which separates the two entirely. They can assume the ‘full competence’ or ‘strong identity’ hypothesis (Smith, 1973; Hale & Reiss, 1998), whereby the child and adult are separated not by divergence in competence but only in performance, e.g., differences in production caused by articulatory difficulty due to the incomplete development of the child’s vocal tract. This is as compared with OT, for instance – in a 1988 paper McCarthy, who later became one of the founders of OT, makes his view clear that he sees incorporating phonetics into the phonology as not a redundant but a beneficial endeavour. NP is similarly ‘grounded’ in both phonetics and language acquisition, and OT inherits its approach in considering child phonology and its development into adult phonology evidence of there being ‘natural’ markedness constraints that persist in adult systems. As Stampe, the architect of NP, puts it, what the speaker brings to the language

(Stampe's 'processes') is just as important as what the language brings to the speaker (Stampe's 'rules'). The appropriate OT parallel is between W(ellformedness)-constraints and F(aithfulness)-constraints, respectively – in (2), *VOICED-CODA is a wellformedness constraint and IDENT-IO(voice) is a faithfulness constraint. On the simplest interpretation, $W \gg F$ (where \gg means 'outranks') in the initial constraint ranking. The raising of faithfulness constraints and the demotion of wellformedness constraints by the learning algorithm leads to marked ('ill-formed') structures eventually being output (Smolensky, 1996).

One (not in fact redundant) fact of language acquisition is thus that language is learnable – in the terms discussed above, our theory of phonology (as a component of I-language) must be explanatory. So, an explanatory theory must be 'grounded' in acquisition in this sense. So-called 'natural' theories like NP and OT descend in altitude by necessitating that I-phonology also account for markedness, in the form of innate phonological processes or constraints brought to the language by the learner, to borrow Stampe's phrasing. Indeed, this also represents a divergence between classic RBP and SFP: in the epilogue of *SPE*, Chomsky & Halle propose that the grammar also outputs language-specific acceptability gradings based on markedness. This parallels a similar idea in Chomsky's syntax at the time: the difference between the 'Core Grammar' and the 'Periphery' as expressed in Chomsky (1981), and the parallel idea in Chomsky (1986) that the output of the grammar is a pair <Output representation, Wellformedness>. In SFP as espoused by Hale & Reiss (2008) and in Samuels' (2009) Minimalist program for phonology, for instance, this formulation is removed from the theory of competence, paralleling developments in syntax (in which such properties arise at the interfaces, cf. Chomsky et al. 2019, p. 238). Instead of being part of the grammatical, computational, phonological module, wellformedness considerations arise from performance systems, including the phonetic component, following Anderson's (1981) line. Two divergent approaches to the facts of phonological acquisition are thus evident, regarding whether or not an explanatory theory of phonology needs to account for surface child phonology phenomena or not – indeed, whether 'child phonology' is phonology at all (cf. Smith, 1973; 2009).

This links to an idea from Hale & Reiss (2008), who frame three 'problems' confronted by the linguist, presented in (1).

- (3) (a) **The (weak) AI problem:** to create a model that is 'weakly equivalent' to language – i.e. a model that generates the same output strings as language.
 (b) **The Human's problem:** the learner acquires only one grammar⁶, rather than any number of other extensionally equivalent grammars.
 (c) **The Linguist's problem:** to work out how learners solve the Human's problem.

It is apparent that the Human's problem links up with the ontological question, 'what is the theory of a language?', and the Linguist's problem links up with the epistemological question, 'what is the theory of language?' Everyone has to figure out a theory of their language, whereas only linguists care about *the* theory of language. So where does the AI problem fit into this? In line with Hale & Reiss, I conclude that the AI problem has no bearing on an *explanatory* theory of phonology, and in turn on language acquisition problems generally. Machine learning AI, in the form of deep neural networks that generate

⁶ This wording to avoid the tautological 'the learner acquires only the grammars they acquire', despite the fact that retaining the latter would continue the ambiguity of my use of 'learner' to refer not just to first, but to bilingual first, and second language acquirers. For relevant comments regarding the endemic focus on the 'ideal' monolingual in much work in theoretical linguistics, cf. Bley-Vroman (2009, p. 180) and, correspondingly, Chomsky (1997, p. 128).

weakly equivalent output, are not ‘intelligent’ in a way that resembles human capacity, and they do not meet the criteria for explanation as defined *supra*. On the contrary, the Linguist’s problem is to create a theory equivalent to a *strong* AI with genuine human intelligence – the kind Turing envisioned, and that which will be returned to below, in Section 3⁷.

This has direct consequences for (classic) OT as a viable theory of I-language. Most strikingly, if a neutral/random ordering of the constraint set CON is innate (part of UG), CON must also be especially large and complex in order to account for phonological phenomena in every studied language, let alone every possible language or even every humanly computable language, the latter of which it is arguably impossible to come to a constraint set for anyway. Furthermore, it seems like an unnecessarily difficult task for the learner to continuously reorder CON as dictated by each parsed input string to the learning algorithm. This is difficult to reconcile with two of the aforementioned crucial facts of language acquisition – its speed and reliance on impoverished input. These two problems in particular are discussed in more detail in Section 4 below. OT’s learnability problems and extensional nature are taken by Hale & Reiss (2008) to demonstrate that OT has abandoned the endeavour of solving the Linguist’s/Human’s problem of finding an intensionally equivalent grammar, and instead can only solve the extensionally equivalent AI problem. In other words, they claim that OT is an inconceivable model of human phonological competence and is merely a point of mathematical interest.

Next, I move onto another set of ‘facts’ about phonological acquisition, namely empirical data from child production and perception. As explained in Section 1, following the Popperian ideal the use of this data as evidence depends strongly on the theory. Theories like SFP which put acquisition down to grammar-external performance factors make no use of child phonology data. NP and OT may then be able to gain empirical ground on SFP by killing two wugs with one stone⁸ – that is, accounting for both child phonology and adult phonology in the same model, as a unified, contingent phenomenon. If this can be done, it may be a sign that SFP is on the wrong track as a theory of I-language. Unfortunately, in OT’s case, the fatal theoretical flaws discussed above extend into the empirical domain. A well-attested fact of phonological acquisition is the spontaneous emergence of what Smith (1973) calls ‘puzzles’ – opaque chain shifts. Smith’s example from his case study of his son ‘A’ is as in (2):

- (4) ‘puzzle’ /pʌzəl/ -> [pʌdəl]
 ‘puddle’ /pʌdəl/ -> [pʌgəl]

Clearly A is able to produce the phone [d]; the issue is in the *mapping* from underlying to surface forms. This is trivial to account for in a rule-based system like RBP, adopted by Smith, or SFP (although I leave the issue of why such a rule would arise aside, cf. Bach & Harms, 1972). Classic OT, on the other hand, struggles. There is no constraint ranking which can create this kind of opacity (Hale & Reiss, 2008). This and other unnatural processes found in child language, such as the Click Girl (Bedore et al., 1994) who substituted clicks for consonants, but was able to rapidly unlearn this with instruction, is problematic for theories grounded in acquisition in this sense, and prefers a rule-based analysis over constraints, since rapid unlearning of an opaque rule requires only trivial adjustment. The reasoning behind W>>F and the focus on markedness thus grows increasingly shaky.

⁷ Note that the ‘Turing test’, described by Turing (1950), is in reality a poor measure of strong AI, as an extensionally equivalent weak AI would likely perform just as well. The early success of simple computational models that were able to ‘pass’ the test in certain settings, like Weizenbaum’s (1983) ELIZA, is clear evidence of this. Note further Turing’s (1950) own opinion, that: “The [] question, ‘Can machines think!’ [*sic*] I believe to be too meaningless to deserve discussion”. See the original Turing (1950) paper, and Watumull (2012) for further discussion.

⁸ With apologies for the gruesome image. The word ‘wug’ was coined by Berko (1958).

NP may be more promising in this regard, being even more explicitly grounded in child phonology, whilst not eschewing the notion of ‘rule’ entirely. Stampe claims that there are innate phonological processes that must be ‘suppressed’ by the child in the learning process. Some processes survive into the adult grammar and show up especially in casual (i.e., more ‘natural’) speech. One example of a process that is rife in both adult and child language is assimilatory nasalisation. Stampe cites a number of diary studies that show this; another example from Ferguson (1986) – [buã] for /pen/ – shows nasal assimilation followed by deletion of the final nasal, alongside voicing assimilation and some vowel quality changes which appear in part to be driven by coarticulation or other markedness effects. Other processes suggested by Stampe are flapping and flap-deletion, which show up in my dialect (an idiosyncratic Americanised facsimile of Standard Southern British English) and many American dialects of English, plus syllabification. Furthermore, NP processes apply non-linearly, randomly, sequentially, and iteratively – which allows them to derive a lot of different possible output forms even in adult speech. This can account for the difference between ‘formal’ speech patterns and casual speech, whilst simultaneously providing a full-competence style model for child phonology. Stampe exemplifies this using the example ‘divinity fudge’; I show a partial derivation (leaving aside stop aspiration) of a simpler example ‘carnival’ in (3), where non-asterisked forms are potential outputs:

- (5) /kɑrnɪvəl/
 Syllabification: *kɑ.r.nɪ.vəl
 Flapping: *kɑ.r.ɹ̩.vəl
 Nasal assimilation: kãĩ.ɹ̩.vəl
 Flap deletion: kãĩ.ɪ.vəl
 [...vowel assimilation, syllabification, vowel shortening ...]
 [kãɹ̩.vəl]

One can imagine a child utterance that continues the application of processes, further reducing the output. NP is thus able to derive child utterances using the same processes as present in adult grammar – what varies is the degree of suppression. Opacity effects can arise from rules (although again the ontology is murky), and Kiparsky’s feeding and bleeding orders are taken care of simultaneously. Another interesting consequence of this regards L2 acquisition: very briefly, Hungarian learners of L2 English appear to apply a process of final devoicing in their L2, despite it being an active process in neither the L1 nor the L2 (Altenberg & Vago, 1983). These kinds of emergent unmarked processes in interlanguage constitute very productive test cases for NP.

However, trying to account for the fact of variability found in child L1 and adult L2 production in the grammar also leads to problems for NP – not least, the sheer scale of variation found in acquisition data, both within and across individuals. I cited Ferguson’s child data for /pen/ earlier, but I should note here that [buã] was amongst ten different realisations of supposedly the same word in just a half hour period. Controlling for the fact that all of these data may well have been patched by the observer in making their phonetic transcription masks a potentially even greater degree of variation than is apparent. For Hale & Reiss (2008), this is a strong indication that acquisition-oriented theories like NP are on the wrong track, and that such variation is better attributed to performance constraints. As a final point on this matter, child phonology has in the past mostly been studied in terms of *production*, but only rarely in terms of *perception*. This is an unfortunate lacuna as, assuming that there is only one I-phonology for both perception and production, production-oriented theories like NP may turn out to suffer empirically. The work that has been done in this area, for instance by Jacques Mehler and colleagues

(cf. Gervain & Mehler, 2010, for review) certainly suggests that the child has a very early capacity for some kind of phonological processing that does not rely on production systems, which obscures the ontology for NP's 'ease of pronunciation' argument for processes. A further related issue is the stipulation of so-called 'richness of the base', a term coined by OT theorists but an idea that is also made explicit by Stampe (1979, pp. 18ff). The claim is that the actual representations the child constructs do not matter, since thanks to NP processes/OT constraints the grammar will output the same surface representation anyway, e.g. /kæ̃t/ vs /kænt/ for *can't*. This seems to eschew an important part of phonology vital to acquisition – the nature of phonological representations, the importance of which was noted even by McCarthy in 1988: 'if the representations are right, then the rules will follow' (p.84). This is not just a theoretical problem but feeds into an empirical gap too: a crucial finding of Smith's (1973) is that children don't recognise their own utterances played back to them. In other words, they can recognise that their productions do not match their (adult-like) representations – indeed, this 'metalinguistic' knowledge is well attested more broadly (see Gombert, 1997, for review). NP and OT cannot account for this, since they claim that the child's production is a direct output of the grammar, which should be recognised by the grammar as an output of said grammar. The more convincing hypothesis is that something is intervening between the grammar and the actual phonetic realisation – a hypothesis that fits well within SFP, where this 'something' is performance.

SFP's position on this data comes down to the phonology-phonetics boundary dispute alluded to earlier. Following a Minimalist view on language (e.g. Chomsky, 1995; Samuels, 2009) the grammar should be as minimal as necessary: everything that can be done by a grammar-external mechanism which is arguably needed anyway should be done by said mechanism. I-phonology is a computational device that algebraically transforms inputs to outputs which are then transduced into phonetic units at the phonetic interface, to borrow cognitive terminology from Pylyshyn (1984). On Watumull's (2012) interpretation, I-language can be seen as equivalent to the Turing machine. This emphasises the requirement for a highly formal, generative theory of phonology, which NP and OT reject. Substance-free rules can easily be implemented in a phonological Turing machine, as will be elaborated in the following sections. This also constrains the material involved in learnability, be this the requirement for innate features following Hale & Reiss's interpretation of the Subset Principle, or a neo-emergentist approach without innate features *per se* at all, with greater appeal to third factors (Chomsky, 2005; Samuels, 2009; Biberauer, 2019, in syntax). This offers a highly constrained perspective on phonological competence and its acquisition, which OT and NP sacrifice along with any hope of solving the Linguist's/Human's problem.

To sum up this section: language has to be acquired, and so a theory of I-language has to account for its acquisition. (Classic) OT is unable to account for acquisition – rather, it is a theory of 'E-phonology' which achieves surface predictive power at the expense of a plausible ontology. This hinges on the proposed answer to (i): a theory of phonology should be constrained to I-language, i.e. should solve the 'Linguist's problem'. In line with the Chomskyan worldview, the answer to (ii) ('what makes a theory of phonology 'explanatory'?') revolves around the issue of learnability. Learnability considerations should constrain a theory of phonology and are a useful heuristic for evaluation. On the other hand, 'facts of language acquisition' extends to a group of phenomena that can be labelled 'child phonology'. If the child's phonological competence is the same as the adult's, as claimed by Smith and Hale & Reiss, then so-called 'child phonology' is not phonology at all, but rather the result of grammar-external performance factors. Stampe takes the contrary view – that child phonology is a valid object of study, since for child phonology constrains adult phonology, not the other way around. A more modular approach to phonological theory has more potential for explanatory power, on the metrics of falsifiability and predictive power, in the spirit of the scientific programme. Thus, phonological theory

should not be ‘grounded’ as many have suggested, but rather should treat acquisition facts as interface considerations in order to reduce the explanatory burden of phonological competence to what is minimally required. Computational complexity is clearly one of these potential burdens, as will be explored in Section 4. With this theoretical foundation, however, it is first time to explore the concept of representation and its counterpart, derivation, in more detail, which will require a description of the phonological Turing machine.

3 The Phonological Turing Machine

I first offer a minimally sufficient definition of the linguistic Turing machine appropriate to the following discussion – for much more detail, see Watumull (2012; 2015).

A Turing machine is a mathematical object that describes a set of computable functions. It consists of three basic components: an unbounded bidirectional tape divided into discrete symbols; a read/write head that can move left and right along the tape; and an instruction table that interprets the symbols that can be read off the tape. During operation, the machine reads the symbol under its head, then the head can move left or right, or write a new symbol onto the tape at its position. This cycle continues indefinitely, or until a ‘halt’ instruction is read. Although apparently simple, Turing proved that this machine could perform any computable operation, given appropriate rules. Since a Turing machine can itself be defined mathematically, it is possible to construct a *universal* Turing machine, which takes the specification of a particular Turing machine’s instruction table as input on the tape. Such programs can consist of any computable operation, given an appropriate ruleset, thus there is no reason to assume that I-language, as a formal system, cannot be implemented on one. A phonological theory of I-language is a stipulation of what the specification, input, and output for the phonological Turing machine should look like, at a certain level of abstraction.

This has consequences for the way we look at phonological operations. To mimic McCarthy: if the derivation is correct, the representation will follow. One can look at the approach detailed above and contrast it with one like McCarthy’s in the following sense: representational theories (such as OT in phonology, perhaps Government & Binding in syntax following Epstein & Seely, 2002) assume that there is an undefined mechanism beyond the scope of the theories that generates candidate representations (cf. GEN in OT). Derivational theories make no comparable assumption, as they inherently must start each derivation from scratch, namely from whatever is taken as primitive. Nevertheless, Brody (2002) argues that it is impossible to escape representations entirely, as a derivational theory remains ‘weakly representational’, because the derivation needs to be able to ‘see into’ previous stages of the derivation, where each ‘stage of the derivation’ is a representation. I disagree, however, that this makes a derivational theory disfavoured, as it is really merely a paraphrasing of the fact that the derivation algorithm needs to be recursive, which has been assumed since the origin of generative grammar (Chomsky, 1957). Indeed, you can still do away with ‘representations’ altogether in a derivational theory, passing the input of the derivation for a particular representation as part of the input for another derivation instead of merely passing said pre-constructed representation. This notational game-playing results in derivation coming on top as epistemically prior to representation in a computational phonology. Once this has been rebutted, it is difficult to see any way of redeeming the representational approach within the formal component, given the specific constraints of explanation detailed above. This is not to depreciate representational approaches entirely – it is by all means useful to look at the output representation of a derivation, for example in an attempt

to work out what the nature of said derivation is. For instance, representations are a crucial source of data for the phenomenon of derivation, using the terms as defined in Section 1.

Despite this, Ian Roberts (p.c.) does highlight the potential importance of representation at the interface: for syntax, for instance, there has to be some kind of ‘representation’ at the output, in order that it be interpreted into truth conditions at the conceptual-intentional interface and into a phonological representation at the ‘sensorimotor’ interface (using terminology from Chomsky, 1995). The same applies to phonology, which effectively transduces a syntactic representation into a phonological one, which is subsequently interpreted by phonetics⁹. Nevertheless, conducive with the derivational approach, another concept can be exapted from computer science, namely that of *streams*. A stream is a serialised flow of information – in computers, bits are transferred more or less one by one – a representation would have to be ‘rebuilt’ step by step on the other side. This fits naturally into a Turing machine approach, in which effectively only one operation can occur at a time since there is only one read/write head, and it also conveniently parallels the idea of derivation. Information has to be passed around the brain, and if streams are the right answer – and considering their computational simplicity, they may well be – then continually constructing large representations is highly inefficient. This mirrors one of the motivations for phases (Chomsky, 2001), but importantly phases are not a conceptual necessity under the stream approach (see, for instance, the approach taken by Epstein et al., 1998). Empirical arguments in the domain of locality are the more relevant factor in deciding between phases and alternative approaches, which will be discussed little further here (cf. Chomsky, 2008; Rizzi, 2009; Samuels, 2009, for a phonological interpretation). Syntax can be argued to be a Turing machine, phonology can be seen as such, and the same may well go for the semantic-pragmatic component. In spite of the name, Discourse Representation Theory as defined by Kamp & Reyle (1993) is a highly formal, algorithmic theory that would be trivial to implement in a Turing machine. The representations it uses are built and interpreted stepwise from syntactic structure, and are thus perfectly compatible with the information stream approach.

Overall, the approach outlined in this section appears at least to be sufficient to describe I-language and all its putative components. Speculative reasons regarding to what extent it is necessary are the topic of the next section, alongside description of the possible theoretical benefits of its adoption.

4 On Complexity

Adopting this derivational, computational view also allows us to incorporate computational ideas about the nature of complexity. Complexity is an aspect of the phonological component that it is vital to understand, from the perspective both of acquisition and of everyday use of the language faculty. Acquisition and use of language is rapid and based on limited input, and this has led many researchers to adopt principles of ‘economy’ when deriving phonological theories. Unfortunately, whilst under many mainstream assumptions the most (formally) economical theory is considered the one most likely to be true (Kenstowicz, 1994, i.a.), the idea of economy is often defined weakly, if at all. I suggest that introducing a measure of complexity commonly used in computer science may go some way to resolving this, namely Big-O notation (cf. Knuth, 1997). This is used to represent how the time and space complexity of an algorithm varies with the size of the input(s). An algorithm that completes in constant time $O(1)$ does not vary with the size of the input; one that completes in linear time $O(n)$ varies in direct proportion with the size of the input; etc. Subroutines of different time complexity can

⁹ Following the architecture proposed by Hale & Reiss (2008). There are alternatives to this worldview, including those that consider phonetics/phonology to be non-distinct (Lieberman & Pierrehumbert, 1984; Ohala, 2005), although much of this may be considered definitional (Hale & Reiss, 2000).

be combined, resulting in higher complexities. For instance, a routine of complexity $O(n)$ that occurs n times has the complexity $O(n^2)$. Additionally, a polynomial is always represented simply by the degree of said polynomial (Knuth, 1997). If the aforementioned subroutine also contained a constant-time operation that needed to occur n times, its complexity would be $O(n(n+1)) = O(n^2 + n) = O(n^2)$ – that is, the addition of said operation makes no difference.

There are further levels of time and space complexity that can be described with Big-O beyond $O(1)$, $O(n)$, and $O(n^2)$. The most important options are summarised in Table 1, adapted from Huang (2020), alongside rough evaluations of the expected worst-case performance of an algorithm with such complexity.

Table 1: *Common Big-O complexities*

Notation	Description	Evaluation
$O(1)$	Constant	Excellent
$O(\log n)$	Logarithmic	Good
$O(n)$	Linear	Fair
$O(n \log n)$	Log-linear	Poor
$O(n^2)$	Polynomial	Very poor
$O(2^n)$	Exponential	Extremely poor
$O(n!)$	Factorial	Extremely poor

Co-opting this approach into phonological theory means is that we do not need to decompose the operations that we take as primitive, assuming that we can estimate the order of magnitude of their time complexity. This is the benefit of the abstraction: we do not necessarily need to deal with neurophysiologically plausible operations, which are far from being fully understood (although the stronger argument, supported by Watumull (p.c.), is that this abstraction is in fact very close to the reality). Instead, we deal with an abstraction of the architecture, the Turing machine, and build our theory of economy on top of this architecture, using time and space complexity in the form of Big-O notation. As a result, our phonology can contain any computational operation (since it is a Turing machine), *and* we have a means of evaluating which (constraints on) operations are more plausible, based on time and space complexity.

So, let's put this into practice. For simplicity, I primarily compare (classic) OT and the rule-based phonology espoused by Samuels (2009), which draws much from Hale & Reiss (2008) and also from Minimalist syntax (Chomsky, 1993 *et seq.*). In line with the descriptive-explanatory, epistemological-ontological tension detailed in Section 2, there are two important domains of each theory: everyday (adult) use of phonological computations, and corresponding mechanisms to acquire this competence.

Samuels (2009) proposes three arguably domain-general procedures needed for phonology in everyday use: SEARCH, which provides a means for a probe to establish a relation with its goal; COPY, which copies a feature from a goal to a probe; and DELETE, which removes an element from the derivation. Note that there is no ADD, which would violate the Inclusiveness Principle (Chomsky, 2001) and greatly add to the complexity of the derivation, since constraints on what can and cannot be added – and what exactly is the source of the additions – would be required¹⁰. In any case, COPY and

¹⁰ Chomsky (1995, p. 238) overtly claims that Inclusiveness is "radically false" at the sensorimotor interface. That this may not be necessary, as per Samuels' (2009) model, is therefore an interesting counter-hypothesis. Distributed Morphology (Halle & Marantz, 1993) introduces further complications here, but these lie beyond the scope of this article.

DELETE are both $O(1)$, whereas SEARCH is worst-case $O(n)$, since the algorithm may need to check every element sequentially to see if it can serve as a goal. Every phonological algorithm can use only these operations albeit in any permutation, so the analysis of the worst-case time complexity of a derivation in this theory needs to find the slowest possible combination of these operations. Significantly, combinations of COPY and DELETE do not actually contribute to complexity on this metric, since $O(1 + 1 + 1) = O(1 + 1) = O(1)$, i.e., constant time, following the simplification rule dictated above. SEARCH is more problematic – one can conceive of a particularly troublesome derivation where each element in the derivation serves as a probe and needs to use SEARCH to find its goal. The worst-case scenario here is n searches, each of a progressively larger set as each element gets added, up to a maximum of n . In other words, this is mathematically a series, so its time complexity can be written as $O(\sum_{r=1}^n r)$, which expands to $O(\frac{1}{2}n(n + 1)) = O(n^2)$. The worst-case time complexity of a derivation where every element can be a probe is therefore $O(n^2)$, which is very poor. This analysis makes it clear that placing a limit on n , such as with phase theory (Chomsky, 2000 *et seq.*; Samuels, 2009) and other theories of phonological locality (cf. Rose & Walker, 2011), is a computational imperative, lest the temporal burden of the derivation spiral out of control in quadratic time. Along these lines, the number of probes could also be limited. Indeed, this is the approach taken in Chomsky's (2008) model, where only syntactic 'phase heads' can serve as probes, entailing that each phase has only one probe. If such an analysis could be adapted to a Samuels-like phonological model, then the complexity of derivation is reduced to $O(n)$, equivalent to a single instance of SEARCH.

Moving onto OT, it must be mentioned that the computational complexity of OT has been much debated. For context, the use of asymptotic complexity in some form to analyse the complexity of theories of natural language dates back at least to Barton et al. (1987). It is also important to note that this approach does not come without criticism, as anticipated by Barton et al. (1987, section 1.4.1): 'Aren't the complexity results irrelevant because they apply to problems with arbitrarily long sentences and arbitrarily large dictionaries, while natural languages all deal with finite-sized problems?' Following the Turing programme for linguistics, as set out in Section 3, this is not a concern: the working, minimalist assumption is that linguistic competence *is* infinite, limited only by performance constraints. Idsardi (2006), adapting an earlier proof from Eisner (1997), presents a proof that the computational model provided by Classic OT is 'NP-hard', meaning that it is not computable in polynomial time on the size of the grammar. Kornai (2009) disputes the validity of the proof – to him, it has a 'fundamental flaw: [using] a mathematical method, asymptotic analysis, that relies in an essential fashion on the ability to create arbitrarily large problem instances' (Kornai, 2009, p. 702). Heinz et al. (2009) also dispute Idsardi's (2006) result, claiming that finite constraints on grammars eliminate the intractability problem. This, again, appears to hint at OT's concern with 'possible' languages as opposed to 'humanly computable' languages, as discussed in Section 2. To borrow Hale & Reiss's (2008) thought experiment: if only the performance systems of humans were to change suddenly, allowing computations of much greater time and space complexity to take place, would the computational procedure for human language be any different? Of course, by the very nature of the competence/performance distinction, it would not. This entails that the capacity for infinity be built into the grammar itself, a proposal that must be taken seriously. Indeed, similar arguments are presented by Roberts et al. (in press), and by Watumull (2015) for syntax. Returning to the OT issue, Heinz et al.'s (2009) arguments lose some of their weight, because they rely on a finitude that is incompatible with the Turing approach to phonological computation. Taking seriously the phonological enterprise as defined by Hale & Reiss (2008) makes such an approach especially appealing.

Even leaving these concerns aside, the OT algorithm intuitively appears slow compared to that of Samuels (2009). Since GEN is not considered part of the computation in OT, it will be assumed as $O(1)$, although this is of course a problematic omission from the theory, as discussed in Eisner's (1997) formalism. Each output of GEN then undergoes a constraint evaluation under EVAL. For m outputs and n constraints this algorithm takes $O(mn)$ in the worst-case scenario. Unlike in Samuels' theory, however, each instance of EVAL, for each output of GEN, can be calculated in parallel, as they are independent from one another until each has reached its end. One could argue that, with parallel operations, the time complexity could be reduced to $O(n)$. This kind of optimisation doesn't create a level playing field, however: we could easily apply parallel optimisation to Samuels' algorithm too, which might be able to reduce the time complexity. OT theorists may point to this as a drawback of the Turing machine approach – it only allows one operation to occur at a time. As Watumull (2012) explicitly points out, however, there is nothing inherently against there being *multiple* Turing machine instances in the mind, which interact in a kind of network. A Turing machine is, after all, simply a model for computation – it is clearly possible to have multiple computations taking place simultaneously. This remains a fundamentally different proposal from connectionism, which assumes instead that the nodes in the network are simple processing devices (Buckner & Garson, 2019).

Additionally, Big-O notation actually hides some of the nuances. The OT algorithm requires, without fail, $O(mn)$ consistently – effectively quadratic, which is very inefficient. The order of magnitude of operations is also vastly different: a very low estimate for the number of OT constraints needed (n) is 30, and GEN presumably needs about that many outputs, if not more, in order to cover every representational possibility. A more realistic estimate for the size of CON is given by Ashely et al. (2010) in their large-scale review of the OT literature, in which they conclude that there are at least 1,666 constraints – making this computation unreasonable, even leaving the acquisition algorithm aside. On the other hand, the locality constraints built into Samuels' RBP, in the form of phases, mean that n is probably never that large at all.

In light of these facts, OT is clearly more computationally complex than Samuels' brand of SFP. Assuming equivalent empirical coverage (descriptive adequacy), the demands of genuine explanation dictate that the computationally simpler theory prevail. This is not, of course, an innocent assumption, but a sufficient empirical review is beyond the scope of this article.

Traditional RBP, using *SPE*-style rewrite rules, isn't necessarily much better, despite at least being computable in polynomial time. Indeed, despite the appearance of being derivational, it is actually fundamentally different from Samuels' system, the latter being based on features and operations that build the derivation stepwise. Indeed, in some sense, Samuels' operations are more like Stampe's processes: they apply iteratively, sequentially, and locally. Traditional cyclic rules are linear, but necessarily run externally to the derivation, rather than from within. Each rule needs to search through the working representation in order to find its context (left-hand side). This ends up being just as computationally complex as OT in the fully developed adult system, merely replacing 'constraints' with 'rules'. Using Samuels' system appears much simpler from this perspective: the derivation only searches through (a limited portion of) the working representation for a single feature when triggered by SEARCH, instead of searching for a particular, potentially highly complex configuration for each rule in each cycle.

The facts become more interesting when looking at language acquisition, where one can argue that time and space complexity play an even greater role, because of the performance constraints imposed on the child. The goal of the child is to reduce the hypothesis space – to one, ideally. Problematically, it is a fact of our reality that there are always an infinite number of hypotheses

compatible with any dataset. The Halting Problem inevitably arises here: how does the child (in particular the phonological Turing machine) ‘know’ when it is finished, or even if it will finish? Following Roberts & Watumull (2015), in the tradition extending from Chomsky, in turn extending from Leibniz: ‘it cannot be proved that an “unsuccessful” search of the hypothesis space of possible explanations has been exhaustive’ (p. 220). Even more crucially, this applies to *both* the Linguist’s problem and the Human’s problem – in the same way that the Child needs UG in order to evaluate their theory of *a* language, the Linguist needs some way of limiting their possible theories of language. The logical conclusion for the child is the presence of a large epistemologically prior toolkit to deal with the input in order to establish the most likely hypothesis (Chomsky, 1986), and this is likely through some kind of Bayesian inductive reasoning (Tenenbaum & Griffiths, 2001) or some system compatible with Yang’s Tolerance Principle (Yang, 2016) – indeed, this is where the necessity of UG as defined in Section 2 above becomes evident. The Linguist, however, does not apparently have access to UG in order to solve the Linguist’s problem. One typical Chomskyan answer to this is presented by Ludlow (2011): the Linguist *does* have access to UG, in the form of intuition. The other forms of evidence presented are also relevant, as ways of ‘seeing into’ competence. The more radical suggestion advocated here is that consideration of computational complexity should be added to the list of sources of evidence. In the spirit of the biolinguistic programme, it seems relatively inoffensive to attribute this tentatively as a consequence of evolution. Time is a reasonable evolutionarily grounded pressure – fast communication saves lives. This also applies in the acquisition domain: rapid acquisition of language allows the organism to focus on other important things, like survival and procreation – having the LAD atrophy immediately could be beneficial evolutionarily. This also links to third factors like attention: since there is a practically unbounded amount of sensory information theoretically available to a human at any single moment, filters on this input are essential for learning anything. Consequently, the sooner that the detailed attention to language needed to learn it is taken out of the picture, the sooner other preoccupations can take hold. Thinking requires time and energy, both of which are naturally in limited supply. There is thus every chance that cognitive economy is a highly weighted constraint on the Bayesian algorithm (or such) that inductively hypothesises and evaluates a theory of a language. As Chomsky (2004) hypothesises, if the crucial aspect of language is Merge, then it is highly probable that one can go *beyond* explanatory adequacy in suggesting that at least this component of language *is* optimal, in line with the Strong Minimalist Thesis. Following this line of reasoning, it is not at all unreasonable, as done in Section 3, to propose the Turing machine abstraction, and thus the computational phonological component on top of this, especially seeing as researchers from otherwise in places diametrically opposed persuasions agree on phonology being necessarily computational (Berent, 2013; cf. Hale & Reiss, 2008; Samuels, 2009)¹¹.

In following, it becomes necessary to look at what computational operations are required of the child in each learning algorithm. On the one hand, OT champions so-called ‘factorial typology’: the number of possible languages is the number of permutations of the constraint set CON, which, assuming strict ordering only, is $n!$ ¹². With the earlier estimate for n as 30, the child is thus faced with an inconceivably huge innately endowed possibility set. With every new piece of input, CON is reordered accordingly, through an algorithm like that of Smolensky (1996). Reordering constraints in this way is

¹¹ A reviewer notes that there are of course interesting alternatives to this ‘mind-as-computer’ perspective. One example is that of *embodied cognition* (Shapiro, 2011), in which a full explanation of faculties of the mind/brain like language may necessarily need to refer to physical properties of humans, blurring the line between competence and performance and making the ontological nature of mathematical abstractions less clear. A full review of such alternatives is beyond the scope of this article, but see Reiss (2009) and Vukovic et al. (2017) for examples from phonology.

¹² With Stochastic OT (Boersma & Hayes, 2001), the picture is greatly complexified, as the strict ordering requirement is abandoned.

a relatively complex process: indeed, one could argue that it may even take factorial $O(n!)$ time complexity, as each constraint needs to be compared to all of the others in turn, every time a reordering takes place – this would therefore be completely intractable, although it is possible that this algorithm can be optimised. Idsardi’s (2006) proof directly concerns the ranking problem – assuming that CON is not set in stone, which it evidently cannot be for acquisition to take place, he proves that this ranking problem is indeed ‘NP-hard’, meaning that the solution does not belong to the class of algorithms computable in polynomial time. In other words, the ranking problem is computationally intractable. Furthermore, Hale & Reiss (2008) show that the proposed learning algorithm is empirically problematic. As an aside, it is likely that extensions to Classic OT, such as Stochastic OT (Boersma & Hayes, 2001) and the theoretical propositions of Jarosz (2019), heighten the computational requirements, as a consequence of the need to calculate weighted constraints, at least when computations are considered within the context of the phonological Turing machine (and not, for instance, a connectionist or neural network model, cf. Gallistel & King, 2010, for general comments on computation and connectionism).

I propose that there are at least two further tentative ways out here. Firstly, eliminate the innateness requirement of CON – constraints are then acquired along with their ranking. This radical step cannot be taken lightly and comes with its own whole host of problems. One is that it is difficult to constrain a theory of emergent constraints, since wellformedness constraints are inherently defined negatively – as Reiss (2008) posits, what’s to stop a child positing the constraint NOBANANA? Whilst this particular example is evidently *reductio ad absurdum*, it is undeniable that an infinite set of constraints can be proposed to account for any input data set – e.g., **#hta* is valid for English but surely inconceivable as a part of the grammar. This option to save OT thus eliminates any potential explanatory power, by virtue of the nature of language acquisition. It is also not clear whether this solves the complexity issue – clearly, the space complexity is reduced, as ‘unused’ constraints will never need to be postulated, but the generation of constraints appears very similar to the NP-hard problem proposed by Idsardi (2006). The second way I can conceive of saving OT, which is at first appearance more modest, is to constrain the learning algorithm to make more conservative adjustments to CON at a time, which do not involve factorial comparison. It is difficult to see, however, how factorial typology holds up, if fundamental alterations such as these are required in the name of computational economy. These facts appear especially problematic when contrasted with parametric systems which instead assume a set of binary parameters within UG, which would give a maximum of 2^n possible languages. This is still large, but an exponential typology is far easier to deal with than OT’s factorial one. Furthermore, optimisations can be made to an exponential typology, following for instance Elan Dresher’s Contrastive Hierarchy (Dresher, 2015) and Ian Roberts’ Parameter Hierarchy (Roberts & Holmberg, 2010; Roberts, 2019), by assembling parameter hierarchies in the form of binary branching trees defined by implicational relations. Such a decision tree can be easily implemented as a conditionally branching Turing program, i.e. ‘If C go to X , else go to Y ’, where X and Y are positions on the tape. Indeed, a particular implementation of the type of parameter hierarchy advanced by Roberts & Holmberg (2010) is provided by Bazalgette (2015) for certain syntactic parameters.

In any case, both approaches require some definition of the ‘features’ which populate the constraints or the parameter hierarchy. Much substance-free work (*pace* Reiss, 2017) allows for the existence of so-called emergent features, which allow features to be generated as necessary by the child to account for the input; an example implementation of this is presented by Mielke (2008). Following this line, a template system for emergent features is incredibly useful: it is a given that a strict template drastically reduces a hypothesis space, with exceedingly minimal overhead since the template itself is

typically fairly simple. This is thus very much in line with Biberauer (2019), who for syntactic features proposes the template $[uF, iF]$, where uF is a feature uninterpretable at the interfaces and iF one that is interpretable (see Chomsky, 1995, p. 277 for a technical description of ‘interpretability’). Phonological features could have their own template, or, perhaps more optimally, they could even recycle the syntactic template, or the syntax could recycle a phonological template. The latter suggestion plays into a crucial discussion on the ontology of language: are the most important resources available to the child and the clues they look for syntactic, phonological, or conceptual-intentional? There is almost certainly, and perhaps necessarily, evidence for all three, and so perhaps the feature template is indeed something much more fundamental. Instead of interpretability being defined at the sensorimotor and conceptual-intentional interfaces used by syntax, the relevant interface for phonology is, naturally, the phonetics – or, more precisely, the device which *transduces* the phonology to a form legible by the phonetic module. It is entirely conceivable that some features are uninterpretable in this sense since phonology under SFP is arbitrary and symbolic. Nevertheless, this is likely an empirical matter to decide. The ‘recycling’ option will prove especially appealing if it appears to capture templatic effects across domains, which would appear to suggest that the broad concept of ‘features’ does have some kind of fundamental basis as a unified phenomenon. This would be particularly important for the Turing machine approach, since, as discussed for Samuels’ SFP above, features are often the trigger for computations, and it would also reveal something more widely about the computational capacity of the mind if this theory is on the right track.

5 Conclusions

A theory of phonology – indeed any theory of I-language – must be epistemologically adequate, in that it must *describe* the universal human knowledge of language, and individual human knowledge of *a* language. It must also be ontologically adequate, being able to *explain* how this knowledge is acquired by the child, through some combination of genetics, emergence, and inductive Bayesian learning. It must predict the *phenomena* involved in language, which may be obscured by the data and the theories imposed thereupon. The prediction of the theory presented from Section 3 onwards is that the Turing machine is a sufficient and arguably necessary abstraction of the computational procedure for phonology, and for language, and indeed for the mind generally. The evidence needed to test this prediction will come from considerations of child language acquisition, for instance as presented in Section 2, as well as from evolutionary considerations, as are popular within the biolinguistic programme. Following Chomsky (1993 *et seq.*) there is increasing evidence that the language faculty is in some sense optimal. Accepting this conclusion has significant implications for the evaluation of theories of this faculty. Section 3 advocates a strongly derivational approach, and the suggestion in Section 4 is that theories should consider the implementation of the primitive operations and data structures they propose in the Turing machine. Computational complexity would be the evaluation metric between different options. Samuels’ (2009) theory is taken as a case study in phonology, as it makes use of clearly defined computational procedures. It would be rash to suggest that this is the most optimal theory, however, and this is in part due to ambiguity about the precise nature of ‘features’. The apparent potential of this approach and the corresponding philosophical deficit in OT directly contradicts McCarthy’s (1988) proclamation that rules follow from representations; on the contrary, the clearer the picture of the operations and derivational procedures used by the mind, the clearer the picture of the actual representations they build will become.

6 References

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Positioning Theory as a Tool for Analysing Working Class Identities: Angela Rayner in Interview

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Abstract. In recent years, narrative has emerged as a ‘prime vehicle’ through which speakers are able to construct identities (de Fina, 2015a, p. 351). This research utilises positioning theory (Davies & Harre, 1990, p. 48) in its three-tiered adaption to the field of narrative (Bamberg, 1997, 2004) to explore how one speaker in particular, Deputy Leader of the Labour Party, Angela Rayner, negotiates a sense of self in situated narrative interaction. Previous research has extensively explored each ‘level’ of positioning in depth (see de Fina’s, 2013, investigation of conflict narratives told by Latin American immigrant women, for example). This research instead focuses on how the interplay at different levels assists the speaker in arriving at a reflexive, locally contingent and evolving working class identity. Positioning framework facilitates sophisticated, connected exploration that allows for researchers to elegantly bridge the gap between micro- and macro-level phenomena, imposing neither a top-down nor a bottom-up imposition as the speaker orients to master discourses when and only when relevant. The stories told by Rayner and the ensuing analyses therefore work as a model for future research aiming to describe the relationship individuals have with Discourse and ideology, and the construction of identity within these forces.

Plain English Abstract. In recent years, the field of narrative has emerged as a way in which speakers are able to construct their identities (de Fina, 2015a, p. 351). This research explores identity through the lens of positioning theory (Davies & Harre, 1990, p. 48), a three-tiered framework which has later been adapted to apply more readily to the field of narrative (Bamberg, 1997, 2004). The paper focuses on how one speaker in particular, Deputy Leader of the Labour Party Angela Rayner, negotiates a sense of self in an interview context. Previous research has extensively explored each ‘level’ of positioning in depth (see de Fina’s, 2013, investigation of conflict narratives told by Latin American immigrant women, for example). This research instead focuses on the relationships between the levels and explores how the speaker establishes her reflective, context-dependent, and evolving working class identity. Positioning theory facilitates sophisticated connections that allow for researchers to elegantly bridge the gap between micro- and macro-level phenomena, imposing neither a top-down nor a bottom-up imposition as the speaker draws upon master discourses when and only when relevant. The stories told by Rayner and the ensuing analyses therefore work as a model for future research aiming to describe the relationship individuals have with discourse and ideology, and the construction of identity within these forces.

Keywords: positioning; discourse; identity; ideology; working class

1 Introduction

Narratives function as important sites for studying how individuals construct identities. Positioning theory provides one such avenue through which to explore said identities and posits that the narrator takes part in positioning activities ‘whereby selves are located in conversations as observably and subjectively coherent participants in jointly produced story lines’ (Davies & Harre, 1990, p. 48). In the years following Davies and Harré’s early work, positioning theory has been adapted by various researchers to apply more readily to the study of narrative (Bamberg, 1997, 2004; Wortham, 2000; Bamberg and Georgakopoulou, 2008).

Bamberg (1997) proposes that when telling a story, the narrator constructs her identity by positioning herself on three levels: ‘vis-à-vis other characters in the world of the story, vis-à-vis interlocutors in the storytelling world, and vis-à-vis herself’ (de Fina, 2013, p. 43). This article explores

how one individual in particular, Deputy Leader of the Labour Party, Angela Rayner, navigates multiple aspects and formations of her identity across these three levels in an interview for the daytime television programme, *This Morning*.

Stories told by working class people have long been neglected and undervalued in academic research and wider society alike (Strangleman, 2018). By exploring the autobiographical outputs of Rayner, an individual with a working class background, this research aims to address this fact and redirect academic efforts (much like the work done by Freeman, 2010; Reay, 2002; and Hey, 2003). As Rayner is a politician, she is no longer considered working class in the economic sense. However, the speaker indicates that she still identifies with working class culture and identity (she implies that it hasn't been 'taken out' of her, line 60). This endurance of working class identity is present in other individuals who operate in traditionally middle or upper class contexts (such as politics or academia) with similar roots (Lucey et al., 2003; Reay, 2004). Furthermore, some of these individuals also experience feelings of conflict, in that at times, they can feel detached from their past selves and do not identify with the characteristics of their new surroundings (Hey, 2003; Mahony & Zmroczek, 2005). By analysing Rayner's past and present stories, we are able to explore how those from minorities navigate (accept or reject) the positions afforded to them by existing dominant narratives and assess how their identities evolve (Saini, 2022).

2 Literature Review

As established, Bamberg proposes that the narrator positions herself at three levels. At the first level, the narrator constructs an image of herself in the storyworld (elsewhere 'taleworld' – Georgakopoulou, 2008, p. 9), assigning 'protagonists and antagonists', proposing 'evaluations of such characters' actions', and 'distributing responsibilities' (de Fina, 2015, p. 360). Further positioning techniques at level one include describing attributes (Kitzinger & Wikinson, 2003), labelling emotions (Bamberg & Georgakopoulou, 2008), and assigning degrees of agency (Bamberg, 2011). The second level explores the interactional influences on storytelling and the actions taken in conversation, simultaneously examining how stories are told and what motivates their inclusion in a given scenario. Actions at this level can include justifying (Stokoe & Edwards, 2006), seeking advice (Bamberg, 2004; Korobov & Bamberg, 2004), defending, and flirting (Stokoe & Edwards, 2006) – to name a few. Lastly, level three responds to the question, 'who am I?' (Bamberg, 1997, p. 337). This level transcends the moment-by-moment, local interaction and extends to 'how the narrator positions a sense of self/identity with regards to dominant discourses or master narratives' (Bamberg & Georgakopoulou, 2008, p. 385). Accordingly, identity is conceptualised as a process taking place in specific concrete interactions, as a 'constellation' of selves as opposed to an essentialist, unwavering singularity, and as a negotiation with wider social and discursive phenomena (de Fina, 2013, p. 42).

The stratification of positioning across three levels prompted de Fina (2013) to describe positioning theory as a 'middle ground' between conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis, analysing stories in a clause-by-clause fashion and relating these findings to broader, pre-existing Discourses and ideologies. Whilst levels are distinct and have the potential to contradict one another (ibid), Bamberg (2004, p. 336) describes how they interact as follows: 'By talking about others and arranging them in narrative space and time (level one), and by talking to others in the here and now (level two), narrators engage in the creation of a sense of (them as) selves (level three)'. Despite these assertions, Bamberg admits that making the practical distinction between levels one and two is not straightforward (Bamberg, 2004), with McQuillan (2000, p. 12) arguing that the symbiotic relationship

between the telling and the tale renders any attempted separation or distinction inappropriate. Others praise this distinction, arguing that the double temporal indexicality of telling vs tale allows for the analyst to explore notions such as constancy and/or change (Bamberg, 2011). This is especially poignant given that other identity related narrative frameworks (Membership Categorisation; for example, Sacks, 1972; Schegloff, 2007) may miss a level of nuance that accompanies temporal or attitudinal changes. Positioning theory has thus been praised for its ability to analyse identity as it is constructed by the individual, identifying enduring properties without an essentialist or top-down imposition (Bamberg & Georgakopoulou, 2008).

Further criticisms include the exact mechanisms by which level three phenomena, that is, ‘big D’ Discourses or ‘master narratives’ (Bamberg & Andrews, 2004; Mishler, 1995) are oriented to, given the long standing difficulty in describing the relationship between micro and macro level structures (de Fina, 2008). Indeed, the question remains: how exactly can one illuminate the other? Researchers have proposed various answers to this question. Bamberg and Georgakopoulou (2008, p. 391), for example, suggest that speakers include these dominant discourses in narration by ‘making them relevant’ to the interaction. However, as de Fina (2013) highlights, this is difficult to identify and difficult to measure empirically. Heritage and Clayman (2010, p. 20) suggest that these discourses are ‘talked into being’ during local action. In this way, discourses factor in the creation of positions in an inductive/abductive manner, following the theoretical tenets of Conversation Analysis (CA) and rejecting any top-down impositions that assume discourses and social structures to be automatically present and relevant (Benwell & Stokoe, 2006), as is the case in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA; Wodak, 2013).

The types of study that utilise positioning theory when studying narrative vary in a number of areas. For example, some studies focus solely on positioning at one level, such as de Fina’s 2013 investigation of conflict narratives told by Latin American immigrant women. Other studies focus on the interaction between levels (Zimmerman, 1998; see Depperman’s (2015) investigation of the turn-by-turn relationship between levels one and two, for example). Different still are the kinds of narratives studied, with some researchers working within a small stories paradigm (Clifton, 2014) and others conceiving of narrative in a Labovian, grand sense (Sargeant et al., 2016). We thus arrive at a varied and vast field of study. For instance, Wortham and Gadsden (2006) have examined how working class, African American fathers navigate masculinity through a series of semi-structured interviews; Saini (2022) utilises the episodic narrative interview to explore one woman’s experience with care work in the Global South; and Bamberg (2004) investigates how adolescent males collaborate in ‘slut shaming’ their female peers during a group discussion. This research follows previous research in varying the level of focus, characteristics of the speaker(s), and types of narrative studied, ultimately centring on the prominent political figure, Angela Rayner.

As mentioned, the types of stories elicited in naturalistic interviews can vary greatly. Defining and classifying stories is a hotly and extensively debated topic, the likes of which fall outside the remit of this research (Ryan, 2007). For the purposes of this article, narratives are conceptualised, more as a tool of interpretation (de Fina et al., 2006) than as a phenomenon abiding by formal criteria, though many stories identified can be classified as either Labovian (Labov & Waletzky, 1967) or ‘small’ (Georgakopoulou, 2007). At times, Rayner displays narratives that can be identified as Labovian in that they feature ‘a coherent temporal progression of events... A plotline that encompasses a beginning, a middle, and an end, conveys a particular perspective, and is designed for a particular audience who apprehend and shape its meaning’ (Ochs & Capps, 2001). In other instances, Rayner’s narratives are markedly non-canonical, narratives which have largely been neglected in the wake of the narrative turn (Georgakopoulou, 2006). These are classified as ‘small stories’ and have been defined as ‘an umbrella-

term that captures a gamut of under-represented narrative activities, such as tellings of ongoing events, future or hypothetical events, shared (known) events, but also allusions to (previous) tellings, deferrals of tellings, and refusals to tell’ (ibid, p. 123). Accordingly, working within a small stories paradigm (Georgakopoulou, 2007) is also suited to this research.

3 Method

Titled ‘From Working Class Carer to Deputy Leader: Angela Rayner on Her Rise Into Politics’, this dataset is a thirteen minute long interview (13:36) in which presenters Holly Willoughby and Phillip Schofield probe Rayner about her past experiences and political life in the present. This example can best be described as a blend between an autobiographical narrative interview (Svašek & Domecka, 2020) and an informal conversation, providing the researcher with the opportunity to analyse situated narrative interaction.

Bamberg (2004) proposes, when analysing stories using the positioning framework, working through the different levels chronologically, starting at level one. This progression is loosely followed here, whilst also exploring how the levels interact with each other simultaneously. As positioning theory acts as a middle ground between conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis, the methodological process requires analysing the narrative output in a sequential, clause by clause manner (Sacks et al., 1974), whilst also drawing on cultural and social knowledge (Benwell & Stokoe, 2006).

The interview was transcribed using the notations outlined in Davidson (2010, p. 120-121), whilst also utilising Gardner’s (2001) suggestion to create specific symbols for the data when necessary. Where new symbols are created, their inclusion is justified in Table 3. The full transcript of the video features in Appendix 7.2.

4 Analysis

4.1 Level One

Bamberg (2004, p. 336) describes Level One positioning as ‘talking about others and arranging them in narrative space and time’. Table 1 identifies the narratives Rayner tells, and Table 2 describes the characters present across the various storyworlds.

Table 1: *Narratives identified*

Story type	Story structure	Presence in data	Line number(s)
Anecdote 1	An anecdote is a story aiming to invoke an emotional response from the audience (Martin and Plum, 1997). The structure is as follows: Orientation// Remarkable	<p>Orientation: ‘mixing with people who went to private education who have got (.) loads of wealth’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The listener infers that proceeding information is likely to be related to wealth disparities, given that Raynor mentioned growing up on a council 	24-33

	Event// Reaction// Coda.	<p>estate seconds prior.</p> <p>Remarkable Event: “I remember having a joke once with one of the MPs talking about the (.) issues on our estate because there was um (.) ca – um horses churning up the grass on the estate and he went ‘oh we have llamas on our estate’ I’m like no I’m talking about the <u>council</u> estate”</p> <p>Reaction: ‘[((laughing)) oh my god]=’</p> <p>Coda: ‘=in the wild so it was ya know those moments where two worlds [collide]’</p>	
Labovian Narrative 1	<p>Abstract</p> <p>Orientation</p> <p>Complicating Action</p> <p>Resolution</p> <p>Evaluation</p> <p>Coda</p>	<p>Abstract: ‘but I just learned in a different way’</p> <p>Orientation: ‘when I was early (.) erm in my I – when I was younger’</p> <p>Complicating Action: ‘I wasn’t on education my mum had bipolar and was very depressed so I was looking after ma mum and things like that’</p> <p>Resolution: ‘so education wasn’t (.) drilled into me as important’</p> <p>Evaluation: ‘but (.) that doesn’t mean to say that I was (.) less intelligent and I think (.) a lot of people think that you have to speak a certain way (.) or you don’t talk about those things cause you’re ashamed or you’re embarrassed by it whereas I think we should talk about it [more]’</p> <p>Coda: –</p>	71-75
Labovian Narrative 2	<p>Abstract</p> <p>Orientation</p> <p>Complicating Action</p> <p>Resolution</p> <p>Evaluation</p> <p>Coda</p>	<p>Abstract: ‘one of the biggest challenges that I found’</p> <p>Orientation: ‘when I had Ryan’</p> <p>Complicating Action: ‘I ended up on income support’</p> <p>Resolution: ‘now obviously I – I pay my taxes I’m a ya know high income earner... I managed to you know get on and achieve’</p> <p>Evaluation: ‘I felt humiliated and ashamed to ask for help and people that use foodbanks now (.) it’s that humiliation it’s not a lifestyle choice but some people think (.) oh it’s a lifestyle choice to do that you know you’re</p>	90-102

		responsible and (.) the the difficulties and the challenges I had (.)' Coda: 'I just wanted to be a good mum'	
Hypothetical Small story	N/A – whilst Georgakopoulou (2007) outlines that hypothetical stories are a type of small story, they do not describe a structure.	'if – if you've got no money at the end of the month and then your fridge breaks down your fridge freezer (.) you can't get credit (.) to get a fridge freezer (.) it's impossible and you don't (.) have (.) a couple of hundred quid in the bank= and that pit (.) in your stomach that (.) feelin of absolute dread (.) what am I gonna do (.) the panic (.) and I think sometimes people in positions of (.) influence like um (.) politicians they've never felt that'	106-118
Shared ('known') Stories – Small story	Temporal adverbial indicates speaker is starting a narrative	'I mean there are times when you (.) haven't held back (.) I mean you uh (.) said in October 2020 you used the word scum (.) in reference to the Tory MP Chris Clarkson in the midst of a commons debate (.) late night event in September '21 at the Labour Party conference you described the Conservative government as homophobic (.) racist (.) misogynistic and vile (.) a bunch of scum (.) now they are big they're big words (.)'	122-128
Labovian Narrative 3	Abstract Orientation Complicating Action Resolution Evaluation Coda	Abstract: 'well it goes back to what I said before about bein' (.)' Orientation: 'growin up on the council estate (.) bein a ginger kid (.) who was poor (.) and then havin' a child when I was a child myself at [sixteen (.)] um (.)' Complicating Action: 'I already had that level of abuse and that stigma (.) and I always I I felt that there was (.) um (.) y'know I was bullied and everythin' else so (.)' Resolution: 'what I get now doesn't (.) doesn't impact on me because I think (.) I'm (.) I'm worth it (.) and' Evaluation: 'that's why I say what I say in the way I do because I want the young people of today (.) and the young (.) single	181-191

		<p>mums like me (.) to know that they are absolutely worth it (.) don't let anyone make you feel like you're not valid because you absolutely are'</p> <p>Coda: –</p>	
Anecdote 2 /Projection	Orientation// Remarkable Event// Reaction// Coda.	<p>Orientation: 'I was a home help (.)'</p> <p>Remarkable Event: 'I saw people in big huge houses (.) who'd live in the kitchen (.) with a little stove on for an hour (.) in the cold (.)'</p> <p>Coda: 'I don't want any older person in our country thinkin' they have to do that and they will do that'</p> <p>Reaction: 'yeah'</p>	254-257

Table 2: *Characters present in the storyworld(s)*

Narrative	Characters present
Anecdote 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rayner when she first entered parliament 2. A privately educated colleague that she met in her first week there
Labovian Narrative 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rayner's 'younger' self, aged sixteen (inferring from instances elsewhere in the interview) 2. Rayner's mother
Labovian Narrative 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sixteen year old Rayner 2. Rayner's son, Ryan 3. Plural 'you' – those in a position of financial insecurity
Hypothetical Story	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plural 'you' – those in a position of financial insecurity
Shared World (known) Stories	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rayner in 2020 2. MP Chris Clarkson 3. Rayner in 2021 4. The Conservative Government
Labovian Narrative 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sixteen year old Rayner
Anecdote 2/Projection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rayner prior to being a politician

1.1.1. *Responsibility, Agency, and Emotion*

Rayner attributes various qualities to the characters in her stories, one of which being responsibility. At sixteen, she cares for both her mother and her son. In Labovian Narrative 2, she absolves working class members of responsibility for their financial insecurity, stating ‘it’s not a lifestyle choice but some people think (.) oh it’s a lifestyle choice... you’re responsible’ (lines 96-97). Rayner is therefore seen to be personally responsible for the wellbeing of others, but rejects that working class people should be held responsible for their hardship(s).

In this same Labovian Narrative, Rayner describes agency in two ways – firstly, she describes being agentic in that she managed to overcome hardship and ‘get on and achieve’ (line 102). She also cites an initial lack of agency in that she relied on the welfare system, something which she was uncomfortable with (‘I wanted to go to work... I wanted to help ...and I wanted to do the right thing’ – line 100). In Labovian Narrative 1, her agency is curtailed by her responsibilities, in that caring for her mother impacted her ability to achieve in educational settings. Agency is further featured in the Hypothetical Small Story, where Rayner describes working class people experiencing food insecurity as unagentic, in that they are unable to carry out the actions that would better their situation (in this instance, buying a new fridge freezer). In the Shared Story, she is described by Phillip as agentic, in that she uses strong language at her will.

In the narrative output, Rayner states that she felt humiliated and ashamed. She also describes characters in Labovian Narrative 2, those relying on foodbanks, as feeling humiliated. Within her evaluations of her stories, Rayner describes her opinion that ‘people’, i.e., wider society, perceive of class struggle (such as relying on foodbanks and the welfare state; Wunderlich & Norwood, 2006) as something to be embarrassed of. Rayner also describes the feelings of fear and dread that arise from not being able to feed your family (felt by many working class people, as demonstrated by her use of the plural ‘your’) that is present in the Hypothetical Small Story, and points out that many wealthy MPs in parliament have not felt those same feelings. In sum, Rayner positions characters in her grand, personal narratives as well as characters in her small stories by describing their agency, responsibility, and the range of emotions felt.

4.2 Level Two

Narratives have the potential to be shaped by their interactional contexts. Schofield tells two Shared Stories (stories known to all interlocutors prior to the telling) in which Rayner is accused of using ‘big’ language (line 127). During this interaction, Rayner mentions Boris Johnson’s lack of apology for his comments about racial minorities, homosexual men, and women. Schofield responds to this by stating that Rayner has not apologised for her language, either, implying that he feels that she should. This in turn implies a level of wrongdoing, a moral evaluation, which Rayner rejects. This is demonstrated at level two through the conversational actions taken by both parties in their speech. Phillip presents a statement, which Rayner then defends (‘the language that Boris Johnson used... has been racist it has been homophobic it has been misogynistic’, lines 150-151). This interaction underscores how positioning amongst interlocutors is a negotiation.

In her first narrative, Anecdote 1, Rayner describes a humorous situation whereby herself and a wealthier colleague have different understandings of the word ‘estate’ (lines 27-28). This positions her wealthy colleague as out of touch with the general public and Rayner as in touch, by contrast. Telling a humorous anecdote constructs Rayner as a politician that employs informal and relaxed conversation styles, further positioning her as a woman of the people. She also describes, as detailed at level one,

how politicians in the telling world have not experienced financial insecurity and its effects – a contrast to her own experience. It could subsequently be the case that Rayner utilises the affordances of the interactional setting, a wider audience of *This Morning* watchers and potential voters, in positioning herself as an in touch, approachable, and electable politician. Indeed, Gee (1999, p. 13) argues that this kind of level two positioning – describing a past version of oneself within the here and now, allows the speaker to construct the ‘kind of person’ one wishes to convey to the audience. This is one example of how the types of stories and characters within those stories are adapted to the situated interaction.

Rayner carries out many communicative actions in this interview. As mentioned, she defends her lack of apology for her strong language during her interaction with Phillip. At other times, she defends working class people and justifies their actions by saying that using foodbanks is ‘not a lifestyle choice’. Rayner uses further defensive positioning when discussing reliance on the welfare state, saying that she ‘just wanted to be a good mum’, and that she ‘wanted to go to work... wanted to help and... wanted to do the right thing’ (line 100). Rayner justifies her lack of formal academic education by outlining that she helped look after her mother who has mental illnesses. She then defends the conditions that her caring responsibilities left her with, saying ‘that doesn’t mean to say that I was less intelligent’ (line 75). The communicative action(s) taken in these narratives are primarily those of defence and justification.

Rayner frequently tells stories of a similar structure. She tells a Hypothetical Story, in which she puts herself in the shoes of somebody on the breadline, describing how many people cannot afford for incidents such as your fridge freezer breaking to happen. In the Projection, she again looks to the future, describing how she has seen elderly people heat one room of their house with a stove, and how ‘they will do that [again]’ (line 257). These particular types of stories demonstrate a consideration for the future well-being of working class people. This, accompanied by the fact that she often plays the role of advocate (by telling stories of struggle that are not her own), positions Rayner as a politician aligned with the needs and struggles of the working class. Indeed, one of the strengths of positioning theory is its ability to convey characteristics over time (Bamberg, 2011). The double temporal indexicality of telling vs tale has allowed for Rayner to convey a sense of constancy – whilst she is no longer working class in the economic sense, her interests remain aligned with working class needs and identity. This has been demonstrated here through the types of stories she tells as well as the communicative functions employed.

4.3 Level 3

The positions Rayner assigns to characters in her storyworlds and the range of actions taken in conversation frequently demonstrate an interplay between positioning at the first two levels and positioning at level 3, that is, an orientation to master narratives. Starting at level one, Rayner discusses responsibility – how she performed her caring duties and the level of responsibility she assigned to food bank users. By arguing that working class people are not responsible for their own poverty, Rayner orients to and subsequently rejects the positions afforded to working class people in neoliberalist discourse (Wilson, 2007). Neoliberalism is an ideology in which ‘human beings are made accountable for their predicaments or circumstances... as opposed to finding faults in larger structural and institutional forces like economic inequality’ (ibid, p. 97). These ascriptions of responsibility, taken together with the interactionally defensive positioning at level two, demonstrates how Rayner rejects neoliberally constructed perceptions of working class identity. Positioning theory thus presents the researcher with the opportunity to investigate how speakers orient to master discourses when and only

when they become relevant in a given scenario (Bamberg & Georgakopoulou, 2008), as opposed to a framework that might hastily assume them to be relevant at all times (such as CDA).

Further instances of Rayner orientating to master narratives are displayed in her descriptions of agency and emotional responses. In the Labovian Narrative 2, Rayner attests that, despite being on Income Support (a means-tested legacy benefit), ‘I wanted to go to work... I wanted to help... and I wanted to do the right thing’ (line 100). She describes other working class actors, both in the storyworld and storytelling world (people she grew up with and those on the breadline today) as motivated and possessing the desire to achieve. Rayner also mentions elsewhere in the interview, ‘I don’t want people to feel that pit in their stomach if they’re working’ (line 227-228), omitting unemployed working class members from these considerations in turn. Here, she constructs herself, and a particular subsection of working class people (those that are working, wanting to do the ‘right thing’, and those who are motivated – and only this subsection), as agentic. This orients to what Levitas (1998), Morris (1994) and Fairclough (2000) describe as the ‘division of respectable and abject within the working class’ (Skeggs, 2005, p. 972). That is, ‘abject’ working class individuals are branded ‘skivers’ (Valentine & Harris, 2014) and ‘lazy’ (Haylet, 2003) if they claim benefits, use food banks, or are unemployed, with ‘respectable’ working class members avoiding such labels by demonstrating a so-called desire to work and achieve. Through descriptions of certain working class characters in the storyworld as agentic and not others, Rayner is seen to orient to the master narrative that there is such a thing as a ‘good’ and ‘bad’ way to be working class, firmly positioning herself as the former. This could therefore be characterised as an acceptance of this abject/respectable division, as opposed to her previous rejection of the positions afforded to working class people by master narratives. As Saini (2022) notes, positioning theory is a particularly useful framework to apply to stories told by minorities, in that it offers up an opportunity to investigate how the individual navigates (accepts, rejects, subverts) existing dominant discourses.

Rayner frequently describes the emotions she and other working class individuals felt as a response to negative public sentiments around stigmatised activities such as having children at a young age. These emotions were also featured in the narratives told about financial insecurity (such as needing food banks and relying on benefits), and included shame, humiliation, and embarrassment. By assigning these emotions, Rayner orients to the master narrative of ‘moral disgust’ towards working class people (Skeggs, 2005, 2006; Tyler, 2008). As Skeggs (1997) highlights, this perception of working class individuals is so pervasive that many internalise this negativity, feeling emotions of shame in accordance with their perceived lack of ‘moral value’ (Skeggs, 2005, p. 48). Society treats working class white women in particular, especially those relying on the welfare state who have had children at a young age, as aimless, promiscuous, and uncouth (Tyler, 2008). Here, the distinction between the telling and the tale, in contrast to a sense of constancy as established prior, instead conveys a sense of change. Whilst Rayner internalised moral disgust in the storyworld, she rejects those feelings at the time of the interview and instead advocates speaking out about stigma, saying ‘a lot of people think... you don’t talk about those things cause you’re ashamed or you’re embarrassed by it whereas I think we should talk about it [more]’ (line 78), and ‘I want the young people of today (.) and the young (.) single mums like me (.) to know that they are absolutely worth it (.)’ (lines 188-191). Positioning theory has proven itself to be a sophisticated framework in conveying consistency and change over time, in turn underscoring the unstable and evolving nature of identity.

5 Conclusion

This research has demonstrated how narratives, both grand and small, function as rich data sites through which to investigate adaptable, contestable, and locally situated identities. Abstract qualities such as responsibility, expressed in real time through actions such as defending and justifying, have together demonstrated orientation to and rejection of overarching neoliberalist ideology, for example. Thus, as exemplified by the interplay at different levels, positioning theory is particularly apt at describing the relationship between micro and macro phenomena, exploring how master discourses are orientated to in local interaction and negotiated amongst speakers. This in turn strengthens the case for inductively/abductively grounded frameworks by challenging the need for wholly top-down or bottom-up starting points, the critiques of which are extensively documented (de Fina, 2008). This research has demonstrated how by placing characters in a story world, relaying those stories in context, and employing wider discursive information, a working class speaker can navigate their past, present and future in displaying a layered self.

Questions remain, however, regarding the distinction between the told (level one), and the telling (level two). A post-structuralist stance might postulate, for instance, that both are ‘contextually and reflexively dependent on one another’ (Watson, 2007, p. 384). Speakers may describe, place, and evaluate (position) characters in storyworlds differently, depending on the interlocutors present and the specificities of any given environment. Schofield’s insinuation that Rayner should apologise for her language and the inclusion of that narrative on a national stage could be interpreted as Schofield demonstrating a political commitment, in that some left leaning journalists may not have framed the situation in a negative way. Indeed, Bamberg (1997) describes how characters’ actions may be described differently depending on the desire of the speaker and the interlocutors to evaluate themselves with particular moral weight. Future research could therefore explore the tellings of the same story to different audiences in order to examine the effects of level one on level two, and vice versa. This in particular may be fruitfully applied to stories told by working class actors, given that some working class professionals like Rayner have claimed to have changed their behaviour and linguistic output when around individuals whose class is different to their own (Verdi & Ebsworth, 2009).

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7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix 1: Transcription Notations

Table 1: *Transcription Notations*

Symbol	Meaning
:::	Elongation of the sound prior
[]	Overlap in talk
=	Speech that directly follows prior speech without pause
(.)	A very short pause
(())	Descriptions of behaviour
<u>test</u>	Word underlined demonstrates emphasis
TEST	Upper case demonstrates volume
test	Bold indicates the presence of a narrative

7.2 Appendix 2: Transcript

Line no.	Sp.	Dialogue
1	H:	good afternoon joining us is one of the most powerful women in westminster
2		with a reputation for being fiery and outspoken
3	P:	but getting to her senior political position hasn't been easy not just because of
4		her gender but because (.) also of her working class background
5	H:	well (.) to tell us about life as deputy leader of the labour party we're joined
6		now by (.) Angela Rayner good [morning and]
7	A:	[good morning]
8	H:	welcome
9	A:	[thank you]
10	H:	[it's lovely to have] you here (.) um (.) it's funny because you see you (.) in
11		Westminster (.) doing your job pro- uh (.) carrying out your role (.) I didn't
12		actually know too much about your background until I read this and I'm not
13		sure I mean a lot of people will do but a lot of people won't (.) but it was that
14		background and your upbringing that really shaped you (.) who you are as you sit
15		here on the sofa today
16	A:	yeah (.) and it was crazy when I first went into parliament because (.) yaknow
17		the whole building is like goin' to hogwarts it's a bit (.) surreal you know (.) I
18		still
19		think that yaknow when I stand at the dispatch box and you think of the people
20		[that have stood there and been there]
20	H:	[who have been there before you]
21	A:	before me it's a bit like wow (.) I'm here and I'm doin' this (.) you know so it

- 22 does feel a bit surreal from (.) growing up on a council estate and (.) ya know
23 having my son at sixteen and (.) and basically you know um (.) being very poor
24 and (.) having very big challenges and then all of a sudden being in (.) **mixing**
25 **with people who went to private education who have got (.) loads of**
26 **wealth and (.) I remember having a joke once with one of the MPs talking**
27 **about the (.) issues on our estate because there was um (.) ca- um horses**
28 **churning up the grass on the estate and he went oh we have llamas on**
29 **our estate I'm like no I'm talking about the council**
30 **[estate and the horses that were just left]**
31 H: [((laughing)) oh my god]=
32 A: =in the wild so it was ya know those
33 moments where two worlds [collide]
34 P: [when] you left school at sixteen (.) um (.) you
35 were
36 told that you wouldn't amount to anything
37 A: yeah (.)
38 P: what was life like (.) for you then (.) la- and life at home=
39 A: =you see this is the thing cause (.) in parliament people do see me as quite
40 (.) brash and quite (.) confident but (.) part of the reason I'm like that is
41 because when I was sixteen and I was (.) I was pregnant (.) the shame and the
42 humiliation that people made me feel like (.) you know (.) institutions of
43 government (.) ya know doctors (.) police (.) they were there (.) above you (.) and
44 they were there to do things and you had to keep order they weren't (.) people
like you

- 45 H: yeah
- 46 A: so (.) I always felt know your place (.) so (.) I felt that humiliation and shame
- 47 then so now (.) I'm like (.) no I'm proud of who I am and I'm proud of the people
- 48 that I represent (.) and the people that I grew up with so (.) now I don't have any
- 49 (.) cares about speakin' (.) ma mind and bein 'cause everyone's got unique
- 50 talents it doesn't matter where they're from whether (.) they're from an affluent
- 51 background or not but (.) there's people from working class backgrounds that
- 52 are (.) from a very young age (.) taught to know your place [y'know]
- 53 H: [yes yeah]
- 54 A: and and I- I -learnt that and then I unlearned it (.) and realised that actually (.) its
- 55 important that people do speak out=
- 56 H: =a-and do you think that therefore actually (.) um um (.) within parliament there
- 57 needs to be a bit more broader representation of people from all sorts of
- 58 walks of life then because obviously clearly its so important
- 59 A: yeah and y'know (.) there's so many (.) colleagues from different parties that
- 60 have got working class backgrounds but it almost gets (.) taken out of them (.)
- 61 and its a frustration for me cause when I speak to them [an-
- 62 H: [who's] taking it out of
- 63 them?
- 64 A: The SYSTEM (.) they just they grow up thinking that in order to be somethin' (.)
- 65 ya have to:: speak a certain way (.) or ya have to hide that you didn't like I
- 66 talk about not having a formal academic education
- 67 P: ((murmuring))

- 68 A: and (.) then people say oh you're thick (.) i I'm I'm clearly not because i
69 wouldn't be in the job I'm doin now if I was stupid
- 70 H: yeah
- 71 A: **but I just learned in a different way and I had challenges in ma life when I**
72 **was early (.) erm in my I- when I was younger so I wasn't on education my**
73 **mum had bipolar and was very depressed so I was looking after ma mum**
74 **and things like that so education wasn't (.) drilled into me as important but**
75 **(.) that doesn't mean to say that I was (.) less intelligent** and I think (.) a lot of
76 people think that you have to speak a certain way (.) or you don't talk about
77 those things cause you're ashamed or you're embarrassed by it whereas I think
78 we should talk about it [more]
- 79 H: [I agree]
- 80 P: you spend some time uh- uh working as a carer
81 [working within the social services]
- 82 A: [I did yeah (.) I loved it] (.) yeah
- 83 P: so (.) when you have that sort of background (.) um (.) the background with your
84 mum (.) looking after her (.) the background of having um uh a child when you
85 were very young (.) um the background of of that (.) uh (.) growing up uh in in
86 sort of social area that you grew up in
- 87 A: mmm
- 88 P: um (.) when you get into westminster (.) do you look at it and think (1) you have
89 no clue what's going on in the outside world

90 A: yeah sometimes it's really frustrating because (.) **one of the biggest challenges**
 91 **that I found so when I had Ryan I ended up on income support and (.) I**
 92 **needed that support at the beginning now obviously I- I pay my taxes I'm a**
 93 **a ya know high income earner (.) and at that time I needed that little bit of**
 94 **help and I felt humiliated and ashamed to ask for help and people that use**
 95 **foodbanks now (.) it's that humiliation it's not a lifestyle choice but some**
 96 **people think (.) oh it's a lifestyle choice to do that you know you're**
 97 **responsible and (.) the the difficulties and the challenges I had (.) I just**
 98 **wanted to be a good mum**

99 H: mmm

100 A: **I wanted to go to work I wanted to help and I wanted to do the right thing**
 101 **but (.) the system at the time was a struggle for me (.) but I managed to you**
 102 **know get on and achieve and (.) and I think the misconception a lot of time is**
 103 **people think (.) oh well they're on benefits so they don't really want any- they**
 104 **don't aspire to anything in life and the challenges that (.) you know some of the**
 105 **people I grew up with ma friends (.) they've got like (.) children they're on the**
 106 **breadline they're struggling and and you know I've helped them out in the past if**
 107 **if you've got no money at the end of the month and then your fridge breaks**
 108 **down your fridge freezer (.) you can't get credit (.) to get a fridge freezer (.)**
 109 **it's impossible and you don't (.) have (.) a couple of hundred quid in the**
bank=

110

111 H: =no

112 A: to just go and buy one

113 P: yeah

114 A: **and that pit (.) in your stomach that (.) feelin of absolute dread (.) what am I**

115 **gonna do (.) the panic (.) and I think sometimes people in positions of (.)**

116 **influence like um (.) politicians they've never felt that**

117 H: [no no no]

118 A: **[they've never felt] that fear of not being able to [look after ya family]**

119 P: [and has this made you]

120 quite obviously you know you have uh you've got a lot to look back on you have

121 an immense amount of experiences it made you (1) angry i mean you are (.) you

122 are (.) uh- uh-outspoken (.) **I mean there are times when you (.) haven't held**

123 **back (.) I mean you uh (.) said in October 2020 you used the word scum (.)**

124 **in reference to the Tory MP Chris Clarkson in the midst of a commons**

125 **debate (.) late night event in September '21 at the Labour Party conference**

126 **you described the Conservative government as homophobic (.) racist (.)**

127 **misogynistic and vile (.) a bunch of scum (.) now they are big they're big**

128 **words (.)** uh Keir Starmer I think said they're not quite the words I wouldn't use=

128

129 A: =sure

130 P: have you (.) be-cuh is that because (.) you are angry and frustrated or is that just

131 the person that you are (.) speakin' your mind

132 A: no it's because I get really (.) frustrated and you know you do have to watch ya
 133 tone because obviously people have (.) have got abuse and I I don't condone
 134 abuse what I want (.) and what I aspire is that people get involved in politics
 135 because it matters (.) and the reason why I get so angry about that is (.) because
 136 (.) if you're in (.) Boris Johnson has said some pretty awful things (.) very very
 137 bad things that actually (.) even if you were in a a job workin' in a supermarket
 138 you'd have been sacked (.) for the things that he's said (.) so I think (.) why do
 139 you treat a supermarket worker to a standard that you say (.) if you said that
 140 comment (.) that you wouldn't be in the job (.) but the prime minister of the
 141 country has never apologised for those comments it's the HYPOCRISY of it (.)
 142 because they're posh and they've gone to a posh school (.) [they can say those
 143 things but]

144 P: [but you didn't
 145 apologise for saying] (.) uh homophobic (.) racist (.) misogynistic and vile

146 A: no I've I've I've asked (.) Boris Johnson to actually have a debate with me on this
 147 because I really want to say to him because (.) this is the problem that I have (.)
 148 if
 149 you if you put working class people (.) ordinary people doing their day to day job
 150 your lorry driver whatever (.) to a standard that says if you use language like (.)
 151 you know (.) um (.) the language that Boris Johnson used (.) which has been
 152 racist it has been homophobic it has been misogynistic (.) they wouldn't last five
 minutes in their job (.) yet you've got the prime minister (.) who thinks he doesn't

153 have to apologise for those comments and he can say it (.) so it's the hypocrisy
154 for me (.) I accept that some of the language was (.) y'know (.) it was it was not
155 the language that they would use (.) but for me it's the frustration of (.) you (.)
156 you treat people to a different standard (.) so if I walk into a room for example
157 'cause I- I've got a Manchester accent (.) I have to prove and because I'm a
158 woman (.) I have to prove why I've got the (.) skills to do my job (.) if (.) Boris
159 Johnson walks into a room because he's from Eton (.) private educated from a
160 certain class (.) and he's a man in a suit (.) he's automatically oh well he must
161 know what he's [talkin' about]

162 P: [well you walk] up to the dispatch box and you get that as a
163 woman at the dispatch box because (.) you will be (.) a- a- abused online (.) and
164 trolled online because of what you're wearing (.) [whereas that would never
165 happen to a guy]

166 A: [well it's funny because I keep
167 sayin' y'know (.)] I'm gonna turn up to PMQs one day I'm gonna ruffle ma hair
168 (.)
169 so it looks really scraggy like I've not got up and (.) done anything with it I'm
170 gonna wear a bland suit with a pair of (.) male shoes on and put (.) no makeup on
171 (.) and then when I get like the tsunami of abuse sayin' look at the state of her (.)
172 how can she turn up like that I'll say well I'm just (.) dressed (.) exactly the same
173 way as the person opposite me (.) because you do get (.) unfortunately=

173 H: =yeah

174 A: you do get ya know (.) a different standard and ya do get (.)uh criticised for

- traditional politicians are] (.) nervous of you (.) like do you that think you sort of
196 hold a mirror up to something that's quite (.) o-old fashioned in some ways
197 A: yeah some of them are (.) they don't quite know how to take me (.) they're a bit
198 like woah (.) and I think that's the other thing as well cause (.) Mancunians we're
a bit in ya face (.) ya know and and where i grew up it's like y'kno we are a
199 bit (.) boisterous and (.) loud and (.) and they they see it as woah you're a
200 bit full on and actually that's quite normal ya know in fact i'm quite tame
201 compared to [how I am when I'm with my mates in Manchester]
202
203 H: ((laughing))
204 P: [well you (.) you've said] you've said of (.) of Keir Starmer it's fair
to
205 say me and Keir are completely different in the way that we do things it's like
206 putting two dogs together in a room they'll fight for a bit then they'll find a way
(.)
207 and then they become best of mates we haven't quite got to be best of mates yet
208 (.) um (.) do you want to be leader
209 A: I want Keir to be Prime Minister so that I can rock it at the other side then I can
210 go in number 10 and he has all the responsibility of being Prime Minister and I
can (.) get all of the stuff that I think will help [working class people from my
211 background]
212
213 P: [so you don't (.) you don't (.)] you
214 have no ambitions of being Prime Minister
215 A: I want to get into number ten with Keir (.) I just want to get into government (.)
dya know what (.) seriously (.) seven years (.) nearly (.) i've been on frontline

- 216 politics(.) I've I've sacrificed (.) seein' ma kids as much as I'd want (.) I'm a
 217 grandmother now
 218
 219 H: mmm
 220 A: I haven't seen my grandkids as much as I'd like to (.) and (.) for me (.)
 221 opposition is not a place to be cause ya can't change people's lives
 222 H: mmm
 223 A: I want to be able to do all the things that I know will make the difference that
 224 helped me (.) when I was growin' up (.) and that's my number one target is to get
 225 into government (.) so that we can actually implement policies that will change
 226 people's lives so (.) y'know the cost of livin' now and (.) I talked about worryin'
 227 about if ya fridge freezer breaks (.) I don't want people to feel that pit in their
 228 stomach (.) if they're workin' I want them to feel (.) [confident that they can live
 229 their lives]
 230 P: [where would you] where
 231 would you find uh w- the money (.) the UK prices rose by six point two percent
 232 in
 233 the twelve months to february (.) fastest rate for thirty years (.) [fuel]
 234 A: [yep]
 235 P: energy (.) food costs (.) absolutely soaring you've got Rishi Sunak today
 236 delivering his mini budget (.) um (.) there is only like any household in any
 237 country there is only a limited pot (.) of money that you can (.) you can dish out
 (.)

238 where would you guys find the money (.) to pay for what you're asking
239 A: and and ya know the most important thing about what ya sayin as well is those
240 costs (.) those day to day costs people who are on low incomes and ordinary
241 people workin' families (.) they spend majority of their wages on those costs its
242 a
243 bigger pot of what they spend on (.) and we've said that the -the oil and energy
244 companies have made massive profits over 40 billion (.) they've made (.) they
245 didn't expect to make that level of profit (.) we said the government should do a
246 windfall tax (.) we've done it before (.) and they should help with the households
247 bills now because people cannot find that money (.) it's not just a case of oh well
248 it's just gonna tighten your belt (.) people cannot find that money (.) it is (.)
249 yaknow energy bills are going up fifty-fifty six PERCENT (.) how can people
250 find
251 that MONEY(.) its- its people are literally petrified about it so (.) we have to do
252 something (.) the energy companies made huge money(.) that they didn't expect
253 to make (.) so now times are difficult (.) put that money back into helping those
254 families cause they really desperately need it (.) it's not just a case of politics here
255 (.) this about people feelin' like they can live and they can look after their kids (.)
256 and many older people as well (.) **I was a home help (.) I saw people in big**
257 **huge houses (.) who'd live in the kitchen (.) with a little stove on for an hour**
258 **(.) in the cold (.) I don't want any older person in our country thinkin' they**
259 **have to do that** and they will do that

- 258 H: yeah
- 259 A: And they will do that (.) even if they've got big huge houses you'll see them in
 260 the
 kitchen with a little stove on (.) for an hour (.) because they'll be worried about
 261 spending so much money energy o-o-on their energy bills (.) we've got to do
 262 somethin' to help
- 263 H: [thank you thank you] thank you
- 264 P: [we have to leave it there] (.) uh but thank you (.) very much
- 265 H: yeah (.) it's great to talk to you (.) [thank you thank you]
- 266 A: [thank you thank you]

About the author

Georgia Jukes graduated from the University of Birmingham in July 2022 with a first-class degree in English Language and Linguistics. With a particular interest in the relationship between language and society, she conducted a corpus assisted critical discourse analysis of the representations of Ghislaine Maxwell in the British Press for her undergraduate dissertation. This research suggested that Maxwell was treated preferentially on account of her class and race.

Through her role as a researcher with Journey to Justice, a charity aiming to shed light on injustice and barriers to education in the UK, Georgia continues to contribute to literature on class, gender, and race inequalities. Georgia is particularly committed to feminism and advancing gender equality through her role as Outreach Officer for the Young Fabian Women's Network, where she helps to create spaces for young women to engage in politics and policy.

Having just started her career in policy, Georgia works as an adviser for Citizens Advice Bureau, assisting the public with topics ranging from welfare to immigration. This position equips her with coalface insights which will guide her Master's degree in Social Policy, which she intends to undertake in 2024.

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Influence of Different Walking Speeds on Speech

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Abstract. The objective of this paper is to examine the effect of different walking speeds on concurrent speech tasks. Entrainment of talking to walking would support a model in which speech production planning is governed by coupled oscillators as proposed by Articulatory Phonology and Task Dynamics. The experimental design involved a walking-while-talking paradigm with three different gait velocities (normal, fast, slow) and two different speech tasks – reading aloud and repeated syllable production. Participants were 32 adults between 18 and 32 (mean age 22.5 ± 2.9 years) with no neurological, physiological, or psychological conditions impacting speech and/or gait. Results indicated that walking speed significantly affected speech measures in both tasks, but the effect size was considerably smaller for talking than gait. The effect of gait velocity was numerically much greater in the Syllable condition than in the Prose condition. This may show entrainment of talking to walking, supporting an oscillatory model of speech production. But the model would need to explain why speech did not change to the same extent as gait. Conversely, non-oscillatory models need to account for the fact that walking speed influenced speech in the first place.

Plain English Abstract. Does our brain have a “metronome” for speech? According to the Articulatory Phonology and Task Dynamics model, the timing with which we produce speech sounds is governed by coupled oscillators (the “metronome”), making speech a periodic (rhythmic) action. We know that walking is periodic. If speech were too, the two actions should entrain (converge to the same frequency) when carried out simultaneously, like two metronomes that eventually beat the same rhythm. 32 participants between 18 and 32 years with no conditions that impacted their speech or gait were asked to walk and talk simultaneously at three different speeds (normal, fast, slow). One group was reading a text, the other repeated the syllable ‘ba’. The speed of participants’ speech was affected by their walking speed, but speech slowed down and sped up to a lesser extent than gait. Walking speed had a much greater effect on speech for the participants repeating ‘ba’ than the ones reading the text. This might show entrainment between speech and gait, supporting an oscillatory (“metronomic”) model of speech production. But the model would need to explain why speech did not change to the same extent as gait. Conversely, non-oscillatory models need to account for the fact that walking speed influenced speech in the first place.

Keywords: entrainment; periodicity; coupled oscillators; walking-while-talking; Articulatory Phonology; Task Dynamics

1 Introduction

This paper aims to investigate the possibility of periodic, oscillatory mechanisms behind speech production through a walking-while-talking paradigm (see 2.3). In a walking-while-talking paradigm where participants are asked to produce speech while manipulating their walking speed, one would expect their speech rate to change in line with their walking speed according to the Articulatory Phonology/ Task Dynamics (AP/TD) framework. I.e., we would expect speakers to talk faster when walking faster and talk more slowly when walking more slowly. One might expect entrainment, if present, to be more pronounced during continuous syllable repetition than natural speech, since the former constitutes a more periodic and rhythmic motor task than the latter. Should significant differences in participants’ speech be found between the different walking-and-talking conditions, they would likely reflect entrainment of speech production to the walking speed and thus support the idea that speech production planning is governed by coupled oscillators as proposed by AP/TD.

1.1 The Articulatory Phonology/ Task Dynamics Framework

Researchers have proposed neural oscillators as control structures underlying different aspects of speech production planning, including syllable structure and rhythm production (Barbosa, 2002; Goldstein, 2008; Goldstein et al., 2009; Kröger et al., 2016). The AP/TD framework is one such oscillatory model (for an in-depth explanation, see Krivokapić, 2020). In AP/TD, the basic speech unit is the gesture, defined as ‘a linguistically relevant constriction of the vocal tract’ (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 1). Each of the gestures forming an utterance is associated with a planning oscillator; for example, the word “mad” consists of four gestures: lip closure and velum opening at onset /m/, wide pharyngeal constriction of the tongue body at vowel /a/, and tongue tip closure at the coda /d/ (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2). At the start of utterance planning, the oscillators ‘move’ in a random relationship to each other, but through changes of individual oscillators’ phases, they eventually reach a stable phase pattern (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241). In this stable system, gestures are activated at phase 0 of their oscillators, whose relative coupling controls the temporal coordination of the gestures in the utterance (Goldstein et al., 2009, p. 241; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2).

Syllable structure results from the timing of gestures involved in the syllable, and prosodic structure emerges from the coordination of prosodic gestures (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 3f.). Krivokapić (2020, p. 4) defines two types of gestures: π - and μ -gestures, both of which slow concurrently active gestures, causing a later start, longer durations, and less overlap in gestures which are active at the same time. π -gestures represent prosodic boundaries while μ -gestures control lexical stress (Krivokapić, 2020, pp. 4-8).

The AP/TD approach to speech production has several theoretical advantages. For example, no mediation between phonology and phonetics is necessary, since gesture specifications combine both phonological and phonetic information (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 2). AP/TD also places relatively little cognitive processing load on the speaker, since the movement trajectories of utterances are specified by the task dynamical system once the word sequence, prosodic structure, and rate of speech of a given utterance are planned, so movement trajectories need not be computed (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 46f.). Further, speakers are not required to plan surface speech timing since it emerges from AP/TD’s coupled oscillator model (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 47). This phonology-intrinsic timing mechanism allows AP/TD to avoid the use of a phonetic planning component and phonology-extrinsic (general-purpose) timer (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 47).

1.2 Speech Rate Entrainment

The role of coupled oscillators in speech production may lie in controlling speech rate. Evidence for this comes from studies showing entrainment of speech rate to concurrent tasks such as walking. Walking has been defined as an oscillatory, rhythmical motor behaviour emerging from cyclical neuronal activity in central pattern generators – neural structures in the spinal cord (MacKay-Lyons, 2002, p. 69; Samulski et al., 2019, p. 90). If speech gestures were governed by periodic oscillations as AP/TD proposes, we would expect these to entrain with other oscillators. During entrainment, two oscillators with different frequencies converge to a common period, whereby the weaker oscillator locks into the frequency of the stronger, or, if both are equally strong, they settle on a middle frequency (Pantaleone, 2002; Thaut, 2013, p. 31ff.).

Studies show that entrainment of concurrent motor tasks to walking is possible. For example, Hill et al. (1988, p. 570ff.) tested for entrainment of breathing to walking in 38 participants (18 male, 20

female, mean age 29). Subjects were asked to walk on a level treadmill at 2.5-3.0mph while breathing through a pneumotachograph. The time intervals between heel strikes of the right foot and onset of in- or expiration were analysed, and the researchers found evidence of entrainment between steps and breaths in most subjects. Only eight participants exhibited little to no entrainment, while the remaining thirty showed entrainment to walking rhythm in at least 25% of breaths. Similar results were found by Armstrong et al. (1997, p. 288), who investigated the effect of upper limb movements on entrainment of breathing frequency to walking rhythm. The researchers collected data from eight women (mean age 22), who were asked to walk on a treadmill at 3.0mph in three different conditions: normal gait and two different arm swing conditions in which two contrasting arm movements were performed with 1lb and 3lb hand-held weights while walking. Weight and arm swing pattern did not significantly affect the rhythmic entrainment between breathing pattern and heel strikes. All participants except one displayed entrainment of breathing and walking, with one subject showing entrainment of up to 48% of breaths.

Entrainment with walking has also been found for chewing. Samulski et al. (2019, pp. 91-95) studied the influence of different chewing frequencies on gait in 15 younger (mean age 23.2) and 15 older adults (mean age 66.5). Four gait tasks were performed: walking at a preferred speed without chewing, walking while chewing at a preferred rate, walking while chewing at a slow rate (1Hz), and walking while chewing at a fast rate (2Hz). In both age groups, walking speed was significantly influenced by chewing rate, with lower chewing rates causing slower walking speeds and higher chewing rates causing participants to walk faster. The researchers interpreted this as neural entrainment between the two motor behaviours. However, in the slow and fast chewing conditions, participants attained the desired chewing rate by deliberately entraining to a metronome at the start of each trial. This may have indirectly influenced the subjects' gait timing, so that changes in walking speed may have been due to entrainment to the metronome rhythm rather than chewing rate. Control conditions in which participants are asked to listen to the metronome at different rates and then walk without chewing would have been helpful in determining whether the metronome frequency influenced gait performance. Prebor et al. (2021, pp. 365) used the same walking-while-chewing paradigm in a study with 16 typically developing children (mean age 13.1), with the only difference that fast chewing was performed at 2.2Hz rather than 2Hz as in Samulski et al. (2019). The results confirmed Samulski et al.'s (2019) findings that chewing rate had a significant effect on walking and additionally showed that this effect was stronger in the fast-chewing condition (Prebor et al., 2021, p. 369). The average chewing and walking rates showed a tendency for convergence, suggesting bi-directional coupling between the neural oscillators associated with both actions (Prebor et al., 2021, p. 369f.).

Both Samulski et al. (2019, p. 91) and Prebor et al. (2021, p. 366) asked participants to walk at a preferred speed throughout trials while only chewing rate was consciously manipulated. While their studies show entrainment of walking speed to chewing rates, Maezawa et al. (2020) found that entrainment also happens the other way around, i.e., when participants chew at their preferred rate and walking speed is manipulated. In this experiment, the chewing rates of 12 participants (8 male, 4 female, mean age 24.4) were measured during different gait tasks on a linear treadmill (Maezawa et al., 2020, pp. 88-91). Subjects were asked to chew a piece of paraffin gum at their preferred rhythm while walking at a self-selected speed, a high speed (1.3x self-selected speed), and a low speed (1.3x slower than self-selected speed). Additionally, a baseline for chewing rate was measured in a chewing-only condition. Chewing rhythm in the chewing-only condition was not significantly different from the slow-walking condition but differed significantly from both the preferred-speed and fast-walking conditions. There were further significant differences in chewing rate between all three walking conditions. Maezawa et al. (2020, p. 93) concluded that 'entrainment of habitual chewing rhythm to gait speed occurs in humans'.

If walking entrains with rhythmic, periodic motor behaviours such as breathing and chewing, it is plausible to assume that if speaking is inherently periodic, it too should entrain with walking. Jablecki (2013, pp. 21; 86-91) compared 40 participants' (20 male, 20 female, mean age 23.9) production of real-words and non-words during standing versus walking. They found that articulation rate did not significantly differ between the walking and standing conditions, but that pause durations were significantly longer while standing. Due to the longer pause durations, total rate of speech was significantly slower while standing versus walking for both real- and non-words. Jablecki (2013) interpreted these results as indicative of motor entrainment between speech rate and gait. However, in a model where speech production is governed by coupled oscillators, one would expect all aspects of speech to be influenced by entrainment. If only pauses were to entrain to walking, would this indicate that only speech pauses are governed by coupled oscillators while articulation is not? If so, why should an oscillator mechanism apply to some aspects of speech production and not others?

1.3 Polysyllabic Shortening

Further evidence for AP/TD's coupled oscillator approach to speech production comes from polysyllabic shortening (Turk, 2020, p. 2). Here, an increased number of syllables in a foot (the interval between two stressed syllables) leads to a shorter duration of these sub-constituents (Turk 2020, p. 2; Krivokapić, 2020, p. 13f.). In other words, the syllables in the foot are shorter than they would be in isolated production, so that 'the larger constituent is shorter than expected based on the number of its sub-constituent[s]' (Turk, 2020, p. 2). The foot's duration shows a linear increase with higher numbers of syllables, indicating a tendency towards isochrony potentially due to periodic control through coupled oscillators (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14; Turk, 2020, p. 2). In AP/TD, polysyllabic shortening is explained as follows: stressed syllables are longer than unstressed ones because the μ -gesture slows the activation of co-active gestures (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). Depending on whether the foot or syllable oscillator is stronger, either the duration of the foot or syllable is kept constant, leading to either foot or syllable isochrony, respectively (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14; Saltzman et al., 2008, p. 180). In the case of foot isochrony, an increased number of syllables in the foot at constant foot duration results in polysyllabic shortening (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). According to Kim & Cole (2005), only stressed syllables shorten, but not unstressed ones. This can be accounted for in AP/TD by modelling the foot oscillator as dominant during stressed syllables and the syllable oscillator as dominant during unstressed syllables (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14). It is important to note that this model predicts a tendency towards, rather than strict isochrony (Krivokapić, 2020, p. 14).

AP/TD's account of polysyllabic shortening is challenged by Turk (2020, p. 2) who does not consider the phenomenon reliable evidence for syllable and foot oscillators since in many experiments, the location of word- or phrase boundaries is not controlled for, making it difficult to unambiguously attribute the observed effects to polysyllabic shortening over word- or phrase-final lengthening. Final lengthening may suffice to explain the durational difference between mono- and polysyllabic cross-word feet, making an oscillator-based mechanism obsolete (Turk, 2020, p. 2; Windmann et al., 2015).

Windmann et al. (2015, p. 36ff.) investigated a corpus of English broadcast speech for polysyllabic shortening effects on vowel duration in words, inter-stress intervals, and narrow rhythm units, the latter being defined as 'the interval between the onset of a stressed syllable and the following word boundary'. Observed polysyllabic shortening effects disappeared at all three constituent levels once within-word position (word-final vs. non-final) was accounted for, supporting the notion that such observations may result from a lack of control of constituent- final syllables in the data. In contrast

to this, prominence and constituent-final position were found to have large and reliable lengthening effects on syllables, which Windmann et al. (2015, p. 39) interpreted as the root of prosodic timing in English, as opposed to underlying oscillator-based periodicity.

Turk (2020, p. 142f.) claims that words without phrasal stress may remain unaffected by polysyllabic shortening or be affected to a smaller extent. According to Turk (2020, p. 4), polysyllabic shortening is strongest in phrasally-stressed words, which are preferentially targeted by the phenomenon. This challenges AP/TD's oscillator-based approach, since if such a periodic control mechanism were in place, compression should apply equally to every constituent of an utterance (Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel, 2020, p. 143). Turk and Shattuck-Hufnagel (2020, p. 143) propose that rather than reflecting underlying periodicity, speakers may use a set of mechanisms to signal the locations of word-based prosodic constituent boundaries in utterances, one of these mechanisms being polysyllabic shortening.

The evidence presented in this paragraph suggests that polysyllabic shortening effects may be spurious and apply preferentially to phrasally-stressed constituents of utterances, contradictory to the predictions of AP/TD's model of oscillatory, periodic control of speech timing. This calls into question the need for a suprasegmental oscillator model to explain these effects.

2 Method

2.1 Participants

32 participants (10 male, 20 female, 2 other) between 18 and 32 years (mean age 22.5 ± 2.9 years) took part in the experiment. Participants confirmed they had no neurological, physiological, or psychological conditions impacting their speech and/or gait. To avoid selection bias, participants were allocated to two groups, Prose and Syllable group, by sign-up order. Group allocation was subsequently altered as minimally as possible to ensure equal numbers of native and non-native speakers of British English in the Prose group. The native languages of non-native speakers of English were not recorded as native language influence on experiment outcomes was only of concern in the Prose group, where the small number of non-native English speaking participants was so small (8) that a differentiated analysis of native language influence on experiment outcomes did not seem statistically viable. The Prose group had 16 participants (6 male, 10 female), half of which were native speakers of English. All non-native speakers rated their English proficiency at C1 or C2 level according to the CERF framework¹³. The Syllable group had 16 participants (4 male, 10 female, 2 other). English-language proficiency was not assessed in this group since there was no reason to expect an influence of language proficiency on task performance.

2.2 Materials

The experiment was conducted in a public square, relatively wind-shielded by surrounding buildings. For each trial, participants walked a straight stretch of 23.75m, turned around, and walked back to the starting point without pausing, so that they walked 47.5m in total. The start and end of the 23.75m were demarcated using brightly coloured tape on the floor. A mobile phone stopwatch was used to record the time participants needed to walk the 47.5m.

¹³ Please find information on the CERF descriptors here: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages/cefr-descriptors>

Participants’ speech was recorded using a lavalier microphone (audio-technica® ATR3350) attached to their clothing near the face and directed towards their mouth, which was connected to a recorder (H2n Handy Recorder 200M, 44.1kHz, 16 bits) that participants held in their hands while walking. The gain on the recorder was adjusted to each participant’s speech volume before the trials. Participants in the Prose condition were then given a laminated sheet with the experiment text. Head position was not specified for participants, but observably all Syllable participants held their heads upright while most Prose participants were looking down at the text while walking, bringing their mouths closer to the microphone and influencing vocal tract shape; although this was not considered a concern since these circumstances applied universally across all participants and experiment conditions in the Prose group and should therefore not influence entrainment observations.

2.3 Trials

Prose participants were given a text to read aloud (Appendix One) during the talking trials, as well as time to familiarise themselves with the text before the experiment, while Syllable participants were asked to continually repeat the syllable ‘ba’. The experiment consisted of six conditions:

Table 1: *Gait and speech tasks in the different conditions for Prose and Syllable participants.*

Condition	Prose Group	Syllable Group
1	standing while reading the text aloud once	standing while repeating ‘ba’ for 30s
2	walking at normal speed	
3	walking at normal speed while reading aloud	walking at normal speed while repeating ‘ba’
4	walking at slow speed while reading aloud	walking at slow speed while repeating ‘ba’
5	walking at fast speed while reading aloud	walking at fast speed while repeating ‘ba’
6	repetition of condition 1	

During the walking-and-talking conditions, Prose participants repeated the text until they had finished the walking stretch. The normal, fast, and slow speeds were self-selected by each participant. For condition 4, participants were asked to imagine themselves on an evening walk, enjoying themselves and hence walking slower than usual. For condition 5, they were instructed not to run or walk so fast as to get out of breath, but to imagine themselves talking to a friend while on the way to an important appointment. The order in which participants fulfilled conditions 4 and 5 was counterbalanced in each group to account for carry-over effects. To mitigate learning effects, participants completed three trials each for conditions 1 and 6, and five trials each for conditions 2, 3, 4, and 5, so that the experiment consisted of 26 trials in total. Whenever a trial was interrupted due to loud noise or obstructions of the walking stretch by passers-by, it was deleted and repeated as soon as the interruption/obstruction had passed. Throughout trials, the experimenter was explicit about manipulating walking speed with no mention of manipulating speech rate. One session took around 45 minutes to complete. As compensation, participants could enter a prize draw for a £50 restaurant voucher.

2.4 Annotation

The annotation purpose was to separate speech from pause intervals to obtain measures for pure utterance and pause time for each recording, as well as the full speech duration in the Prose group and the number of syllables uttered in the Syllable group. For tangibility of the data and ease of analysis, I annotated only one full repetition of the text in the Prose recordings and focussed on a 20s-interval in the Syllable recordings.

Recordings were annotated using the Praat software package (Version 6.1.12). A script based on Lennes (2011) was used to automatically annotate the sound files to text grids with an interval tier named ‘pauses’ and segment pauses from speech intervals (Appendix Two), as seen in Figure 1. A pause was defined as having a maximum intensity of 50dB and minimum duration of 0.2s. The intensity threshold was determined through previous trial runs to strike a balance between pauses not being detected due to background noise, and low-intensity speech sounds being classed as pauses. The duration threshold was based on Zellner (1994:44), according to whom a duration of 200-250ms is the auditory threshold for perception of a pause. Both breathing and silent pauses were included in the analysis while filled pauses (coughing, laughing, sneezing etc.) were excluded, meaning they were neither counted towards pause time nor overall duration. Vocal hesitations such as ‘uh’ or ‘um’ did not occur in the data. Pauses were checked visually in the spectrogram and waveform, and boundaries adjusted manually where necessary. Common causes for pause detection errors were pauses not being detected due to loud breathing or background noise from wind or passers-by, as well as unvoiced fricatives being included in pause intervals as in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Automatically annotated sound file of a Prose participant, using a script based on Lennes (2011) (Appendix Two).

Figure 2: Segmentation error – The [s] in ‘house’ was segmented as part of the pause by the algorithm. NB: The transcription in the bottom tier is provided for explanatory purposes and was not part of the annotation process.

To set boundaries between utterance and pause intervals, segmentation followed the strategy outlined in Turk et al. (2006:6) of using changes in the spectrogram to define the general regions of a boundary and consulting the waveform for more precise decisions. Vowels were segmented at the start/end of distinct vertical striations in the spectrogram, or, failing this, at the shading onset/offset in the first and second formants. Voiceless fricatives were segmented using the shading onset/offset in the spectrogram or changes in the waveform. The end of nasals was demarcated at the last vertical striation in the spectrogram or at the end of formant structures. The start of liquids was segmented at the onset of formant structures in the spectrogram while using changes in the waveform for precision. No other segmentation decisions had to be made for the data. In some instances where background noise, especially wind, made visual segmentation difficult, sounds were segmented acoustically.

Pause intervals were labelled ‘p’ and utterance intervals ‘u’. A second interval tier was added to each text grid, called ‘duration’ for the Prose and ‘syllables’ for the Syllable group, see Figures 3 and 4. Most Prose recordings contained only one complete repetition of the text, which was segmented at the start and end in the ‘duration’ tier and labelled ‘dur’. Only pause and utterance intervals falling within this time frame were segmented and used for analysis. In the Syllable recordings, the ‘syllables’ tier contained one interval starting at the beginning of the first uttered syllable and spanning 20s. Only pause and utterance intervals falling within this time frame were segmented and used for analysis. The number of syllables uttered within these 20s were counted both visually from the spectrogram and acoustically. The ‘syllables’ tier interval was then labelled with the number of counted syllables.

Figure 3: Finished annotation of a Prose recording.

Figure 4: Finished annotation of a Syllable recording (CONT group).

Interruptions (e.g., coughs, sneezes, laughs, self-corrections, repetitions) were manually segmented in both tiers and given no interval label to exclude them from subsequent measurements as in Figure 5. For Syllable recordings, the time spent on such interruptions was measured and added to the end of the original 20s interval to maintain 20s of uninterrupted recording material for the analysis.

Figure 5: The participant mispronounced the word ‘nearby’ and corrected themselves. This interruption was segmented out and not counted towards utterance time or overall duration. NB: The transcription in the bottom tier is provided for explanatory purposes and was not part of the annotation process.

2.5 Exclusions

During annotation, two subgroups of the Syllable group were determined: eight participants produced syllables continuously while only pausing occasionally (CONT group) as can be seen in Figure 4, four participants paused after each syllable (PAU group) as in Figure 6.

Figure 6: *Pause pattern of a participant in the PAU group. For a CONT example, see Figure 4.*

Two participants varied their pause pattern throughout recordings and were thus excluded from the analysis. A further two were excluded for producing syllables in a simulated conversational rhythm, since their speech did not represent a cyclical action as was the objective of the Syllable task. This left 12 Syllable participants for analysis (3 male, 7 female, 2 other), eight of which belonged to the CONT group, four to the PAU group.

2.6 Measurements

For the Prose group, the following measurements were extracted from the text grids: duration, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time. Measurements were collected as absolute values and individual variation was accounted for in the statistical analysis. Duration represents the time participants needed to read the text once in seconds, number of pauses refers to the pauses made during this reading, utterance time is the time spent speaking during the duration interval in seconds, pause time is the time spent pausing within the duration interval in seconds. Participants' walking time was also recorded, i.e., the time needed to walk the 47.5m in seconds, as well as their proficiency level of English (native/non-native), age, and gender (male/female/other/prefer not to say).

For the Syllable group, the following measurements were extracted from the text grids: syllable count, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time. Syllable count refers to the number of syllables uttered within the segmented 20s-interval. A syllable was counted if the vowel started before the end of the 20s-interval. Number of pauses refers to the pauses made during the 20s-interval. All pauses with a minimum duration of 0.2s starting within the 20s-interval were counted, even if the portion of the pause that fell within the 20s-interval was shorter than 0.2s. Utterance time is the total time spent speaking during the 20s-interval in seconds, and pause time is the total time spent pausing during the

20s-interval in seconds. Additionally, participants' articulation rate was calculated, i.e., syllable count divided by utterance time. Participants' walking time was also recorded as well as their age and gender (male/female/other/prefer not to say). English proficiency was not recorded in the Syllable group since it was not expected to influence syllable production. However, participants' Group was recorded after annotation, i.e., whether participants belonged to CONT or PAU.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted in R, separately for the Prose and Syllable group. Models were fitted using the 'lme4' package (version 1.1-25). The 'emmeans' package (version 1.7.2) was used to compute estimated marginal means. For the script used to produce the figures and fit the statistical models, see Appendix Three.

For the Prose group, I obtained the means and standard deviations for all variables (walking time, duration, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time) with all participants pooled together, native speakers only, and non-native speakers only. I investigated the effects on walking time using a linear mixed effects model with walking time as dependent variable, age, gender, and condition as independent variables, and random intercepts were fitted for participants. This analysis was conducted for all Prose participants pooled together, native speakers only, and non-native speakers only. The `emmeans()` function was used on the model which included walking time values for all Prose participants, computing the estimated marginal means for all combinations of walking conditions to investigate whether the difference between any two conditions was statistically significant. Further linear mixed effects models were used to investigate the effect of level of English on the walking and speech measures. In these models, the independent variables were level of English and random by-participant effects, the dependent variables walking time, duration, number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time, respectively. The effects of different factors on each speech measure were analysed with linear mixed effects models. In each model, the dependent variable was the relevant speech measure, the independent variables walking time, age, gender, the interaction between walking time and level of English, and random by-participant effects.

For the Syllable group, I obtained the means and standard deviations for all variables (walking time, syllable count, articulation rate, number of pauses, utterance time, pause time) with all participants pooled together, CONT only, and PAU only. I investigated the effects on walking time using a linear mixed effects model with walking time as dependent variable, age, gender, and condition as independent variables, and random intercepts were fitted for participants. This analysis was conducted for all Syllable participants pooled together, CONT only, and PAU only. The `emmeans()` function was used on the model which included walking time values for all Syllable participants, computing the estimated marginal means for all combinations of walking conditions to investigate whether the difference between any two conditions was statistically significant. Further linear mixed effects models were used to investigate the effect of Group on the walking and speech measures. In each model, the independent variables were Group and random by-participant effects, the dependent variables walking time, syllable count, articulation rate, number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time, respectively. The effects of different factors on each speech measure were analysed with linear mixed effects models. In each model, the dependent variable was the relevant speech measure, and the independent variables were walking time, age, gender, the interaction between walking time and Group, and random by-participant effects.

3 Expectations

I do not expect age or gender to affect participants' gait or speech in this study, but they are nonetheless included in the analyses for completeness. In the subset of participants whose speech task was to read a text (Prose group), English proficiency may play a role since non-native speakers may struggle to read the text. However, this effect may level out due to each experimental condition being repeated multiple times and participants becoming more practiced in reading the text. Since all non-native English speakers evaluated their language skills at C1 or C2 level, it is also possible that there is no significant difference between native and non-native speakers in this group.

If talking entrains to walking, I would expect the following outcomes for Prose participants: duration of reading the text once might increase and decrease in line with walking time since participants would talk more slowly when walking more slowly and talk faster when walking faster and therefore need more or less time, respectively, to read the text. I would expect entrainment to apply to both pause and utterance intervals, meaning pause time and utterance time would both increase and decrease in line with walking time. I have no specific expectation for the number of pauses made.

In the Syllable group, I would expect the following results if talking entrains to walking: syllable count might be negatively correlated to walking time since participants would talk more slowly when walking more slowly and talk faster when walking faster, therefore producing less or more syllables, respectively, within a 20s-interval. Since the duration of the interval is fixed, I would expect pause time and utterance time to stay roughly constant at different walking speeds. I expect articulation rate to be negatively correlated to walking time, i.e., increase at faster walking speeds and decrease at slower speeds. I have no specific expectation for number of pauses made.

4 Results

4.1 Prose: Did Speech Entrain to Gait when Reading Aloud?

4.1.1 *Did Walking Speed change between Conditions?*

In the Prose group, walking time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.96$), but it was by gender ($p = 0.003$). According to the model, men needed on average 6.73s less than women to walk the stretch ($se = 1.95s$). The linear mixed effects models for both native and non-native speakers returned significant p -values for at least one comparison between two walking conditions, indicating that condition significantly affected how fast participants walked. On average, non-native speakers had a longer walking time than native speakers by 3.16s ($se = 2.34s$), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.196$), which justifies grouping native and non-native speakers' walking time values together in subsequent analyses.

The average walking time was 32.05s in condition 2 ($sd = 3.85s$), 35.65s in condition 3 ($sd = 4.84s$), 44.71s in condition 4 ($sd = 9.30s$), and 29.89s in condition 5 ($sd = 4.16s$). Medians and distribution of walking time by condition are displayed in Figure 7. The differences in walking time were significant between any two of the walking conditions ($p = 0.0003$ between conditions 2 and 5, $p < 0.001$ for all other comparisons). This shows that participants significantly altered their walking speed in each condition.

Figure 7: Median and distribution of walking time in each walking condition for native and non-native speakers.

4.1.2 Did Duration Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with duration as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 6.55e^{-13}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants needed 0.08s longer to read the text ($se = 0.01s$). Duration was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.28$) or gender ($p = 0.38$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was not significant ($p = 0.595$), meaning that the effect of walking time on duration was not significantly different for native vs. non-native speakers. Non-native speakers took on average 1.82s longer than native speakers to read the text ($se = 0.85s$). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.048$). Figure 8 illustrates that non-native speakers had longer duration than native speakers across conditions, but that duration followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 8: *Median and distribution of duration in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.*

To read the text, native speakers needed on average 18.57s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.72s$), 19.15s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.76s$), and 17.80s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.60s$). Non-native speakers needed on average 20.86s in condition 3 ($sd = 2.31s$), 21.34s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.97s$), and 19.39s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.65s$).

Since the interaction between walking time and level of English was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on duration for native and non-native speakers together: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, but their duration increased by only 2.69%. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their duration decreased by 5.67%.

Figure 9: Values for duration in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 9 shows a slight tendency for duration to increase with increasing walking time, but there is no obvious linear relationship. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as native and non-native speakers display a similar relationship between walking time and duration. These results suggest that walking time affected duration in that when walking faster, participants read the text faster and when walking more slowly, participants took longer reading the text. However, participants' speech did not speed up or slow down to the same extent as their gait.

4.1.3 Did the Number of Pauses change depending on Walking Speed?

A linear mixed effects model with number of pauses as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned no significant results.

4.1.4 Did Utterance Time Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with utterance time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 1.45e^{-07}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants had a 0.05s longer utterance time ($se=0.008894s$). Utterance time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.69$) or gender ($p = 0.22$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was not significant ($p = 0.0503$), meaning that the effect of walking time on utterance time was not significantly different for native vs. non-native speakers. Non-native speakers had on average a longer utterance time by 2.21s than native speakers ($se = 0.78s$) and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.01$). Figure 10 illustrates that non-native speakers had longer

utterance time than native speakers across conditions, but that utterance time followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 10: Median and distribution of utterance time in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.

During one repetition of the text, native speakers had an average utterance time of 16.27s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.31s$), 16.43s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.25s$), and 15.63s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.18s$). Non-native speakers had an average utterance time of 18.79s in condition 3 ($sd = 2.25s$), 18.94s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.04s$), and 17.42s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.83s$).

Since the interaction between walking time and level of English was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on utterance time for native and non-native speakers together: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, but their utterance time increased by only 0.88%. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their utterance time decreased by 5.70%.

Figure 11: Values for utterance time in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 11 shows a slight tendency for utterance time to increase with increasing walking time, but there is no obvious linear relationship. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as native and non-native speakers display a similar relationship between walking time and utterance time. These results suggest that walking speed affected utterance time in that when walking faster, participants articulated faster and when walking more slowly, participants took longer to produce the utterances. However, the difference in walking speed is much greater than the difference in utterance time across conditions.

4.1.5 Did Pause Time Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with pause time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and level of English as independent variables returned a significant effect of age ($p = 0.0056$): participants paused 0.19s less per added year in age ($se = 0.06s$). Gender did not significantly influence pause time ($p = 0.20$). Walking time had a statistically significant effect on pause time ($p = 1.03e^{-12}$): with every second increase in walking time, participants paused 0.03s longer ($se = 0.0042s$). The interaction between walking time and level of English was also statistically significant ($p = 0.0084$), meaning that the effect of walking time on pause time was different for native vs. non-native speakers. On average, non-native speakers paused 0.34s less than native speakers ($se = 0.22s$), but this effect was not significant ($p = 0.14$). Figure 12 below illustrates the tendency for non-native speakers to pause less than native speakers across conditions, though there is considerable overlap in values, and pause time followed the same pattern in both groups:

Figure 12: Median and distribution of pause time in each walking-and-talking condition for native and non-native speakers.

Native speakers had an average pause time of 2.31s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.61s$), 2.72s in condition 4 ($sd = 0.66s$), and 2.17s in condition 5 ($sd = 0.54s$). Non-native speakers had an average pause time of 2.07s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.48s$), 2.40s in condition 4 ($sd = 0.70s$), and 1.97s in condition 5 ($sd = 0.56s$).

Due to the significant interaction, native and non-native speakers were analysed separately for the effect of walking time on pause time: Participants walked on average 25.43% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their pause time increased by 18.11% for native, and 15.95% for non-native speakers. Participants walked 16.15% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, while their pause time decreased by 5.97% for native and 4.995% for non-native speakers.

Figure 13: Values for pause time in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for native and non-native speakers.

Figure 13 shows a trend for the native speakers for pause time to increase with increasing walking time, while for the non-native speakers, pause time remains roughly constant for different walking times. Although the data are spread out, different participants display a similar relationship between walking time and pause time.

4.2 Syllable: Did Speech Entrain to Gait during Syllable Repetition?

4.2.1 Did Walking Speed change between Conditions?

In the Syllable group, walking time was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.95$) or gender ($p = 0.25$). The linear mixed effects models for both the CONT and PAU groups returned significant p -values for at least one comparison between two walking conditions, indicating that condition had a significant effect on how fast participants walked. On average, the PAU group had a longer walking time than the CONT group by 1.76s ($se = 2.30s$), meaning participants who paused after every syllable walked slower than participants who produced syllables continuously. However, this effect was not statistically significant ($p = 0.46$), which justifies grouping CONT and PAU values for walking time together in the subsequent analyses.

The average walking time was 33.00s in condition 2 ($sd = 3.44s$), 33.33s in condition 3 ($sd = 3.93s$), 40.91s in condition 4 ($sd = 6.69s$), and 28.00s in condition 5 ($sd = 3.28s$). The difference between conditions 2 and 3 was not significant ($p = 0.88$). The differences in walking time were significant between any of the remaining conditions (i.e., 2-4, 2-5, 3-4, 3-5, 4-5) at $p < 0.001$. This shows that participants significantly altered their walking speed according to experimental instructions. The non-significant difference between conditions 2 and 3 had no bearing on the subsequent analyses since only the walking-and-talking conditions were investigated for the speech measures' dependency of walking time.

Figure 14: Median and distribution of walking time in each walking condition for CONT and PAU.

4.2.2 Did the Syllable Count change depending on Walking Speed?

A linear mixed effects model with syllable count as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 0.00027$): with every second increase in walking time, participants produced 0.28 syllables less ($se = 0.07$). Syllable count was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.068$) or gender ($p \geq 0.058$). The interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant ($p = 0.0043$), meaning the effect of walking time on syllable count was different for the CONT vs. PAU group. CONT participants produced on average 25.46 syllables more in the 20s-interval than PAU participants ($se = 9.65$). This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.022$).

Figure 15: Median and distribution of syllable count in each walking-and-talking condition for CONT and PAU.

In 20s, CONT participants produced on average 51.38 syllables in condition 3 ($sd = 17.23$), 52.65 syllables in condition 4 ($sd = 21.97$), and 57.73 syllables in condition 5 ($sd = 23.69$). PAU participants produced on average 28.1 syllables in condition 3 ($sd = 5.40$), 24.7 syllables in condition 4 ($sd = 5.16$), and 33.7 syllables in condition 5 ($sd = 6.33$).

Since the interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on syllable count separately for CONT and PAU: Participants walked on average 22.74% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their syllable count increased by 2.48% for CONT and decreased by 12.10% for PAU. Participants walked 15.99% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, and their syllable count increased by 12.36% for CONT and 19.93% for PAU.

Figure 16: Syllable count in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for CONT and PAU.

In Figure 16, syllable count seems to remain roughly constant for different walking times. Although the data are spread out, different participants as well as the two groups display a similar relationship between walking time and syllable count. The linear mixed model outcome, however, suggests that syllable count was significantly influenced by walking time in that longer walking times, i.e., slower walking speeds, led to lower numbers of syllables being produced in 20s. The comparison of mean walking time and syllable count suggests that in the CONT group, this trend is contradicted since participants produced 2.48% more syllables in the slow than in the normal condition. In the CONT group, the increase in syllable count from condition 3 to 5 was of a similar magnitude to the increase in walking speed. In the PAU group, the increase in syllable count between conditions 3 and 5 exceeded the increase in walking speed by nearly 4%. Between conditions 3 and 4, PAU showed a decrease in both walking speed and syllable count, though the difference in walking time between the two conditions was greater than the difference in syllable count.

These results suggest that walking speed affected the syllable count produced in 20s in that when walking faster, participants tended to produce more syllables and when walking more slowly, participants produced less syllables. This means that participants' syllable rate increased and decreased with their walking speed. The difference between walking speeds was similar to the difference in syllable count between the normal and fast conditions. Between the normal and slow conditions, walking speed slowed down to a greater extent than syllable count decreased in the PAU group, and in the CONT group, the syllable count even increased slightly with slower walking speed.

4.2.3 Did Articulation Rate Entrain to Gait?

A linear mixed effects model with articulation rate as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group as independent variables returned a significant effect of walking time ($p = 0.0045$): with every second increase in walking time, participants' articulation rate decreased by 0.02syllables/s ($se = 0.007$ syllables/s). Articulation rate was

not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.27$) or gender ($p \geq 0.83$). The interaction between walking time and Group was not significant ($p = 0.47$), meaning the effect of walking time on articulation rate was not significantly different for the CONT vs. PAU group. On average, PAU participants had a higher articulation rate than CONT participants by 1.02syllables/s ($se = 0.66$ syllables/s), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.15$). Although PAU participants had a higher articulation rate than CONT participants throughout, there is considerable overlap in the values, and articulation rate follows a similar pattern across conditions, as illustrated in Figure 17:

Figure 17: Median and distribution of articulation rate in each walking-and-talking condition for CONT and PAU.

CONT participants' average articulation rate was 2.80syllables/s in condition 3 ($sd = 0.91$ syllables/s), 2.89 syllables/s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.14$ syllables/s), and 3.15syllables/s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.22$ syllables/s). PAU participants had an average articulation rate of 3.89syllables/s in condition 3 ($sd = 1.03$ syllables/s), 3.78 syllables/s in condition 4 ($sd = 1.41$ syllables/s), and 4.55syllables/s in condition 5 ($sd = 1.92$ syllables/s).

Since the interaction between walking time and Group was not statistically significant, I analysed the effect of walking time on syllable count for CONT and PAU together: Participants walked on average 22.74% slower in condition 4 compared to 3, and their articulation rate increased by 0.65%. Participants walked 15.99% faster in condition 5 compared to 3, and their articulation rate increased by 14.25%.

Figure 18: *Articulation rate in dependency of walking time in the walking-and-talking conditions for CONT and PAU.*

From Figure 18, no obvious trend is discernible for the relationship between articulation rate and walking time. Although the data are spread out, most participants of both groups show a relatively constant articulation rate at different walking speeds. Some participants, like P19, show more variation in their articulation rate, but without clear correlation between articulation rate and walking time. The linear mixed model outcome suggests that articulation rate was significantly influenced by walking time in that longer walking times, i.e., slower walking speeds, led to lower articulation rates and shorter walking time, i.e., higher walking speeds, led to higher articulation rates. In the comparison of mean walking time and articulation rate, this trend is contradicted since articulation rate increased slightly in the slow compared to the normal condition, while walking speed slowed considerably. The increase in articulation rate between conditions 3 and 5 was of nearly the same magnitude as the increase in walking speed.

These results suggest that walking speed affected articulation rate in that when walking faster, participants produced more syllables per second and when walking more slowly, participants produced less syllables per second. The difference between walking speeds was similar to the difference in articulation rate between the normal and fast conditions. Between the normal and slow conditions, walking speed slowed down while articulation rate increased slightly.

4.2.4 *Did the Number of Pauses change depending on Walking Speed?*

A linear mixed effects model with number of pauses as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that the number of pauses participants made in 20s was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.68$), gender ($p \geq 0.13$), or walking time ($p = 0.52$).

4.2.5 *Did Utterance Time Entrain to Gait?*

A linear mixed effects model with utterance time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that participants' utterance time in the 20s- interval was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.49$), gender ($p \geq 0.054$), or walking time ($p = 0.64$).

4.2.6 *Did Pause Time Entrain to Gait?*

A linear mixed effects model with pause time as the dependent variable and walking time, age, gender, participant, and the interaction between walking time and Group showed that participants' pause time in the 20s- interval was not significantly influenced by age ($p = 0.49$), gender ($p \geq 0.054$), or walking time ($p = 0.64$).

5 Discussion

This study investigated whether speech would entrain to gait when manipulating walking speed. Since gait is governed by periodic control structures, entrainment of speech to gait would support a periodic, oscillatory model of speech production planning.

The experimental paradigm included two different speech tasks, reading of a text and repeated syllable production, which participants executed while walking at different speeds. Measurements were collected for walking speed, duration of reading the text once (Prose group only), syllable count (Syllable group only), articulation rate (Syllable group only), number of pauses, utterance time, and pause time. In the statistical analysis, it was first important to establish whether participants significantly altered their walking speed between different experimental conditions. Then, the influence of walking speed on the different speech measures was analysed separately for the Prose and Syllable groups to establish whether entrainment of speech to gait took place.

5.1 Walking Time

In both the Prose and Syllable group, condition significantly affected participants' walking time, meaning subjects altered their walking speed according to experimental instructions, so that the analysis of walking time had to be done separately for the Prose and Syllable groups. Within the Prose group, there was no statistically significant difference in walking time between native and non-native speakers, and within the Syllable group, there was no significant difference between CONT and PAU, meaning that walking speed was comparable between the different subgroups of the Prose and Syllable cohorts.

In the Prose group, there was a significant difference between each of the four walking-and-talking conditions, including between normal-walking (2) and normal-walking-and-talking (3): participants walked significantly slower when simultaneously reading the text than they did when just walking. In the Syllable group, all walking-and-talking conditions differed significantly from each other in walking speed except conditions 2 and 3. This indicates that reading a text places a higher processing load on speakers than syllable repetition, so that reading slows concurrent walking while syllable production does not. Alternatively, the slowing effect may be due to Prose participants being handed a physical sheet to read the text off, while Syllable participants did not require such a requisite.

Directing their gaze onto the text while walking may have caused Prose participants to slow down to avoid tripping or crossing the boundaries of the walking stretch. Both explanations are plausible and not mutually exclusive. To further investigate how walking is affected by speech, it would be interesting to have participants either memorise a text or talk freely about a chosen topic while walking, so that the additional visual distraction of reading from a sheet of paper be removed.

5.2 Speech Measures

In the Prose group, non-native speakers had a significantly longer duration and longer utterance time than native speakers, but there was no statistically significant difference in number of pauses or pause time. This indicates that native and non-native pause patterns were comparable and non-native speakers needed longer to articulate the prose than native speakers, increasing their utterance time and thus their duration. Crucially, this difference is not due to speech errors, since these were not counted towards utterance time or duration (see 2.4).

Walking time significantly affected duration, utterance time, and pause time in that a longer walking time, i.e., slower walking speed, led to longer duration, utterance time, and pause time. The interaction between walking time and level of English was only statistically significant for pause time, but not duration and utterance time. Walking time did not have a significant effect on number of pauses, suggesting that walking speed did not affect the number of pauses participants made during one repetition of the text. Since number of pauses was constant but pause time changed, we can conclude that slower walking speeds led to longer pause durations rather than more pauses, and faster walking speeds led to shorter pause durations rather than less pauses.

If talking entrains to walking, I expected to see duration, utterance time, and pause time increase and decrease in line with walking time. It is true that these speech measures increased with increasing walking time, i.e., with slower walking speeds, and that this effect was statistically significant. However, the speech measures did not change to the same extent as walking time. Pause time is the only variable which increased by nearly the same percentage as walking time between the normal and slow conditions. Overall, the effect size was much greater for walking time than for the speech measures. If entrainment were happening, I would expect the effect to be of a similar magnitude for walking and talking.

In the Syllable group, CONT speakers had a significantly higher syllable count, lower number of pauses, higher utterance time, and lower pause time than PAU speakers, but there was no statistically significant difference in articulation rate. These differences are to be expected since PAU participants paused after every syllable while CONT participants only paused occasionally. The increased number of pauses led to a higher pause time and thereby lower utterance time of PAU speakers in the 20s-interval. Since PAU speakers had a shorter utterance time than CONT speakers, but both groups articulated syllables at the same rate, it follows that CONT participants had a significantly higher syllable count.

Walking time significantly affected syllable count and articulation rate in that a longer walking time, i.e., slower walking speed, led to lower syllable count and articulation rate. The interaction between walking time and Group was statistically significant for syllable count but not articulation rate. Walking time did not have a significant effect on number of pauses, utterance time, or pause time.

If talking entrains to walking, I expected to see a negative correlation of syllable count and articulation rate to walking time, which is indeed the case. I expected utterance time and pause time to stay roughly constant since the length of the analysed interval was fixed at 20s and it is plausible for the proportions of utterance time and pause time to stay the same at different walking speeds. Since

walking time did not significantly influence utterance time or pause time, this prediction was met. Walking time did not significantly affect number of pauses, suggesting that walking speed did not affect the number of pauses participants made in 20s.

Although syllable count and articulation rate increased at faster and decreased at slower walking speeds, the magnitude of this change is much smaller for talking than walking between the normal and slow conditions. Against predictions, CONT speakers' syllable count and articulation rate increased slightly in the slow compared to the normal condition, although the effect size is so small that it may be functionally negligible. In the fast compared to the normal condition, the increase in syllable count and articulation rate was of a similar extent to the increase in walking speed.

5.3 Results in the Theoretical Context

These results show that walking speed influenced speech in a way that resembles entrainment of talking to walking, and that this effect was statistically significant. Walking speed affected pause time as well as utterance time and articulation rate, contradicting the results in Jablecki (2013) where only pause durations entrained to walking. These results are in line with the expectation that entrainment of speech to gait should apply to all aspects of speech since it would seem implausible for a coupled oscillator system to guide pause duration but not articulation. However, the effect size for the changes between conditions was much smaller for speech than gait, even though if talking entrained to walking, we would expect both to change to the same extent. The only instances in which the difference in speech measures was comparable to the difference in walking speed was for the comparison between the normal and fast conditions in the Syllable group and the normal-slow comparison in the Prose group – though in the latter case, this applied only to pause time, not utterance time or duration. This indicates that entrainment of speech and gait may be more likely to occur during syllable repetition, since it constitutes a more periodic, rhythmic motor task than natural speech.

Although the patterns in the data are not clear enough to say with certainty that talking entrains to walking and that speech planning is thus guided by coupled oscillators, the effects of gait on speech found in this experiment would need to be accounted for in a model of speech production. While the formulation of an alternative model lies outwith the scope of this study, for non-oscillatory approaches to speech production planning, see Turk & Shattuck-Hufnagel (2020).

5.4 General Shortcomings of this Study

Due to COVID-19 restrictions, data collection took place outdoors in a public space. This led to background noise from wind, machines, passers-by etc. in the recordings, making annotation difficult in certain instances. A more accurate annotation may be achieved with recordings made in a sound-controlled environment.

Further, the participant cohort was relatively small with, after exclusions, 16 participants in the Prose group, eight of which were native and eight non-native speakers, and 12 participants in the Syllable group, eight of which fell in the CONT and four in the PAU group. It would be interesting to conduct the same experiment with a larger participant cohort to confirm whether the findings reflect general behavioural patterns or are specific to the speakers who happened to take part in this study.

Any future experiments of this kind should also control for speech behaviour in the Syllable condition. Although all Syllable participants were given the same instructions, eight produced syllables continuously (CONT), four paused after each syllable (PAU), two varied in their pause

patterns (excluded), and two simulated a conversational rhythm (excluded). This variability indicates that more precise instructions may have been needed when conducting the experiment.

A conceivable reason for the effect size of walking speed on speech being smaller than might be expected in the case of entrainment of the two motor behaviours could be the speech intervals that were chosen for analysis. In both the Prose and Syllable group, speech measurements were taken from intervals at the start of the recordings. It may be that entrainment of speech to gait takes a certain adaptation phase and that a bigger effect size on speech would have been observed if experiment conditions had been longer and speech intervals for analysis taken 10s, 20s or even 30s after the onset of speech production.

6 Conclusion

This paper has introduced the AP/TD model of speech production planning with a focus on its coupled oscillator mechanism. If speech is governed by coupled oscillators, I expected it to entrain to a rhythmic action such as walking. Previous papers have shown that entrainment of other motor behaviours to walking is possible and have even found entrainment of speech to gait, although this effect was limited to pauses – contradictory to AP/TD's predictions.

The current study employed a walking-while-talking paradigm in which participants walked at different speeds while either reading a text or repeatedly producing the syllable 'ba'. Entrainment of speech to gait, if present, was expected to be more pronounced during the syllable production task due to its repetitive nature.

In the Prose group, a statistically significant effect of gait on overall duration, utterance time, and pause time was found. Each of these speech measures increased at slower and decreased at faster walking speeds. In the Syllable group, walking speed had a statistically significant effect on the syllable count produced in 20s and participants' articulation rate. Both syllable count and articulation rate were lower at slower walking speeds and higher at faster walking speeds.

These effects might be interpreted as entrainment of speech to gait, however, the change in speech measures was much smaller in magnitude than the change in walking speed between different walking conditions. If entrainment were happening, one would expect speech to change to a similar extent as gait. The only instances in which this was the case were for pause time – but not utterance time or overall duration – between the normal- and slow-walking conditions in the Prose group, and for syllable count and articulation rate between the normal- and fast-walking conditions in the Syllable group. This indicates a more stable entrainment pattern during repetitive syllable production than prose.

In conclusion, speech was clearly influenced by gait velocity in a statistically significant way in this experiment – a finding which supports a coupled oscillator model of speech production. However, an oscillatory model would have to account for the fact that for the most part, the effect size on speech measures was much smaller than the changes in gait. On the other hand, non-oscillatory models would need to explain why a significant influence of walking on speech was found in the first place. A repetition of this experiment with a larger participant cohort is recommended to establish the generalisability of these results.

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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix One

Text read by participants in the Prose group:

The site where Old College now stands was known as the Kirk O’Fields in the 16th century. In 1567, Lord Darnley was lodging in the house. At 2 in the morning, barrels of gunpowder exploded under his room. The bodies of Darnley and his servant were later found in a nearby orchard. Somehow, they had escaped the house, but exactly how they were murdered remains a mystery.

8.2 Appendix Two

Praat script used to annotate sound files, based on Lennes (2011): <https://osf.io/smw9>

8.3 Appendix Three

R script used to produce figures & fit statistical models: <https://osf.io/q8ru6>

About the Author

Adela Bartlick Salcedo graduated from the University of Edinburgh with a first-class MA (Hons) in Linguistics and English Language in 2022. Though presently removed from academia, she continues to follow her passion for phonetics by integrating it into her musical career as a singer wherever she can.

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Fostering Second Language Acquisition of Canadian Primary School Children: A Critical Evaluation of Vygotsky's Learning Theory in the French Immersion Programme

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Abstract. According to Vygotsky (1978), language originally emerges as a means for children to communicate with others in their surroundings. This perspective of Vygotsky emphasises the significance of the social interaction between children and their environment, which functions as a driving force for children's language development and learning process. To demonstrate the practices of Vygotsky's theory in second language acquisition, this paper aims to investigate how Canadian primary school children acquire French oracy through interaction with teachers and peers during immersion programmes. Firstly, the two fundamental aspects of Vygotsky's learning theory and their theoretical application in the analysis of the pedagogy of the French immersion programme were highlighted. The importance of social interaction and the limited application of Vygotsky's theory in the construction of children's linguistic skills were reflected through examples of second language learning in the classroom setting. Then, the paper examined the methodology of Vygotsky and discussed its limitations in terms of current education. Additionally, it analysed the nature-nurture dispute concerning Vygotsky's underestimation of the innate factor and the development of his learning theory. Lastly, the paper concluded by arguing that Vygotsky's learning theory had both advantages and disadvantages, which provided a reminder for pedagogic curricula to be more concerned about the interplay between learners, educators, and the learning environment.

Plain English Abstract. In the realm of second language learning, Vygotsky (1978) believed that language originally emerged as a means for children to communicate with people around them. This perspective emphasised the importance of social interaction between children and their environment for language learning. Based on the idea of Vygotsky's learning theory, the present paper aims to investigate how Canadian primary school children acquire French speaking skills through interaction with teachers and peers during a second language learning programme (called French immersion). Starting from the discussion of two main aspects of Vygotsky's learning theory, their theoretical application in the analysis of the teaching methods of French immersion programmes was highlighted. Through examples of French language learning in the classroom setting, the importance of social interaction and the limited application of Vygotsky's learning theory were highlighted concerning children's language development. Additionally, the paper delved into Vygotsky's methodology and discusses its limitations in today's education. Then, the ongoing debate on nature (i.e., what children are born with) and nurture (i.e., what children learn) was examined by focusing on how Vygotsky might underestimate the role of nature in his learning theory. Lastly, the paper concluded that Vygotsky's learning theory had both advantages and disadvantages, therefore, school curricula need to be more concerned about the relationship between learners, educators, and the learning environment.

Keywords: French immersion programme; Vygotsky's learning theory; second language acquisition

1 Introduction: Two main concepts of Vygotsky's learning theory

The zone of proximal development (from now on, ZPD) is one of the central concepts in Vygotsky's learning theory, which includes the actual developmental level and the level of potential development of the learner. In accordance with Vygotsky (1934), the ZPD is defined as the gap between children's

mental age, and the gap between children's real development level and the level of performance they accomplish in partnership with adults. Mental ages are determined based on children's ability to solve tasks that are associated with different difficulty levels and certain ages (Vygotsky, 1934). Similarly, Vygotsky (1978) further defined the ZPD as the difference between children's actual level of cognitive development measured through tackling problems alone and the potential developmental level determined by tackling problems with adults' guidance or cooperation with more knowledgeable peers. Thus, the notion of the ZPD regards learning via guidance or assistance as a regular yet significant component of development, which can be attributed to a child's inter-mental skill eventually transforming into an intra-mental skill through proper interaction (Slater & Bremner, 2017). The importance of guided learning is highlighted to demonstrate how a child may gain a skill with the help of others (inter-mental) and subsequently transform the skill into something they can do independently (intra-mental).

Another main concept derived from Vygotsky is *scaffolding*, which is a process of assisted learning that supports every student to progress to their ZPD or next level of understanding with the assistance of teachers, classmates, or other adults (Kalina & Powell, 2009). In order to accomplish tasks that are beyond the actual developmental level of children, the scaffolding process involves a more capable other providing a less capable one with support and guidance (Vygotsky, 1934). Moreover, Aubrey and Riley (2019) suggested that scaffolding is an engaging practice between children and adults, as the kind and amount of instruction provided to children will likely lead to positive learning outcomes. Therefore, the concept of the ZPD and scaffolding can be used as a theoretical tool to analyse the proposal of French language learning for primary school-aged students through immersion programmes in Canada.

2 The overview of the French immersion programme

With the application of Vygotsky's theory, the immersion programme was first designed to provide the majority group of English-speaking Canadian students with an effective means of achieving proficiency in French, the other official language of Canada (Genesee, 1994). The French immersion programme is now accessible to all students, which means there are various students joining from different cultural backgrounds, heritage languages, and learning styles (Kippan, 2010). These students are then taught together to acquire French as their second language by being immersed in a diverse classroom environment where French is predominantly spoken. In light of the overview of the French immersion programme, it is important to explore how Vygotsky's theory can be theoretically applied to analysing this context of classroom interaction between students and teachers.

3 The application of Vygotsky's theory in the analysis of French immersion programme

The first application of the ZPD and scaffolding can be seen through the interaction between primary school students and their teachers in the immersion class. Despite the majority of students being fluent bilingual English speakers, immersion teachers exclusively communicate with students in French, which is a strategy to encourage and require students to learn to utilise the language (Genesee, 1985). There are various strategies that immersion teachers use to develop students' oracy, such as questioning

and paraphrasing (Ewart & Straw, 2001). During this student-teacher interaction, the role of teachers in giving appropriate scaffolding within students' ZPD is manifested, as they encourage students to speak and answer questions in French. With the help of teachers' guidance, students in French immersion programmes have more opportunities to use their second language to accomplish tasks assigned by teachers, which may effectively help develop their speaking skills.

However, Aubrey and Riley (2019) point out that it is complex and challenging to assess the extent of the difference between what children can achieve on their own and what they can do with adults' assistance. Due to the variety of students and the class size, teachers may have difficulties recognising students' individual differences, thus, failing to provide them with proper scaffolding. For instance, teachers may underestimate students' ability to use French, thus, they need to be cautious during the scaffolding process not to "overcorrect students' usage of French for fear of inhibiting communication" (Genesee, 1985, p. 543). This form of teachers' overcorrection may result in students' lack of confidence and competence in French and further leads to students' fear of communicating with others in French.

Another application of the ZPD and scaffolding can be reflected in students' interaction with their peers during the French immersion classroom. As there is no prerequisite for entering immersion programmes with prior French speaking skills, students with various abilities in French, from struggling readers to outstanding learners, can be found in every immersion class (Kippan, 2010). Therefore, teachers can design group activities to pair up students with different levels of language competency, so that more outstanding learners have the opportunity to share their French knowledge with less advanced learners. In this circumstance, the ZPD occurs as more knowledgeable others assist their peers who struggle with speaking French by completing the group activity together. However, the ZPD may also have some limitations, as it cannot be a continuous process throughout the learning process when learners are placed with peers that have the same language proficiency. If students with the same level of French are grouped together during the activities, there will be no more knowledgeable others to trigger the ZPD and the process of scaffolding. Without the scaffolding process, students who struggle to speak French may find it challenging to complete activities independently and improve their French speaking skills.

4 Theoretical position statement

From the perspective of social constructivism, the important role of social interaction in children's language learning is likely to be emphasised. As a social constructivist, Vygotsky (1978) believes that learning activates a number of processes for internal development that can only function when children interact with others in their environments and collaborate with their peers. Likewise, many other social constructivists believe that learners get enculturated into the learning community and acquire the relevant knowledge by interacting with current learning surroundings, depending on their previous knowledge (Liu & Matthews, 2005). In this view of the social constructivists, Canadian primary school students tend to gradually become enculturated into the French-speaking environment and achieve higher levels of French oracy, by interacting with teachers and peers in immersion classes. Moreover, there is a great emphasis on using French all the time due to the influence and adoption of Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, so that immersion teachers encourage students to speak French even during their free playtime (Ewart & Straw, 2001). During the free playtime, the interaction between students and their peers is likely to occur frequently. This form of social interaction between students during playtime can improve their French speaking, as they voluntarily practice communicating in French with each other while playing.

Although social constructivism regards social interaction as a primary means of the construction of knowledge, some students may prefer to learn independently rather than collaborating and interacting with classmates or teachers during language learning. In Ewart and Straw's (2001) observation of a grade one French immersion class, 11 out of the 13 students were independent readers. The 11 independent learners preferred to read individually rather than discussing the reading content with their teachers or peers. These independent second language learners cultivate their autonomy by being responsible for their own learning, which includes selecting and applying learning methods that align with their language-related tasks and objectives (Oxford, 2008). Consequently, students who learn a second language independently are likely to become more self-directed and less reliant on interaction with others in their language-learning journey. In this case, the view of social constructivism cannot be applied to all students' learning processes because of the different learning styles for dependent and independent learners.

5 Methodology statement

As a social psychological scholar, Vygotsky (1978) developed his theory of the ZPD mainly through observations towards children working with more knowledgeable others. A series of assessments or a range of tasks of varied degrees of complexity is provided to children, and their mental development based on how well they complete them and at what difficulty level is assessed (Vygotsky, 1978). Then, he observed the difference between what children can solve independently during the task, and what they can achieve beyond their abilities under the guidance of or collaboration with more capable others. Consequently, Vygotsky (1978) found that children, by using imitation, were able to accomplish significantly more in group activities or under the adults' guidance. This finding about the ZPD may further prove that the group activities with more capable peers and the teachers' proper guidance in immersion classrooms are effective methods to facilitate students' acquisition of French oracy.

Although the finding of the tests for studying different stages of children's development was described in detail by using careful observation (Vygotsky, 1978), there are some disadvantages and limitations of Vygotsky's methodology. Cordes (1994) suggested that the trustworthiness of data obtained through observations may be consistently problematic due to the inevitable variance among human observers. However, Vygotsky raised his simple observation to a theoretical generalisation of the ZPD (Gindis, 1999), which tends to decrease the reliability of his theory. Additionally, Vygotsky (1934, 1978) observed the development of children through the instruction of school, and later investigated only two ten-year-old children upon their entry into school. Thus, despite Vygotsky's observations, the generalisability of them may still be restricted, as the observations were conducted on a relatively small sample size of children. These limitations of Vygotsky's observational method had better be considered when demonstrating and adopting his theory of the ZPD and scaffolding concerning French language learning.

6 Psychological debate statement

When it comes to the psychological debate against Vygotsky's theory, the dispute concerning nurture versus nature is perhaps the oldest in consideration of human development (Eun, 2018). Vygotsky (1934) highlighted that a wide range of processes for internal development is triggered by learning, while they can only function when the children interact with others in their surroundings and work

cooperatively with their peers. This emphasis on the role of social interaction in shaping the developmental process aligns with the nurture debate argument. Besides that, Vygotsky preferred to regard biological elements as “raw materials” that were subsequently altered by sociocultural influences, while he rarely ever discussed anything relating to how changes in biological factors can impact the sociocultural ones (Lindblom & Ziemke, 2002). Through this lens of Vygotsky, he seemed to overemphasise the role of social and cultural factors in influencing children’s language learning and cognitive development, which might make him neglect the impact of innate factors such as genetics while developing his theory.

Conversely, “the ability to learn the language is the result of innate, language-specific learning mechanisms” (Stromswold, 2000, p. 915). Additionally, based on the most extreme nativist viewpoint, knowledge of some characteristics of language and information processing abilities unique to language development are proposed to be passed down through genes from one generation to the next (Slater & Bremner, 2017). The impact of genetic factors on language development is further emphasised by Chomsky (2011), as he believes that genetic inheritance can be broken down into a distinct segment dedicated to human language and other components that are related to language development, including cognitive processes and neurophysiological frameworks. According to these biologically based views, the acquisition of language is innate rather than learned through the social interaction suggested by Vygotsky in his learning theory. Therefore, the French immersion programme in Canada had better pay attention to the two opposing perspectives from the debate to avoid underestimating either the nature or nurture factors in the learning of primary school-aged students. Besides social and cultural factors suggested by the nurture viewpoint, teachers may also need to recognise students’ varying degrees of innate language learning mechanisms and tailor teaching methods to accommodate students’ different learning paces.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, Vygotsky’s theory has significantly influenced the methods and perceptions of learning and teaching among educators in the field of education (Aubrey & Riley, 2019). His theory of the ZPD and scaffolding has played a vital role in shaping the learning structure and teaching strategies for primary school students and educators, who participate in French immersion programmes in Canada. The adoption of Vygotsky’s concept of ZPD and scaffolding has contributed to students’ second language acquisition of French through their interaction with surrounding people, thus, helping to promote students’ ongoing learning and developmental processes. Nevertheless, there are some drawbacks and psychological debates about Vygotsky’s learning theory based solely on an innatist perspective, which prevent his theory from being applied worldwide to students with different sociocultural backgrounds and innate language learning skills. Hence, the paper provides a reminder for pedagogic curriculum involving effective instruction that understands the complex interrelations between learners’ prior knowledge, experiences, motives, interests, language, and cognitive abilities; and teachers’ own experiences, and cultural influences; and the sociocultural, cognitive, and emotional aspects of the learning environment (NASEM, 2018).

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Expertise, Credibility, Trust and Advice in Veterinarian-Client-Pet Health Communication on Reality Television

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Abstract. Veterinarian health communication differs from human medical communication in that the patient cannot speak for themselves but instead the owner – and the veterinarian have to ask questions and answer them. Since previous research has shown the relative social precariousness of medical discourse, where the patient is clearly marked as a layperson and the veterinarian as the expert, strategies have to be employed to gain the client’s trust. These strategies as well as advice-giving and uptake are studied in three different veterinarian reality television shows with a focus on how the pet patient’s needs is negotiated through the client-veterinarian communication.

Plain English Abstract. Veterinarians communicate differently with their patients than doctors who treat humans. In veterinary care, animals cannot express themselves, so the owner serves as the spokesperson. Previous studies indicate that medical conversations can be socially tricky, with the patient seen as someone who does not know much, and the veterinarian as the expert. To build trust, specific strategies are needed. This research examines these strategies, along with how advice is given and received, by analysing three reality TV shows about veterinarians. The focus is on understanding how the needs of the animal patient are discussed through communication between the owner and the veterinarian. The analysis of the data showed that veterinarians used the pronoun ‘we’ a lot to express collaboration with the client, talked to them in a directive manner as well used humour to appear credible and trustworthy. Results also revealed that clients never asked for advice and veterinarians gave advice unprompted.

Keywords: discourse analysis; health communication; veterinarian communication; advice; relational work; reality television; expertise; credibility; trust management

1 Introduction

Interactions in health are not limited to human medicine and healthcare — rather, they can also pertain to animals and their needs and welfare. In veterinarian settings, already complex communication strategies not only concern the usual two parties (namely patient and health expert) but primarily involve a health expert in dialogue with a client (most commonly the owner or caretaker of the pet), while the discourse revolves around the patient at the centre of attention: the pet. While most animals are able to express their ailments in some form or another, it is the task of both the client and the veterinarian to vocalise the medical condition of the pet at the time, and to discuss the medical procedures which are to follow as a next step.

Since this type of situation not only involves a discourse between client and veterinarian, but also a discourse *around* the pet patient, I argue that there is a role triangle between pet–owner–veterinarian which is continuously performed and negotiated — ideally with the pet’s best interest in mind. In any case, the discourse during the veterinarian treatment is not only limited to the assessment and counsel of the veterinarian party, but the pet’s previous behaviour and medical history which has to be interpreted and (accurately) conveyed by the client. In this context, the veterinarian is clearly expected

to perform an expert role and to appear credible and establish trust primarily for the human client, but also for the pet. On the other hand, clients are assumed to be lay people in the medical field. This classification can be amended, however, since especially long-time pet owners may themselves be ‘experts’ on their pets. Therefore, I expect that each participant (in this veterinarian–owner(–pet) constellation) carefully chooses their communication strategies in the discourse to ensure correct care while maintaining a rapport with the other party.

Medical counsel is not only given but can also be requested from the lay party. While advice is not usually offered deliberately in human medical contexts, the distribution and negotiation of medical counsel in veterinarian settings is another object of interest. This article stems from my Master’s thesis which is in general concerned with veterinarian–client communication around their respective pets, of which expertise, trust, and credibility strategies and advice-giving have been selected as a focal point for this article.

The data for the following analysis has been compiled from studies of three reality TV shows revolving around pet health and veterinarians who encounter multiple patients a day. The chosen medium adds yet another angle to the veterinarian health discourse: not only is the portrayed discourse a real(istic) health consultation, but it also contains an added dimension of entertainment and education for an unseen audience. Given that the shown content is produced with a TV audience in mind, the dialogues are typically expected to contain a degree of stylisation for dramatic and even (in the context of medical reality television) educational purposes. Nevertheless, the discourse is still expected to be spontaneous and natural(istic) (to a certain degree) since the consultations, and most of the interactions, cannot be rehearsed and repeated due to limits on time, resources and money (on the client’s as well as the veterinarian’s side). Treatments are expensive and sometimes urgent, and pets are usually likely to be resistant to any kind of rehearsal or having to spend more time than necessary in a veterinarian’s care.

I aim to look at participant interaction in veterinarian–owner–pet settings that occur during examination scenes in veterinary (documentary) reality TV shows. For this, a corpus has been compiled of three such shows, namely *Bondi Vet*, *Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet*, and *The Vet Life*. The language varieties represented in this corpus are American English (*Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet*; *The Vet Life*) and Australian English (*Bondi Vet*). However, the differences between these two language varieties are not focused on specifically but only respected in the transcription. The selection criteria for the corpus are listed below in the Data section (Section 3). The collected material from each series to analyse ranges from 5 to 8 transcribed ‘pet patient stories’ each, achieving around 20–25 minutes of screen time per series for the analysis.

This article will focus on the participants’ interactions with each other and the management of their respective roles. The analysis focuses on the main aspects of a) strategies employed by the veterinarian expert to warrant expertise, create credibility and trust, and b) advice management. Thus, I will address the material using the following research questions:

- (i) How are the roles of the veterinary expert and the owner negotiated in terms of the differentiation ‘expert’ and ‘lay person’ (since – as I argue – the owner can to some extent be considered the ‘expert’ on their pet), and what strategies does the expert use to warrant expertise, credibility and trust?
- (ii) Is any advice given? How are advice-giver and advice-receiver positioned towards each other?

The unnamed party in this construct, the audience, will not explicitly be taken into account as a participant in this analysis. However, in the qualitative part this will be kept in mind as a segment of the negotiation of owner–veterinarian–pet communication, since the content is specifically produced with an audience in mind.

In order to address the research questions, a literary review on previous research discourse analysis in health contexts is first in order, before touching on what has been studied on the topic of relational work in health contexts, and moving on to communication between veterinarians and clients. Afterwards, I will present a review on research on expertise, trust, and credibility in health contexts, and on advice (specifically in health contexts), and finally offer a brief overview on what has been done on the specific topic of reality television featuring veterinarian shows.

Next, Sections 3 and 4 will present the data and my methodology, afterwards moving on to the data analysis. First, I will quantify the results by means of the labels introduced in the methodology section, before doing a qualitative analysis on the three aspects listed above (distribution of discursive moves, strategies of relational work displayed between interactants, how direct pet communication is managed, strategies to ensure expertise, credibility and trust, and advice-rendering) in a second step. After the discussion of my results, the conclusion will provide an overall summary.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Research on Veterinarian Communication

Following Cipolla et al. (2015), who sought to draw similarities between human medicine and veterinarian medicine communication as a form of ‘One Health’, I will attempt to consider the present research as an extension of previous studies on human medicine communication. The ‘One Health’ concept “links human, animal and environmental health” globally (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 136). This concept encompasses all possible “aspects of health, including mental health via the human-animal-bond phenomenon” (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 140). Considering this aspect, ‘One Health’ not only focuses on zoonoses but is also concerned with owner–pet relationship(s) (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 141).

Thus, communication in a veterinarian–pet context is as important as in human health contexts. The importance of communication in the latter has long since been researched, and more recently also in veterinary medicine. In both cases, successful communication helped “increas[e] client satisfaction and compliance” and reduce general malpractice (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 141). In the case of veterinary–client communication, research has shown that clients not only view their pet as a kind of family member (instead of, e.g., livestock) but this relationship has also been shown to affect the owner’s reactions and attitudes towards the veterinarian consultant concerning their pets (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 141). Therefore, successful communication not only enhances the chance of successful treatment but also promotes the “owner’s comfort, satisfaction and well-being” (and thus, increases the chance of them returning to the consulted veterinary practice) (Cipolla et al., 2015, p. 141). Consequently, communication skills are now increasingly integrated into veterinarian education curricula to enable veterinarian health professionals to not only successfully handle client communication but to also integrate “conflict resolution, organization, the human–animal bond, and grief associated with pet death” (Adams et al., 2004, p. 67). One of the first models to be integrated into veterinary communication education was the ‘four habits approach’ which defined habits as “an organized way of thinking and acting during the clinical encounter” (Adams et al., 2004, p. 21). The four habits approach encompasses the following: “invest in the beginning”, “elicit the patient’s perspective”, “demonstrate

empathy”, and “invest in the end”, which aim at establishing rapport and building trust with the client, promoting the exchange of information, showing empathy and ultimately ensure a positive outcome in health of the animal and client satisfaction (Adams et al., 2004, p. 21).

Adams and Frankel (2004) focused on relationships between veterinarians and clients specifically: according to a survey by the College of Veterinarians of Ontario from 2002–2004, it was revealed that in over 60% of complaints about veterinarian professionals by clients, communication issues were named as the reason (Adams & Frankel, 2004, p. 1). The most frequent of these complaints included not asking for the name of the pet, not returning phone calls, failure to get consent and give postoperative instructions, or absence of empathy shown when a pet was dying (Adams & Frankel, 2004, pp. 1–2). When comparing this with failed communication in human medicine, research has shown that this leads to increased rates of medical errors, dissatisfied patients, noncompliance with treatment, less favourable outcomes (biomedical and psychological), and a propensity to sue for malpractice (Silverman et al., 2005, pp. 884–885). Therefore, an understanding of where veterinarian-patient communication issues could arise is vital for an effective treatment of the clients’ pets.

In a small-scale qualitative study, Coe et al. (2008) examined veterinarians’ and pet owners’ perceptions of their communication with a content analysis of their discourse. They identified five themes associated to veterinarian–client communication: “educating clients, providing choices, using 2-way communication, breakdowns in communication that affected the client’s experience, and challenges veterinarians encountered when communicating with clients” (Coe et al., 2008, p. 1072). Pet owners not only expected information to be explained up front, but also wanted veterinarians to provide information “within the context of the health and well-being of their pets” (Coe et al., 2008, p. 1073). Regarding this theme, veterinarians acknowledged how important it is to educate clients, and felt that they were doing this. However, they also believed that clients could not always necessarily follow the depth of medical information. Further, they mentioned that they felt clients would benefit more from an explanation in layman’s terms and from a description of how the outcome of suggested treatments was to be expected (Coe et al., 2008, pp. 1073–1074).

Regarding the use of terminology, clients expected the communication with the veterinarian to go both ways and for the medical professional to select language they were able to understand, allowing the client to thus also ask “the right questions” (Coe et al., 2008, p. 1075). Further, clients expected veterinarians to present them with a range of options with regards to the treatment (especially considering the material costs). Veterinarians on the other hand replied that they only sometimes offered pet owners a range of treatments, since in their eyes most often there was only one sensible option (and that they only added a potential second one when clients specifically asked for one) (Coe et al., 2008, p. 1074). When looking at the reasons for breakdowns in communication, Coe et al. (2008) focused only on the clients’ perception, but were able to report that issues seemed to arise primarily when they felt misinformed about either treatment, costs, or potential outcomes (Coe et al., 2008, p. 1076).

Since more effort is being made in veterinarian communication education, Armitage-Chan et al. (2016, p. 3) reported that when veterinarians were asked about how they view their (communicational) professionalism, “there was a spectrum in views of the paternalistic/maternalistic nature of the professional–client relationship”, wherein some participants viewed their own role in offering the best treatment option in a directive manner. Other participants, on the other hand, opted for “a more maternalistic professional role” and aimed to provide “different treatment options for the client” while steering clear of offering their own opinion or any advice in a directive manner (Armitage-Chan et al., 2016, p. 3). This “paternalistic” communication style has also been found in Shaw et al.’s (2006) study on communication patterns in veterinarian–client interactions. The study used the Roter Interaction Analysis System and looked for three communication patterns: biomedical, biopsychosocial-

psychosocial and consumerist (Shaw et al., 2006, p. 715). Here, the biomedical pattern reflected the so-called paternalistic approach, in which clients or patients contributed little to the discourse itself. The second pattern was defined as a shared collaborative exchange between the two parties, while the consumerist model reflected a higher contribution from the client/patient, with less input from the healthcare professional (Shaw et al., 2006, p. 715). Ultimately, their study found that the first two models were highly reflected in their veterinarian–client data, the biomedical pattern being the most frequent in use (Shaw et al., 2006, p. 719).

Bard et al. (2017, p. 3) also comment on a “predominant approach [...] of paternalism, where the veterinarian sets the consultation agenda, takes on the role of the guardian and assumes the client’s values match their own”, which often leads to a very one-sided communication where the clients are taking part rather passively while the veterinarian does most of the talking. Further, in their study that was based on role-play interactions they found that “veterinarians dominated the agenda, typically placed minimal value on eliciting the client’s own motivations and ideas [...], kept strictly to the topic of disease management at the expense of rapport building” and in general preferred a directive manner (Bard et al., 2017, p. 12). In this vein of an apparently common paternalistic approach, they also found that when considering further treatments on farm animals, veterinarians often employed the use of a collaborative pronoun ‘we’; however, they could not determine “whether veterinarians were or were not fostering partnership” (Bard et al., 2017, p. 13). Further, it was also left unclear what the reception on the client’s side of this approach was (Bard et al., 2017, p.13). Shaw et al. (2016), in their study on outcome assessments of veterinarian–client interactions, claim that not only has today’s view of this interaction changed, in that the relationship with companion animals is more respected, but also that client communication itself changed in that some conducted their extensive (web-based) research before their appointments (Shaw et al., 2016, p. 420). Their study revealed however that foremost, clients expected information from their veterinarian, with “clear and complete explanations, [...] in various formats” tailored to the client’s understanding, and that they wanted the veterinarian to ask appropriate questions and listen to them (Shaw et al., 2016, p. 428). They also found that a better outcome for the patients and the veterinarian practice was achieved when the veterinarian acknowledged the client’s human–animal bond, i.e. by asking lifestyle- and socially-oriented questions (Shaw et al., 2016, p. 429). Further, it was revealed that clients want to be respected in their decisions, and wish to be involved in the discussion of their animal’s care and to be able to make informed decisions (Shaw et al., 2016, p. 429).

2.2 Expertise, Credibility, and Trust in Health Professionals

In order to successfully propose treatment options, whether in a directive style or not, veterinarian professionals must appear credible and trustworthy to the client. Trust and belief in medical experts is not always easily achieved. Research has shown that expertise, credibility, and trust between medical professionals and patients/owners all have to be carefully negotiated. Birkhäuser et al. (2017) found in their critical review that not only was trust in healthcare providers significantly connected to health outcome, but also that patients who reported “more beneficial health behaviours, higher satisfaction and health-related quality of life” also had “better symptom-oriented subjective outcomes” when trusting their health expert more (Birkhäuser et al., 2017, p. 9).

Mikles et al. (2021) emphasise the importance of trust in health contexts of child development. They found that trust is necessary between interactants to encourage continued communication and further defined it as “the voluntary expectation of a ‘trustor’ that another entity, deemed a ‘trustee’ will

fulfil an obligation on the trustor and where failure to fulfil the obligation brings a level of risk” (Mikles et al., 2021, p. 840). Mayer et al. (1995) found that trustors will trust an opponent if they exhibit the following assets as a strategy: *competence*, *benevolence*, and *integrity* (Mayers et al., 1995, pp. 709–734). Robb and Greenhalgh deem trust not only essential for effective communication but also “particularly critical to healthcare outcomes in those who are vulnerable by virtue of being seriously ill, displaced, uneducated, marginalised in society and dependent on an interpreter to communicate” (Robb & Greenhalgh, 2006, p. 435). Considering models of how trust can have an effect on outcomes in specifically health-centred contexts, Lee and Lin (2008, p. 69) suggest that “patient disclosure, the placebo effect, compliance, and the physician’s caring behaviour” have an influence on patients’ trust as well as the general health outcome.

Grand et al.’s (2013) study on measured trust in veterinarians in training aimed to “develop a measure of trust specific to the context of veterinary medicine” since they argued that building trust in human health care is a primary base for building positive rapport and generating positive outcomes (Grand et al., 2013, p. 330). When questioning the clients, they primarily named “professionalism and technical candor” as the main factors for helping to establish trust (Grand et al., 2013, p. 330). Professionalism in this context was defined as appearing competent as a figure of authority that incorporated a neutral position towards medical treatments and prognosis, with no apparent personal motives in their recommendations. Further, they let clients articulate their concerns and questions (Grand et al., 2013, p. 330). Regarding the factor of ‘technical candour’, the questioned participants defined this as a competent attitude when dealing with clients such as “providing full disclosure about one’s interpretations of diagnostic tests, results, and personal recommendations”, therefore clients are more trusting with veterinarian professionals if they appear competent in completing a given task (Grand et al., 2013, p. 330). Further, they linked their findings back to veterinarian education, with the goal of increasing client satisfaction in general but more importantly garnering more adherence from clients to ensure better continuous care for their pets (Grand et al., 2013, pp. 331–332).

2.3 Advice in Health Contexts

De Capua and Dunham (1994, p. 519) consider advice as “opinions or counsel given by people who perceive themselves as knowledgeable, and/or who the advice seeker may think are credibly trustworthy and reliable”. Advice in health contexts is a delicate matter as research suggests: Sarangi and Clark (2002) have found that often it is stated in the hospital policy to not explicitly advise patients but to rather inform them and leave it up to them to make the decision themselves how to proceed (Sarangi & Clark, 2002, pp. 145–148). Locher and Schnurr (2017, p. 698) emphasise that advice-rendering “is a complex interplay of relational work strategies on different levels”. Therefore, if advice is given in health contexts, it has been shown to display “sensitivity to face concerns by formulating advice in the form of declarative sentences and questions” (Locher & Schnurr, 2017, p. 699). There can also be cases of imperative formulated advice (which are however embedded within an entire response and therefore somewhat mitigated as Locher shows (2006, pp. 98–101)). Since advice-seeking is face-sensitive for both parties, advice-seekers often refer to certain strategies. Principal among them De Capua and Dunham (1994, p. 524) identified “*explanation*, *elaboration*, and *narration*”. On the other hand, they emphasise that if the issue could not be clarified during the previous communication, three steps have to be taken in order to give advice successfully: “determining what the problem is, what the options are for solving the problem, and what action, if any, should be taken in the future” (De Capua & Dunham, 1994, p.526).

In turn, Suggs et al. (2008) found that if advice was solicited in health contexts, this was a strong indicator for behavioural change, and that when communication between patient and professional was contributed to heavily by the patient, it led to better results in their health (Suggs et al, 2008, p. 4). Concerning how medical professionals solicit advice in offline and online health contexts, Pudlinski (1998) as well as Locher (2006) have found that (apart from the directive approach) there are three indirect methods on how to offer advice: “incorporating a solution within a query; sharing one’s own problem and solution; and merely giving information about a solution” (Locher 2006, pp. 260–261, cf. Harrison & Barlow, 2009; Pudlinski, 1998).

Bard et al. (2017) found in their qualitative research on veterinarian–client interaction that the communication in general featured a directive approach, “whilst advisory interactions on-farm are often restricted to fit around other practical tasks” and found this comparable to communication in small animal practices (Bard et al., 2017, p. 13).

2.4 Health in Reality Television

Today, health concerns in all facets are portrayed in every broadcast format on television. It is no longer only news broadcasts that bring the audience’s attention to health content; entertainment shows in all forms communicate health content as well (Christenson & Ivancin, 2006, p. 3). Christenson and Ivancin (2006, p. 4) pinpoint three main reasons why reality television sends health messages to the audience: firstly, “contrivance aside, viewers often perceive RTV [reality television] as being ‘real’ or ‘authentic’ on some level, certainly more real than scripted drama”, secondly, participants in these shows are designed as a person the audience can identify with and therefore their experiences are made “more relevant to the viewer”. Thirdly, both of these previously mentioned reasons “are known to increase the likelihood that viewers’ knowledge, attitudes, values and behavior will be influenced by the show” (Christenson & Ivancin, 2006, p. 4). Further, they found that healthcare practitioners, along with doctors, are usually positively portrayed. Medical professionals are shown as “intelligent, courageous, decisive, principled, sensitive to the feelings of their patients, and successful in their treatments”. (Christenson & Ivancin, 2006, p. 9). Medical practitioners in reality television seemingly have (almost) no bad outcomes, even though they must experience as many failings as other practitioners do. However, the show simply chooses not to show this (Christenson & Ivancin, 2006, pp. 9–10). These findings are also corroborated by Holtz (2007, p. 60): events in medical reality television shows happen as in actual medical reality, however, “which stories and elements to focus on and which to omit, is what separates TV from reality”. Further, he elaborates that the general outcomes of the stories are not only of importance for them to make the cut, but also how the whole narrative of the medical cases fits into the series’ frame. Some shows also choose to show narratives with bad outcomes, but they do not appear in the same frequency as would be medically accurate, since too many bad outcomes in an episode or series would be negatively evaluated (Holtz, 2007, pp. 62–63).

2.5 Veterinarian Reality Television Shows

Research concerning veterinarian-focused reality television is quite scarce. Hill (2005, p. 153), in her extensive research on reality television and its audience, also includes a scope on audiences of veterinary reality television shows. She found that regarding the content, it is mostly framed by a narrative. These “narrative arcs” are important as Hill argues, since the main subject in focus, the animal, cannot speak (in contrast to patients in hospital reality television shows) (Hill, 2005, p. 153).

Like human patients, the animals' medical problems, and thus to a certain extent, their suffering, is shown but they themselves cannot share "their anxieties regarding their illness and hopes for recovery" (Hill, 2005, p. 153). Further, they argue that a narrative format in such shows serves to increase tension, and "to emphasise the commonalities of existence between humans and companion animals", thus representing a parallel between human and animal patient stories which in turn can be addressed the same way to show the audience (Hill, 2005, p. 153).

3 Data

At first, the corpus for this study was collected via a broad web search with the keywords 'veterinary (TV) show', 'veterinary reality show', and 'veterinary documentary show'. This search for veterinarian-focused (documentary) reality shows yielded 27 results. These 27 results were catalogued according to content (how much of the material actually showed veterinarian-owner-patient interactions), number of seasons and episodes, and availability to watch or download. From these original 27, 12 were selected according to their availability (i.e. some were no longer available or only with a subscription to British cable providers). Of the 12, six were deemed suitable in terms of the content they provided (e.g. they contained enough screen time that showed veterinarian-owner-pet interactions such as taking history, doing examinations, and consultations). The overall selection criteria for the corpus were therefore the following:

- (a) The material had to be easily accessible for legal watching (i.e. via YouTube).
- (b) The material had to portray a direct owner/pet caregiver-vet interaction, excluding material that merely cut between interviews of people speaking directly to the camera, and/or only included the portrayal of pet examinations with an explanatory voice-over.
- (c) Material solely focussing on domesticated pets with owners, not on wildlife animals, since it needed to include owners that have a direct relationship with their animals.
- (d) All material had to be focused on the owner-pet-veterinarian relationship, excluding anything such as outside consultations with other veterinarians. Here, some exceptions were made if the dialogue was presented as an interview but framed as a direct treatment explanation to both owner and audience. This also counts for narrative sequences.

Thus, with the help of the requirements listed above, from the original corpus of 27 shows and the temporary selection of 12 and 6 shows, a final 3 veterinary reality TV shows were picked at random for the analysis. The first series, *Bondi Vet*, consists of seven seasons (151 episodes), the second one (*Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet*) also of seven seasons (81 episodes in total), and the third (*The Vet Life*) of six seasons (51 episodes) up to date (as indicated by *IMDb* on the 15/08/21). From this corpus, between 5 and 8 veterinarian-owner-pet interaction scenarios were selected to be analysed for each series, so that in total around 20 to 25 minutes of screen time per series were compiled. These scenarios could be selected from full-length episodes of an entire series or from single stories posted on the official YouTube channel of the series itself.

These scenarios were then transcribed (for the conventions, see Appendix One). The transcripts included the timestamps and the speaker-identification of each person as well as a brief description of the visual content whenever important for context. Since the veterinarians are public figures and part of

the brand name of the series, their names were kept in the transcripts when they were named by someone, however in the speaker column they were only denoted as ‘Vet’. The owner’s names were consistently redacted even though they most often appear in the series with their full name. However, since their conduct in the clinic concerning their pets, that are also often in bad health, is of a rather sensitive nature, I chose to ensure their anonymity. They were subsequently tagged as Owner1, Owner2 etc. The pet’s name was kept in full in the transcripts.

The first of the selected series, *Bondi Vet*, produced by CBS, plays in the eastern suburbs of Sydney, Australia, mainly at the Bondi Junction Veterinary Hospital led by Dr Chris Brown, originally in partnership exclusively with Dr Lisa Chimes, but since the beginning of the series the team has been expanded to include the staff at the satellite clinic SASH (Small Animal Specialist Hospital). They mainly see small house pets, such as cats, dogs, and rodents. However, they also include a section on wildlife animals in parks and visit more exotic patients such as Tasmanian devils or kangaroos. Most of the footage plays in the clinic itself, but sometimes house calls and visits to wildlife parks are included. The show in its original form ran from 2009 to 2016, with seven seasons and 151 episodes in total; it has since been relaunched in a slightly adapted form.

The second selected series, *Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet*, portrays the Planned Pethood Plus Clinic led by Jeff Young and his staff in Denver, Colorado. They treat all kinds of smaller pets with a special focus on spaying and neutering pets (especially for lower-income owners). The ongoing show produced by Animal Planet started in 2015, and has counted five seasons (60 episodes) up to today (February 2022).

The third series is *The Vet Life* which focuses on three veterinarians (Dr Diarra Blue, Dr Michael Lavigne and Dr Aubrey J. Ross) who work together in their animal hospital Cy-Fair with an accompanying animal shelter in Cypress, Texas. The ongoing show has a strong focus on shelter and pet adoption, is produced by Animal Planet as well and has been on-air since 2016 with six seasons (51 episodes) so far (February 2022).

4 Methodology

As mentioned in the previous section, from the selected corpus five to eight ‘pet patient stories’ or vet-owner-pet interaction scenarios for each series were selected for each series to be analysed. Afterwards, these scenarios were transcribed according to the defined conventions (see Appendix One). Since the veterinarians are public figures and are arguably a part of the series’ brand name, their names were spelled out in the transcribed dialogue and only abbreviated as ‘Vet’ in the designated speaker column. The owner’s names were redacted to Owner1 etc. so as to keep their personal integrity intact, since they agreed to have their name portrayed in the respective episode but could not be asked for this study. The pet’s names were kept in full.

In order to answer the research questions stated in the introduction, this work stems from a larger project for which the analysis was structured in the following way: at first, the distribution of so-called ‘discursive moves’ (concerning the pet) exchanged between veterinarian and client will be examined using Locher’s (2006) discursive moves for an online advice column (ibid., 2006, pp. 35–36; p. 51; pp. 60–62). They were modulated after a pilot-study to fit the purpose of this analysis. The labels (see Table 1) were designed to examine the overall distribution of discursive moves between the participants.

The discursive moves are at first categorized as either belonging to a ‘socioemotional’ or ‘task-focused category’. These labels are of a mixed approach since the primary basis for the labelling system

EXPERTISE, CREDIBILITY, TRUST AND ADVICE IN VETERINARIAN-CLIENT-PET HEALTH
COMMUNICATION ON REALITY TELEVISION

is derived from RIAS as presented in Whaley (2014, p. 150) and from Locher (2006, p. 62). Then, they are categorized into one of the subcategories that can be seen in the tables below.

Table 1a: *Exchange categories (socioemotional and task-focused) labels for the discursive moves (ordered alphabetically).*

Codes: Exchange Categories	Description
Socioemotional Exchange Categories	discursive moves of personal and socioemotional nature
Back-Channel Response	interjections or short answers (such as ‘okay’, ‘mhm’) signifying acknowledgment/understanding of the previous turn
Encouraging	encouragement (often for pets)
Open Category - socioemotional	any discursive move of socioemotional nature that does not fit into any of the other categories
Question - socioemotional	personal question
Reassuring	reassuring or soothing a client or pet
Social Conversation: - Personal Remarks - Greeting - Farewell - Giving Thanks	discursive moves around small talk or other social conversation: - sub tag: speaking of personal feelings or experience - sub tag: greeting (and introduction by name) - sub tag: goodbye, farewell - sub tag: thanking the opponent

Table 1b: *Exchange categories (socioemotional and task-focused) labels for the discursive moves (ordered alphabetically).*

Task-Focused Exchange Categories	discursive moves concerned with tasks, actions (non-socioemotional discourse)
Advice - Asks for Advice - Gives Advice	discursive move describing counsel - sub tag: person is specifically asking for counsel - sub tag: counsel is given (solicited or unsolicited)
Agreement	discursive move showing agreement of a previous point
Assessment	assessment or an evaluation of the pet's condition/situation
Bid for Repetition	request to repeat a point or utterance
Disagreement	discursive move showing disagreement or negation of a point
Explanation	explanation of the discursive move made just before (such as an assessment, information)
Gives Instruction	instructs or directs behaviour
Information	general (medical) information (e.g. on an illness or treatment)
Orders Therapeutic/ Medical Regimen	directs or orders a medical treatment, such as announcing the next step in treatment (e.g. "let's do some x-rays"). This also includes bringing in other medical personnel.
Open Category - task-focused	moves that are of task-focused rather than socioemotional nature that do not fit in any other category
Question - task-focused	discursive move asking about anything action-based

The differentiation between task-focused and socio-emotional data is based on the grouping in Roter's framework; however, for this purpose, these two categories remain theoretical as headers for the codes and will not play a role for the eventual analysis of each participant's share of the discourse (cf. Roter & Larson, 2002, pp. 243–255). For the task of labelling the data, the transcriptions were annotated in MAXQDA2020, with the findings of the label distribution afterwards being exported. Coding agreement was achieved by labelling each coding set (exchange category labels and relational work labels) separately, and repeating the labelling two days later. Double labelling was not allowed. Any diversions and all discursive moves were attributed to the 'Open Category' and then evaluated more closely during the second labelling. Anything that still would not fit into the categories was then separately examined in the qualitative analysis. Afterwards, the results of the analysis were analysed in detail while comparing them to the findings of what had been previously described in the literature on veterinarian health interactions (in general and in Reality TV settings) as described in the literature review of Section 2.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Expertise, Credibility and Trust

For this section, a scope of the material is done in the shape of four focuses found in the literature that add to and warrant expertise, credibility and trust. For this, the already labelled discursive moves (for both exchange category and relational work codes) were analysed in light of the phenomena described in the literature review under ‘Expertise, Credibility and Trust’. These are the kinds of approaches taken in counselling or prescribing treatments (directive vs non-directive), the use of a ‘collaborative pronoun “we”’, the use of humour (by the veterinarian) to garner trust from the client, and the relating of personal experiences as a form of establishing trust and provide expertise from a personal point of view rather than a professional one. The discursive move in question is highlighted in bold in the following examples.

5.1.1 Directive vs Non-Directive Approaches in Counselling

As described in the literature review, there are different approaches to how veterinarians talk about treatment for the pet. The two major distinctions that emerged are the directive and the non-directive approach. Since the style of proposing a therapeutic or medical procedure chosen by the veterinarian has been linked to how a veterinarian was seen as an expert by the clients (Armitage-Chan et al., 2016, p.3; Shaw et al., 2006, p. 715), the following section examines the aforementioned two labels regarding how the discursive moves were delivered. When examining the list of discursive moves labelled as ‘gives instruction’ and ‘ordering therapeutic/medical regimen’ for the speech acts uttered by a veterinarian (or veterinarian assistant), most of the discursive moves are phrased in a directive way, as illustrated in the following:

Ex.1: The Vet Life, Story 6		
01.21	Vet:	uh we’re gonna start off with doing some x-rays. but the x-rays will let us know uhm in totality what’s going on. [with the limb.]

In this case, a client presented their pet with a deformed limb. After examining the limb by hand, the next step is presented in this directive manner. Since this is part of the examination of a pet’s limb, not many options can be expected; however, it is also apparent that the client is not being asked for their opinion. This is also the case for this next example:

Ex.2: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 8		
01.56	Vet:	you know we’re gonna revaccinate him today.

Here, the clients presented their cat which was attacked by coyotes in the area. Upon inquiry, the clients reveal that the cat’s vaccines (against rabies) are not up to date. This speech act here being directly ordered can be justified by the emergency situation, however the treatment was fixed without presenting any other options or inviting the client’s opinion on it. A similar case is presented when a client comes in with a cat which requires surgery for its broken elbow. This the client already knows because of x-rays previously made at another clinic. Upon arriving at the clinic to have the surgery done, the veterinarian makes it clear early on:

Ex.3: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 7		
00.53	Vet:	but we'll repeat a set of x-rays to make sure there isn't anything else going on.

Although the client presented with monetary issues, the veterinarian ordered a repetition of the x-rays to ensure proper care in preparation of the surgery which had to be done. The veterinarian however explains why this treatment was ordered. This directive approach of ordering a treatment and being able to support this with an explanation is in line with what Mayer et al. (1995) described as a strategy for competence which according to them ensures trust (Mayer et al, 1995, pp. 709–734). Grand et al. (2013, p. 330) also noted that this kind of treatment corresponds to their notion of “technical candor” which warrants a veterinarian’s position as an expert.

The veterinarians can also use a mixed approach as this next example shows:

Ex.4: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 4		
06.11	Vet:	so we're gonna send him home a:n antibiotic and some Tramadol. (.) it's not a- it's not a good pain med. but it'll drug him up a little bit you know I'll be honest I can give him enough Tramadol where he can't walk but then @@ he can't walk. @@
06.25	Client2:	right
06.26	Vet:	so as I said (.) catch twentytwo. (.) especially at higher doses so it's becomes more and more painful. I think the CBD oil works just as good as any

In the first part, the veterinarian directly prescribes medication for a dog’s cancer treatment. After the description, however, an evaluation of this prescribed medication immediately follows. This is in line with the previously described strategy of competence. The client takes this recommendation and negative evaluation of the prescribed drug briefly into account. The veterinarian then changes approach with another option that is (quite suddenly) presented. Since the first drug is not ideal according to the veterinarian, he recommends using CBD oil instead, which corresponds to a more non-directive approach of counselling clients.

5.1.2 Use of Collaborative ‘We’

In the entire material, 37 instances of a collaborative ‘we’ were counted overall. Bard et al. (2017) in their study on veterinarian interactions with farmers didn’t determine whether the use of a collective ‘we’ was meant to be a form of bonding or not (Bard et al., 2017, p. 13). In my analysis, I found three distinct uses of the collaborative pronoun ‘we’ in client–veterinarian interactions: two different uses by the veterinarian and one by the client (singular) themselves.

The first use I found is the pronoun being used to reference the entirety of the veterinarian collective, so this use can be considered the ‘collective-collaborative use’ of the pronoun. Here, it is utilised to reference any staff (potentially) involved in any kind of following procedure. This form was found 11 times, and was seen to be used in different assessments, such as announcing a treatment that is being ordered:

EXPERTISE, CREDIBILITY, TRUST AND ADVICE IN VETERINARIAN-CLIENT-PET HEALTH
COMMUNICATION ON REALITY TELEVISION

Ex.5: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 8		
01.56	Vet:	you know we're gonna revaccinate him today.

In this first example, the veterinarian orders a simple procedure that seems unlikely to involve other staff. However, some assistance might be needed, and the treatment of the cat in question was ordered as part of a more extensive procedure, such as stitching, which might very well require the attention from other veterinarian staff. The use of this collaborative pronoun was also used in information provided by the veterinarian, as this example illustrates:

Ex. 6: The Vet Life, Story 1		
01.40	Vet:	one thing we worry about when chinchillas stop eating (.) are the- their teeth. because dental disease dental abscesses can exhibit a large amount of pain and with that they won't eat. (.) like they normally will.

The veterinarian informs the client about what the symptoms their chinchilla displays could point to. The use in 'we' in this case references other veterinarians and serves to illustrate that this view is shared by veterinarians unanimously, which adds to his credibility concerning this piece of information. So, when referencing other veterinarian health experts, they are either referencing other veterinarian professionals as a backup for their credibility or to point at other medical staff potentially involved in coming procedures.

Veterinarians were also observed to use the pronoun in the 'collaborative' sense, Bard et al. (2013) described. This use was by far the most represented (24 times), namely formulating the veterinarian themselves and the client as a unity:

Ex. 7: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 1		
00.59	Vet:	[...] let me take some x-rays (hh) a:nd we'll see: (.) see if we can see something in there

Here the veterinarian arranged for the X-rays in a singular form but the assessment discursive move "we'll see [...] if we can see something in there" is formulated so as to include the client, giving them the feeling of being integrated in the diagnostics and therefore enhancing their trust. The collaborative use of the pronoun was also used in assessments regarding the client's feelings:

Ex. 8: Bondi Vet, Story 4		
11.04	Vet:	so:. (.) it's not the news (.) we want

After giving the clients a negative diagnosis, the veterinarian reports back to the client, including them in his evaluation. This corresponds to the strategy of the four-habit approaches for establishing rapport and building trust by 'eliciting the patient's perspective' which Adams et al. described and 'demonstrating empathy' (2004: 21).

There is however only one instance where a collaborative pronoun was used in reference to the veterinarian and a pet (instead of a client):

Ex. 9: The Vet Life, Story 7		
05.44	Vet2:	okay so you can tell we're still kind of sniffing like that we're a lot better than what we were: . but. (.) we're not out of the woods yet

In this case, the veterinarian presents in front of the client with an interim report on the dog, presenting the current symptoms and status of the pet by use of the ‘we’-pronoun.

Regarding the client’s use of the pronoun, only 2 instances appeared (and those were within the same sentence):

Ex. 10: The Vet Life, Story 1		
04.58	Client:	uhm we’re going to go ahead and (1) (hh) I guess. (hh) do the sedation. uhm (1) do the bloodwork? (.) and we’ll go ahead and get the knots done.

The client announces to the veterinarian assistant that they were going through with the proposed treatment. However, this form does not seem to be part of the same collaborative pronoun the veterinarians used, but rather in reference to themselves and their pet together.

5.1.3 Use of humour from the veterinarian side

Phrases or words that were labelled as ‘use of humour’ can be a strategy to bond with the recipient (Locher, 2006, p. 123). Veterinarians used humour 26 times in regards to a client. The following situation serves as an example for this strategy, where a veterinarian comments on a pet bunny which presents with white fur that does not match its name (Blackie) and a skin problem:

Ex. 11: Bondi Vet, Story 2		
00.58	Vet:	you’re lucky Blackie isn’t black otherwise Blackie would have pretty obvious dandruff for its size

When used within a discourse with a patient or client, especially at the beginning or ending of a session, this corresponds with the strategies of ‘investing in the beginning’ and ‘investing in the ending’ to generate trust between a veterinarian and a client (Adams, 2004, p. 21). This behaviour is also clear in this next example, where a veterinarian assistant greets the dog in front of the owner and talks to them (before drawing blood on the dog for a potential cancer diagnosis):

Ex. 12: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 4		
02.53	Vet Assistant:	hi: Weimy-mymer. (.) my Weimaraner she gives what she wants. when she wants. (.) like oh you want to get on the counter and look up your [big fat do:g?]

The veterinarian assistant not only recognizes the dog as a personality on its own (and therefore also the relationship the owners have with him), she also proceeds to tell a personal anecdote that is humorous and bonding in strategy. Both acts serve to establish rapport with the dog’s owners and build trust with them.

5.2 Advice

Health discourse is not only about diagnostics and information. Some health experts stick to these devices and let any therapeutic decisions that may arise be made entirely by the patients rather than giving actual counsel (Sarangi & Clark, 2002, pp. 145–148). Since the communication constellations in my data are professional health expert opposite a layperson, these advice situations are potentially face-threatening and have to be carefully managed, as was described in the literature section (Locher, 2006, pp. 98–101; Locher & Schnurr, 2017, pp. 698–699). Therefore, only a few discursive moves contain advice, and within them an intricate interchange of relational work strategies on potentially multiple levels can be expected.

5.2.1 Asking for Advice

In the 17 instances advice was given, it was unsolicited, and the clients did not ask for advice anywhere else. The only instance where clients came close to asking for advice was the following example. In this story, two clients presented with their dog which was already diagnosed with leukaemia (for which chemotherapy is available for dogs, however, in contrast to human patients, dogs cannot be cured using this approach as of yet). The veterinarian confirms the diagnosis and reiterates the option of chemotherapy for them. Since a concern of the owners is the monetary aspect, one client states:

Ex.13: Dr Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 6		
02.29	Client1:	I definitely wanna see what our options are.

Since the treatment plan for chemotherapy is already set, the phrasing above is labelled as assessment (what the clients want). The veterinarian then offers to research possible, cheaper chemotherapy options within a clinical study. This was marked as advice and will be analysed in the next section.

The absence of ‘asks for counsel’ are not only inherent with previous research but could also be due to the fact that their share of the discourse with the veterinarian is comparatively smaller. This in turn could stem from two reasons: a) the already rather directive communication style the veterinarians assume which has also been found in this data, and b) another possibility would be that this is portrayed through the format of reality television. No research on medical advice within reality television has been done so far. Interestingly, the clients are indeed portrayed as less knowledgeable than the veterinarian professional or often even completely ignorant of their pet’s symptoms, which would be inherently face-threatening, but the format does not add to that or mediate it by letting the clients ask for advice. Instead, medical professionals have been described as being portrayed as not only intelligent and decisive but successful in choosing treatments (Christenson & Ivancin, 2006, p. 9). Adding to this, they are not portrayed as having as many bad outcomes as they would in real life. Therefore, another reason for the missing asks for advice is potentially the aim of streamlining a pet treatment story in a way that the clients arrive, present a problem, the veterinarian hands them the solution, it turns out to be correct and helpful, and everyone is happy, thus providing the narrative arc that producers aim for (Hill, 2005, p. 153).

5.2.2 *Giving Advice*

Regardless of being unprompted, advice-giving can be found in 17 instances within the material. In general, this matches the described reluctance of health professionals to give advice as described by Sarangi and Clark (2002, pp. 145–148), and the fact that previous research had found that most often veterinarians use a directive communicational style where usually only one option is presented rather than having several choices, and the personal opinion of the health expert is not included (Armitage-Chan et al., 2016, p. 3; Shaw et al., 2006, p. 715).

Since this section on advice is intended to be a small-scope overview of advice-giving within veterinarian reality television, the 17 instances of advice are presented and analysed concerning the manner and context in which the advice is given, and the client’s uptake of it.

Within the show *Bondi Vet*, advice is given twice, both in the same patient story involving a litter of malnourished kittens. In order to ameliorate this, the veterinarian suggests:

Ex. 14: Bondi Vet, Story 5		
05.53	Vet:	the best possible thing we could do for them is probably putting them on a drip. (.) the other thing is that they all are looking pale and it probably would be a good idea (.) to take a little blood sample and just check uhm how anemic they are.
06.06	Client:	yeah

The first counsel the veterinarian gives is to arrange for an infusion. This is followed by an assessment of the kitten’s pallor which triggers her to give another counsel which is to take a blood sample. The directness of the counsel is mitigated by use of the hedges “probably”, “just (check)” while at the same time boosting the phrase with “the best possible thing”. The client takes this up with brief confirmation that they had understood. This approach here is rather directive though and since the veterinarian does not provide any other options, it is clear that moving forward, this is the only option to treat the kittens.

In the next series, *Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet*, the veterinarian gives recommendation on what they think is the best for the cat to avoid attacks that brought it into the clinic in the first place:

Ex. 15: Dr. Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 8		
06.47	Vet:	[...] so I would recommend if you can keep him inside. (it will definitely help with his overall health and life expectancy too. (3) I wish you guys the best. (.) all right Max. (.) you’ll be good now okay.)

This is another instance of directive advice and accompanied with an explanation on why this is recommended as the best option. The veterinarian is emphatic to the clients in that they emphasize the client’s wish for a healthy cat. The vet bonds with the clients by wishing them well, as well as bonding with the cat, by saying goodbye to it. This last utterance from the veterinarian is accompanied by them leaving and it is not shown in the filmed material that the clients respond to it. Since the uptake of them is missing, this directive advice as portrayed here seems to mainly serve as a kind of narrative device providing closure to this pet story arc.

EXPERTISE, CREDIBILITY, TRUST AND ADVICE IN VETERINARIAN-CLIENT-PET HEALTH
COMMUNICATION ON REALITY TELEVISION

Another use of a directive advice in the same series is provided after the veterinarian has to give the clients a malignant cancer diagnosis. After delivering the news, the clients appear quite devastated. Upon this, the veterinarian proposes:

Ex. 16: Dr. Jeff: Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 4		
05.17	Vet:	if you really think seriously and you- you go on for chemo
05.19	Client2:	no I would never want him to suffer. (.) happy just still having him. (.) be able to uh just spoil him and love him.

The advice in here is formulated as an interrogative and the veterinarian does not finish the sentence. The counsel is however, immediately rejected by the client who then voices their own opinion on what is best for their pet. This remains the only instance within the material where a client directly refuses the veterinarian’s advice, which promptly resulted in the veterinarian changing his course of treatment and adhering to the client’s wishes, which is congruent with Shaw et al.’s (2016) findings that clients want to be involved and respected in decisions regarding their pet (Shaw et al., 2016, p. 429).

Several times, directive advice is introduced by the phase “I recommend”:

Ex. 17: The Vet Life, Story 7		
02.44	Vet:	my recommendation is that we’re gonna hospitalize him in our isolation ward. u:(h) treatin him for pneumonia (and hopefully we can get Max feeling a little bit better here. (1) I don’t like to see him like this.)

This directive advice is clearly formulated as such, however no other options are provided, and the clients proceed with this plan. The veterinarian is empathic to the clients by emphasizing the dog’s well-being and his own feelings about it.

Another possibility to advise clients is by sharing their own solution:

Ex. 18: Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 6		
06.16	Vet:	[...] I like putting vitamin e on there.
06.25	Client2:	vitamin e.
06.25	Vet:	get yourself some vitamin e. otherwise he looks really good.

The clients complained about the dry nose of their dog, to which the veterinarian responds by giving them their own solution phrased as an own preference. The clients repeat the recommended treatment to which the veterinarian now changes his counsel into an instruction to use the proposed ointment. This directive phrasing is then mitigated by an assessment of the veterinarian that the dog’s condition is fine otherwise, which is a praising strategy implying that the clients care for him well.

Rather than sharing one’s own problem and solution, advice can also be phrased interrogatively:

Ex. 19: Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 6		
02.31	Vet:	I mean I guess what I'd offer you right now is give me some time and let us do some calling around.
02.34	Client1:	yeah

This example is the take-up from the example already discussed in the previous section, when the clients stated that they wanted to know what options were being provided for their dog's chemotherapeutic treatment. The veterinarian replies with an offer phrased as a query whether he should research treatment options (within a clinical study since that would relieve the client's monetary issues). The advice here is mitigated not only by being phrased as a question but by also including hedging in the beginning with "I mean I guess". This is surprising since the clients came to this appointment with the intent on gathering information on treatment options so the advice here would not have been expected to be mitigated like other potentially more face-threatening instances of advice would be.

Another example of advice formulated as a question is the veterinarian talking a client through a treatment plan for her chinchilla. The first few instances of treatment were formulated as advice, however the last agenda item is phrased like this:

Ex. 20: The Vet Life, Story 1		
03.02	Vet:	[...] another thing I would do while he's under anesthesia is doing a good oral exam?
03.12	Client:	mhm

The client's uptake on all three instances of advice (the two directive ones before and this example seen above) was consistently the same. The veterinarian possibly chose this last instance of advice so as not to use too many aggravating face-strategies since the discussion of treatment options is rather delicate in this instance, and the client did not take the advice very readily.

Mitigating advice can also be done by phrasing them as only giving the clients information about a solution (Barlow, 2009, p. 97). This approach has been found twice in the data, both in the same dataset. When explaining the aftercare of a cat with a complex splint after surgery, the veterinarian instructs the client that no jumping is allowed, and in order to ensure this, the following environment should be prepared:

Ex. 21: Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 7		
06.23	Vet:	[...] so the ideal scenario is that they're in a small room with no furniture in it [which-]
06.31	Client:	[yeah] got it
06.32	Vet:	if you guys can do that that's great.

The client makes it clear that he understood the information and advice upon which the veterinarian praises the client. Informational delivery of advice can also be provided regarding elective procedures:

Ex. 22: Dr Jeff Rocky Mountain Vet, Story 2:		
01.55	Vet:	he's not neutered so we can throw that in for free.
01.56	Client:	thank you.

The client's puppy presented with a leg that had to be treated with infection. After explaining and ordering the treatment for this, the veterinarian also offers neutering the pet at the same time. This information about treatments that would be accessible for the client is gratefully accepted by her. In this case, the information given as a solution also serves as advertisement for the veterinarian's clinic, which has a strong focus on providing spaying and neutering options for animals (often free of charge).

This scope-like analysis of advice-giving and receiving within the dataset showed that not only was it consistently unsolicited, but also illustrated all four possibilities represented on how to deliver advice (directive-declarative, interrogative, personal problem and solution shared, and informational). The first possibility (directive) was in this case the one counted most often. In many cases, the advice was mitigated in some form, or transmitted adjacent to praise of the client, which is not surprising since advice-giving has been described as potentially face-threatening, even more so whenever it was not asked for. The use of advice was shown to sometimes be used as a vehicle for mitigating instructions, in order to fit into the narrative arc of the reality television mediated pet story, or if the advice-giving veterinarian showed themselves to be empathetic and personally invested as an advertisement for their clinic. The distribution over the dataset was uneven, however, given that the analysed dataset of *Bondi Vet* featured only two instances of advice can probably be attributed to the fact that fewer but longer pet stories were portrayed.

6 Conclusion

In this work, three different reality TV series that revolve around veterinarians were analysed. The analysis of the work was divided into four steps: In the first part, the transcribed data were analysed using an interactional analysis framework based on discursive movements. This interactional analysis codebook was based on Locher's (2006) health counselling codebook and Roter's interactional analysis system (Roter & Larson, 2002), which was developed specifically for analysing spoken data in health discourse. In a second step, direct interactions with the pet were examined, with a focus on four strategies aiming at warranting expertise, credibility and trust to be found in the dataset. Finally, the discursive moves labelled 'advice-giving' were analysed qualitatively in a scope-like section.

The next section on expertise offered a scope on the previously analysed discursive moves in the focus of four strategies supposed to warrant expertise, credibility and trust — ('directive approach', 'collaborative 'we'', and 'use of humour'). Veterinarians have been found to voice a large share of their speech acts directed at the clients in a directive way, and by using strategies of competence and technical candour. The material most of the time did not depict the clients discussing several treatment options, which adds to the streamlined narratological arc the reality TV shows appear to be following. Veterinarians have been found to use a collaborative form of the personal pronoun 'we' on the one hand towards the staff involved in any procedures, which was found to function as a source for expertise and credibility. The second use of the collaborative pronoun was when referring to themselves and the client, aiming at making the client feel involved and collaborating in the treatment of their pet which helps to establish trust. Further, uses of humour were found as a special tool of veterinarians to build trust in clients.

The second section did a scope-analysis of the instances of advice found in the dataset. In general, clients (and veterinarians as well) did not ask for advice, which could be explained by the narrative arc designing the story in as streamlined a way as possible, causing the client's share of discourse to be smaller than the veterinarians, or that it simply did not occur in the scope of 20 pet stories that were analysed, meaning more material would be needed to reach a definite conclusion. Advice was in most cases found to be phrased directive which fits into the previous described tendency to a directive discourse style adapted by veterinarians. Giving advice by sharing their own problem and solution, in an interrogative or by giving information were also found. Advice was finally also shown to be used as a form of mitigating instructions in order to adapt these in the narrative arc of the show.

Since the data was derived from YouTube, an evaluation of the comments under each video would be worthwhile, in order to receive a perspective from the intended and actual audience, and their evaluation of the communication between veterinarians and clients. Further, a study on peer-to-peer communication around pet health and needs would be interesting to compare to the findings of communication between veterinarian health experts and clients.

For further studies, a larger scale analysis of veterinarian–owner interaction would be possible which also includes not only small pets but owners of large animals such as livestock or horses. It could be of relevance to see whether there are any differences to be found in the communication with owners of small pets vs. those of large domestic animals. This study could also be repeated with data from non-reality-TV interactions in animal hospitals in the US and Australia, in order to compare and contrast the communication to whether it is similar to the one portrayed via reality TV shows. Additionally, communication around highly face-threatening topics, such as investigating and educating on animal abuse, as well as highly emotional responses such as managing grief regarding pet deaths would be of special interest.

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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix One: Transcription Conventions

The following transcription conventions were based on Whaley (2014: 125) and slightly adapted for the purpose of this research:

Vet: Client:	Speaker identifications are for veterinarian (Vet) and clients (Client). If several appear they are numbered as follows: Client1, Client2 etc.
[word]	Square brackets indicate onset and offset of overlapping talk.
wor-	Hyphens indicate a preceding sound is cut off or self-interrupted.
°word°	Degree signs indicate decreased volume relative to surrounding talk.
(1)	Numbers in parentheses measure silences in seconds
(.)	Parenthesis with period indicates a “micropause”, less than a second.
wo:rd	Colons represent prolongation or stretching of the preceding sound.
word.	Periods represent falling or turn-final intonation contours.
word?	Question marks represent rising intonation contours.
word	Underlining represents emphasis relative to surrounding talk.
hh	H’s alone indicate audible breaths or laughter; the more h’s, the longer the ex- or inhalation.
wo(h)rd	Single parenthesis filled with h’s indicate breathy delivery of talk.
(word)	Single parenthesis filled indicates transcriptionist doubt.
((word))	Double parenthesis filled indicates transcriber’s description or characterization of some event.
@	Laughter. Very brief laughter is represented by @, longer the laughter the more instances of @ are printed.
(z)	Clicking tongue.

About the Author

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The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: Does the Evidence Support its Existence?

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Abstract: In this essay, I explore the Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH) in language acquisition, which suggests the existence of a specific time frame during which humans can achieve native-like fluency in a second language (L2). I begin with a historical overview highlighting the methodological issues and criticism of statistical analysis in CPH studies. I mention two contemporary studies, Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021), which I posit to be good examples of how to respond to statistical critiques. I discuss critiques of CPH research methodology, focusing on issues such as the lack of a clear definition for the critical period (CP), variations in experimental designs, and the effects of the native language on second language acquisition. I propose a hypothesis linking the CP to the development of logical thinking in children and suggest using neuroimaging techniques, i.e., ERP and fMRI, to investigate this connection, drawing on proposals by Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975) to connect CPH with the theories of Inhelder & Piaget (1958). In summary, the CPH for language acquisition remains a topic of debate, but recent studies have provided stronger statistical support. I encourage continued research to better understand the CP and its relationship with cognitive development.

Plain English Abstract: This paper discusses the Critical Period hypothesis for second language acquisition, which suggests the existence of a period in which an individual must be exposed to a language to achieve native-like fluency, after which it is no longer possible. In this paper, I give an overview of the hypothesis from its beginnings with Lenneberg's research on patients with the language-related disorder aphasia in 1967. I detail the methodological challenges of critical period research, including finding an adequate statistical model to analyse the data, and the subsequent improvements by more contemporary studies, such as those conducted by Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021). As these methodological challenges are being overcome, there is more support than ever before for the hypothesis. I argue that the hypothesis is well-supported by the data. Then, I suggest a cognitive mechanism that has been speculated by previous researchers Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975). These two researchers hypothesised that the third stage of the development of logical thought in children is linked to the critical period. I suggest an experimental design using neuroimaging, including fMRI and EEG, that might find evidence of such a link. I conclude by encouraging continued research to better understand the CP and its relationship with cognitive development.

Keywords: Critical Period Hypothesis; Second Language Acquisition; ultimate attainment; learning ability; learning rate; aptitude

1 Introduction

Adult learners rarely achieve levels of L2 ultimate attainment (UA), defined as the peak language development that a speaker attains in their lifetime, equivalent to the UA of those who acquired their L2 as children. Although adult learners outperform children in immersion settings during the initial months (Krashen et al., 1979), children have a long-term advantage in L2 acquisition. The Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH) for language acquisition has been an explanation for this phenomenon. Critical periods (CP) are spans of time in an organism's development when it must acquire a specific capacity, after which it can no longer do so. The CPH posits that there is a CP for the human capacity to acquire language, after which a speaker can no longer reach native-like levels of fluency.

Lenneberg (1967) first formulated the CPH, predicting that language acquisition occurs most efficiently between infancy and puberty. Later research on the CPH suggested that the CP affects L2 acquisition. The CP and its effects on L2 acquisition have been tested, but methodological issues have sown doubt about the validity of experimental results of CPH studies (Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994; Vanhove, 2013). Singleton & Leśniewska (2021, p. 2) posit that the CPH ‘remains unproven but also unfalsified’.

In this essay, I examine CPH literature and argue that contemporary research (Hartshorne et al., 2018; Chen & Hartshorne, 2021) has provided rigorous statistical analysis and that CPH research has strong supporting evidence. Then, in Section 6, I suggest future research to test a potential link between the CPH and the development of logical thinking (DLT) in children.

2 Origin of the critical period hypothesis

2.1 Lenneberg (1967)

Lenneberg (1967) introduced the CPH in the publication *Biological Foundations of Language*, in which he examines converging evidence from language recovery in aphasia patients of different ages, language development (LD) in individuals with Down Syndrome (DS), and the effects of acquired deafness on LD. He hypothesised that the cause of the CP was the onset of cerebral lateralisation, a period in neurological development when neuroplasticity reduces and assigns fixed cognitive functions to each brain hemisphere.

2.1.1 Evidence from Individuals with Aphasia from Traumatic Brain Injuries

Lenneberg (1967) compared aphasia recovery in 88 war veterans with head trauma from data compiled by Russell and Espir (1961) to a sample of 17 children aged 1–18 years old with traumatic aphasia. If the aphasia did not clear within the first three months, the war veterans exhibited permanent symptoms. Even among five patients with ‘slow and protracted improvement,’ (Lenneberg, 1967, p. 145) aphasia symptoms remained. On the contrary, children before the age of nine made complete recoveries, so long as their injuries only affected one hemisphere of the brain. Those aged nine and older recovered sufficient language abilities to hold a conversation, but with permanent aphasia symptoms that amplified with emotional tension.

2.1.2 Evidence from Language Development in Individuals with Down Syndrome

Addressing concerns that the evidence from the groups affected by aphasia from brain trauma may not be representative of individuals without brain trauma, Lenneberg (1967) offered evidence from individuals with DS. In Lenneberg et al. (1964), language development (LD) over three years was observed in 54 individuals with DS ranging from six months old to 22 years old. LD was only observed among those younger than 14. Beginning at age 14, LD stopped. Individuals ≥ 14 years old when the study began showed no LD throughout the three-year period. Lenneberg (1967) writes that the study’s results suggest that LD ceases at maturity, even in the absence of brain injury.

2.2 Krashen (1975)

Krashen (1975) published a paper examined the role of the CP in L2 acquisition, introducing a set of testable predictions for how L2 acquisition is affected by the CP. Firstly, that L2 acquisition early in life would occur through the same process as L1 acquisition before the CP, while it would require a different later in life. Secondly, that L2 acquisition before puberty occurs like L1 acquisition, but after puberty, L2 acquisition requires formal instruction. Thirdly, that L2 speakers cannot overcome foreign accents after the CP. Lastly, that only L2 speakers who began acquisition before puberty can achieve native-like competence in syntax and semantics.

Krashen suggested a potential research avenue when discussing the basis of the CPH. Noting differences in how L2 acquisition occurred between groups before and after puberty, he argued that older learners needed formal and rule-based classes to achieve competence in an L2. Citing Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) theory of cognitive development in children, he speculated that the CP coincides with the third stage of development of logical thought, the stage of formal operations. In the discussion section, I explore this hypothesis as an avenue for future research.

2.3 Johnson & Newport (1989)

The research of Johnson & Newport (1989) explored how L2 acquisition is affected by the CP. They gathered 46 native Korean and Chinese speakers, all of whom were immigrants who had been living in the United States for at least 3 years. Age of arrival (AoA) in the US was considered the participants' first exposure to the English language. AoA ranged from three to 39. The participants listened to recordings of English language sentences and were asked to judge whether the sentences were grammatically correct or not, also known as a grammaticality judgment test (GJT). In total, each participant listened to 276 sentences.

Hypothesising that the onset of the critical period began at age 15, Johnson & Newport (1989) separated the participants into two separate groups by AoA, Group 1 being between AoA 3–15 years old and Group 2 being between AoA 17–39 years of age. They found that for Group 1, there was a negative linear trend between AoA and correct GJT scores with a correlation of $R = -0.87$. This trend did not continue with Group 2. Instead, there were significantly lower GJT scores, and a correlation for the second group was $R = -0.16$.

Johnson & Newport (1989) interpreted this sharp contrast in the linear correlation between the two groups as evidence of an onset of the CP at the age of 15. As we shall see in the next section, this statistical analysis was called into question by Hakuta and Bialystok (1994) and Vanhove (2013), casting doubt on the CPH.

3 CPH Literature after 1989

3.1 Hakuta & Bialystok (1994)

Hakuta & Bialystok (1994) criticised the statistical analysis of Johnson & Newport (1989) and offered their reanalysis of their data, performing a nonlinear analysis of the trend as a function of the AoA. Around the age of 20, they noted a bend in the nonlinear trend. Dividing the data by the new CP at the

age of 20, they found that there was a linear decline with a correlation of $R = -0.87$ before the age of 20 and a second linear correlation of $R = -0.49$ after the age of 20.

Johnson & Newport (1989) were criticised for sampling. There were no checks to ensure participants had grown up with an L1 other than English. They note that childhood memory is unreliable and highly susceptible to being rewritten; those who claimed to have spoken a different L1 as a young child may have been monolingual English speakers with unreliable memories.

They argued that the strenuous nature of the test and having to listen to 278 sentences with four seconds in between sentences was an exercise in ‘mental vigor’ (Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994, p. 70), which they say would be easier for younger people due to normal aging processes.

Finally, they note that Johnson & Newport (1989) failed to account for the effect of the participants’ English language education or lack thereof on the study’s findings. Those who immigrated later would not have the support of an English education system and the advantages of ESL classes, putting them at a disadvantage compared to their younger counterparts.

3.2 Hakuta et al. (2003)

Hakuta et al. (2003) tested the CPH using United States census data for immigrant populations, allowing for a sample size of 23,000,000. They gathered data on the self-reported English levels of native Spanish and Chinese-speaking immigrants who had lived in the United States for 10 years or longer and data on the present ages and age of arrival. They tested their data for a break in the line of regression that would signify that the mean had changed at a specific point, at both the age of 15 as the CP hypothesised by Johnson & Newport (1989), and at the age of 20 from the statistical reanalysis by Hakuta & Bialystok (1994). A change in mean at either point would confirm a CP. However, Hakuta et al. (2003) found a linear decline with no break in the line of regression at either 15 or 20, meaning that there was no evidence of a CP.

3.3 DeKeyser et al. (2010)

DeKeyser et al. (2010) conducted two experiments, which tested the relationship between L2 UA and two factors, aptitude and AoA. Aptitude predicts the rate of progress of L2 learning under ideal learning conditions, according to Dörnyei (2005). Seventy-six L2 English speakers in the first study and 62 L2 Hebrew speakers for the second study, all with AoA ≥ 8 years, completed an aptitude test as well as a GJT. The first prediction was that as AoA increased, the UA of the L2 would begin to flatten, which would indicate the existence of a CP. Secondly, they predicted that aptitude would have a significant correlation with UA only among older participants.

DeKeyser et al. (2010) concluded that both predictions were supported by the resultant data. For subjects with AoA < 18 , UA correlated with AoA. For subjects with AoA between 18–40, aptitude was the predictor for UA, and among those with AoA between 50–75, neither AoA nor aptitude was a good predictor for UA. These results, they posited, would be the expected results predicted by the CPH.

Vanhove (2013) published a paper that reanalysed the DeKeyser study’s data using a regression model. They argued that the regression models ‘present the only valid alternative, provided they are fitted correctly and interpreted judiciously’ (p. 5). DeKeyser et al. (2010) concluded that their predictions had been supported by the data based on comparisons of correlation coefficients. Vanhove (2013) argued that this approach was fallacious because it conflated the correlation coefficient with slope. They asserted that DeKeyser et al.’s predictions were not supported by the data and criticised the study for weak statistical analysis.

4 Criticism of the CPH Methodology

Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) published a position paper criticising the methodology of CPH research and experimentation, arguing that the CPH cannot be properly considered a scientific hypothesis because it is unfalsifiable.

They first attack the notion that the CP ends at puberty, first proposed by Lenneberg (1967). Acknowledging that a CP ending at puberty is a testable hypothesis, there is so much variability in the ages that individuals reach puberty that a true test of this hypothesis would require finding out the individual ages at which each study participant reached puberty. A good example of this is seen in Johnson & Newport (1989), where a specific age was hypothesised to be the end of the CP. The variability in the age of puberty may have affected their result.

A second criticism is the lack of a clear, testable definition for the CP. Instead, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) find such variability in the hypothesised CPs and results among researchers that they cannot be rightly considered to be the same hypothesis, but instead a multitude of interrelated and sometimes contradictory ones. As they note, Hawthorne et al. (2018) hypothesised that a CP for the acquisition of syntax closes at the age of 17, while Dollman et al. (2020) predict a close at the age of 9. Additional researchers (e.g., Granena & Long, 2013) hypothesise separate critical periods for lexis, syntax, and phonology. They argue that the hypotheses and findings are all so contradictory and unrelated to one another that they cannot be deemed to be one hypothesis.

Thirdly, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) criticise the notion that experiments testing for the CP should assess the language performance of L2 speakers based on the norms of monolingual speakers. The notion of a single homogeneous standard of L1 fluency is erroneous, as native speakers vary in their mental grammar. They cite Dabrowska's (2012) research that examined individual differences in the mental grammars of monolingual speakers of Polish to show that factors like education contributed to variation in grammatical constructions.

Additionally, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) argue that there are vital differences in the mental grammars of bilinguals and monolinguals. They suggest that a more accurate test of language skills measures the performance of L2 speakers of a given language against bilinguals who were exposed to that language from birth.

The criticisms of methodology continue with how first exposure to the L2 is determined. Since many researchers have drawn their samples from immigrant populations in countries where the L2 was the dominant language, AoA in the country where the language is dominant has been considered the speakers' first exposure to the L2 by some researchers (e.g., Johnson & Newport 1989). Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) argue that L2 speakers' socioeconomic status, educational opportunities, and the quality of L1 input are confounding variables that make AoA an unreliable measure for first exposure to the L2.

Lastly, they conclude with a discussion on statistical analysis and interpretation. As we have already demonstrated in the previous section (e.g., Vanhove, 2013; Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994), researchers can achieve contradicting results by using different statistical models on the same data set. Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) reiterate this concern in the form of a question: what counts as evidence of the CPH? The search for an answer leads to the following section on the work of Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021), two studies that Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) offer as examples of rigorous statistical analysis.

5 Contemporary Studies (2018–2021)

5.1 Hartshorne et al. (2018)

Hartshorne et al. (2018) find that there are two interrelated variables, UA and learning ability (LA), that concern researchers interested in the CPH. Studies including DeKeyser (2010) measure UA, defined as the peak language development that a speaker attains in their lifetime, as the dependent variable in experiments. LA is defined as the ability to continually gain competence in a language up to the point of perfect proficiency. According to Hartshorne et al. (2018), LA has more theoretical applicability to CPH research. LA should be expected to decrease after the CP is over.

To test this, researchers sampled 669,498 participants who spoke over 38 languages, a sample size that was at the time unrivalled by anything else in CPH literature. GJTs measured the participants' knowledge of English syntax. Analyses focused on three groups: monolinguals with L1 English, immersion learners (IL), and non-immersion learners (NIL). IL included two subcategories, simultaneous bilinguals exposed to English and another language from birth, and L2 English speakers who spent 90% of their post-exposure life (life after exposure to L2) in an English-speaking country. NI were L2 English speakers who spent a maximum of 10% of post-exposure life in an English-speaking country. A novel statistical model for testing the learning rate was used to analyse the data.

There were three distinct findings in the results. First, they found evidence that the learning rate declined by 50% by 17.4 years of age. Their analyses also produced evidence suggesting that learners who were first exposed to L2 between the ages of 10–12 were able to achieve similar levels of UA as late learners. Thirdly, their results suggested that monolingual native speakers reach UA by the time they reach 30 years old.

Returning to the question of statistical analysis, Hartshorne et al. (2018) responded to criticism by Vanhove (2013), who had argued that a sample of thousands of participants would be necessary to offer meaningful support to the CPH. As previously stated, Hartshorne et al. (2018) gathered the largest sample size in the history of CPH research.

Furthermore, Hartshorne et al. (2018) used log odds whereas previous CPH research (e.g., Johnson & Newport, 1989) used percent correct. Hartshorne et al. (2018) deemed percentage correct to be problematic because it inflates percentage differences in the results at 0% or 100%, meaning that there is more weight to a difference between 95% and 96% than there is to a difference of 50% to 51%.

Syntax acquisition was modelled using a novel computational model as a simple exponential learning process, which accounted for current age, age of first exposure, learning rate, and amount of experience. The learning rate was calculated with a piecewise function according to a sigmoid. The novel model allowed a wide range of developmental trajectories. It was fitted to the three groups, monolinguals, IL, and NIL. The model was compared against alternative statistical models but ultimately produced the best fit at $R^2 = 0.89$ with a rate change in learning rate at 17.4 years of age.

Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) were praised for how their statistical analyses improved. After Frank (2018) questioned the results of the novel statistical model, Chen & Hartshorne (2021) responded to the critiques with a stronger model.

5.2 Chen & Hartshorne (2021)

Frank (2018) noted that Hartshorne et al. (2018) failed to provide estimates for uncertainty in any of the model parameters. Chen & Hartshorne (2021) addressed this by using bootstrapping, a statistical

procedure that resamples a single dataset into multiple simulated samples, to derive confidence intervals for parameter estimates. Frank (2018) also found that the study's measure of knowledge assumed a direct link between the portion of correct answers and the overall knowledge of a speaker. A stronger model must account for the difficulty of tasks on the test and what can be inferred from specific individuals' correct and incorrect answers. Frank proposes the use of Item Response Theory (IRT), a mathematical framework that would produce different assumptions depending on how respondents answer specific questions of varying difficulty, to avoid ceiling and floor effects. Chen & Hartshorne (2021) used IRT and designed their experiment to reduce biases related to floor and ceiling effects.

Chen & Hartshorne (2021) acknowledged that the learning rate curve was biased toward sharp drops, which could have accounted for the 50% decline in the learning rate as found by Hartshorne et al. (2018). To combat this, they produced a learning rate model that accounted for a wider range of shapes.

With all these considerations accounted for, Chen & Hartshorne (2021) retrieved data from the participants in Hartshorne et al. (2018) and added additional data from 461,903 participants who underwent the same GJT. The resultant data showed a near-perfect match with the results of Hartshorne et al. (2018), with a decline in the learning rate between the ages of 17 and 18.

6 Discussion

In this examination of the CPH literature, I have examined studies where statistical analysis was criticised (eg. Johnson & Newport, 1989; DeKeyser et al., 2010), and examples of how other researchers (Hartshorne et al., 2018; Chen & Hartshorne, 2021) met rigorous demands of statistical analysis. The collective work of Hartshorne et al. (2018), Chen & Hartshorne (2021), and Frank (2018) provides strong statistical modelling for future research.

Although Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) provide the strongest evidence in support of the CPH, researchers must remember that these findings only provide evidence of a decline in syntactic LA. Whether all grammatical phenomena are affected by the CP is another question to be explored. Both studies failed to acknowledge the effects of the L1 on L2 acquisition. Since only performance on English syntax was tested, future studies should test if the results remain true among speakers of other languages.

The evidence supports a CPH for syntactic acquisition. I would like to explore potential research into the cognitive mechanisms responsible for the CP for syntax. Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975) suggested the possibility of a causal link between Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) formal operations stage (FOS) in the development of logical thinking (DLT) and the CP for syntactic acquisition. In the following discussion, I will create a preliminary hypothesis, suggest a tentative experimental design, and explain the predicted outcomes if the hypothesis is correct.

First, I will explain Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) theory of DLT. DLT occurs in three stages, the preoperational stage (POS) occurring between ages two and seven, the concrete operational stage (COS) between ages seven and 11, and the formal operational stage (FOS) between ages 11 and 15. One experiment they conducted tested children in each stage on how they understood the law of floating bodies. This tested their ability to logically make sense of density and specific gravity, the relationship between the density of water and the density of the object.

The children were given a bucket of water and a set of objects (a wire, a needle, and a plank of wood), and asked to classify objects by whether they float or sink. Participants placed the objects in the

water and were asked to summarise their observations and produce a general rule about floating bodies in water.

Children in POS were split into two stages, substages I-A and I-B. In I-A, children did not produce coherent classifications. In substage I-B they began to classify objects, but the classes were inconsistent and contradictory. COS subjects were also split into substages II-A and II-B. At the beginning of substage II-A, subjects categorised the objects into contradictory classes but used a reversible addition to justify contradictions. For instance, one child recognised the contradiction between his classification of a nail as being 'light', yet still sinking, saying that the object was 'iron', and all iron objects sink (p. 29). In substage II-B, children showed progress in understanding weight conservation and specific gravity. They gained a basic understanding of an object's relative 'fullness' to explain specific gravity, but their understanding of volume conservation was limited, which led to contradictory explanations for floating bodies.

The subjects in FOS demonstrated evidence of hypothetical reasoning through their consideration of multiple possibilities and their respective consequences. They identified implications and tautologies, discarding hypotheses that could not be verified. Moreover, they developed the skill to compare combinations of factors and isolate variables to understand their individual effects. They found that children in this stage began to apply abstract thinking to conceptualise and apply relationships between weight and volume.

Keeping these stages of DLT in mind, we will construct a hypothesis linking DLT and CPH. Such a hypothesis would predict that 1) if a child is first exposed to an L2 during a particular stage of DLT, they will use those logical skills to acquire syntactic knowledge, and 2) logical skills acquired during FOS interfere with the ability to acquire native-like levels of syntax, ultimately resulting in a CP. As Krashen (1975) argues, the onset of the FOS brings about a cognitive change to thinking about problems in terms of general solutions instead of specific 'ad hoc' (p. 220) solutions; the need for an explicit knowledge of the L2 grammar would inhibit the acquisition which provides us with an implicit knowledge of the L1 grammar. It is worth noting that FOS and Hartshorne et al.'s (2018) predicted cutoff age to reach native-like levels of syntax occur around the same time, with FOS occurring between ages 11 and 15, whereas the predicted cutoff age for native-like syntax is 12 years old. Equally important is the predicted age at which the learning rate declines in Hartshorne et al. (2018), between the ages of 17 and 18 years, where they argue that the critical period ends. My proposed experimental design will look for neurologically observable changes that occur at each age.

The difficulty in constructing an experiment to test this hypothesis is that the internal cognitive mechanisms are not readily accessible to a researcher observing from the outside. However, we can infer them from observations of brain activity through event-related potential (ERP) and functional magnetic resonance imagery (fMRI). My experiment will make use of both technologies to produce readings during both L2 language production use and logical tasks.

ERP patterns are brain signatures originating from groups of neurons simultaneously firing, which are measured with electroencephalography (EEG). These can answer questions about the timing of events in the brain and when they occur. DeLuca (2019) mentions in a summary of neurolinguistic research that ERP patterns of P600 are associated with morphosyntactic processing and N400 with semantic processing for L1 speakers. ERP patterns for L2 morphosyntactic processing differ from the P600, suggesting that the L2 learning process occurs differently. It is important to note, however, that the brain signatures of L2 speakers at higher proficiency levels parallel those of L1 speakers.

My hypothesis predicts similarities in ERP reading when participants perform tasks involving FOS thinking and during L2 morphosyntactic processing. If Krashen (1975) is correct about the use of FOS thought processes after the CP and the use of explicit rules to understand L2 grammar, we should

expect to observe similar readings during L2 morphosyntactic processing and tasks involving FOS thought processes for children who have reached FOS. On the other hand, ERP readings during L2 morphosyntactic processing at early stages of DLT should show differences.

ERP measures of bilingual children, separated into groups by their levels of L2 proficiency and by DLT stage, should be tested under four separate conditions, 1) at rest without any cognitive task, 2) during exposure to L1 morphosyntactic processing, 3) during L2 morphosyntactic processing, and 4) while performing a cognitive task involving formal operations. Additional categorisations will account for the previously mentioned age ranges, including the predicted cutoff to obtain native-like syntax at age 12, and the age range of 17-18 when the learning rate declines.

fMRI scans, which provide information about the location of neural activity in the brain, might provide supporting evidence that supports this hypothesis. The hypothesis predicts correlations of active brain structures on fMRI scans while a participant performs a cognitive task involving FOS thinking, and during L2 production. Several areas of the prefrontal cortex have been associated with reasoning skills (Krawczyk, 2017). Research shows that syntactic processing occurs in the left inferior frontal gyrus, inferior parietal lobule, superior temporal gyrus, middle frontal gyrus, and middle temporal gyrus (DeLuca et al. 2019). Observations of overlap would provide further evidence of a link between the processes. As above, the same considerations would be taken to measure children at different DLT stages, proficiency levels in the L2, and at the predicted age ranges for the syntax cutoff and the decline in learning rate.

If the hypothesis is correct, it will be a stepping stone toward larger findings. Further testing will be needed to establish a concrete link. Previous CPH research emphasises the necessity of statistical analysis of the data. Only with large sample sizes and improved statistical models can we form a working theory linking CPH and DLT. There is an explanatory gap between observations of brain activity and the cognitive processes which is not easily bridged, but further research may uncover neurological and cognitive bases for the CP.

7 Conclusion

At the current moment, the CPH literature for L2 acquisition is well supported by data. Critiques of methodologies provide important lessons in how future CPH research should be conducted. The main problem with CPH experiments has been statistical analysis, sample size, and unforeseen variables like aptitude which skew the results of experimentation. More recent studies from Hartshorne et al (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) have gathered strong supporting evidence for the existence of the CP, showing that the statistical shortcomings of previous studies can be overcome. Many untested hypotheses may be the key to turning the CPH into a working theory, including the untested link between CP and logical thinking development.

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THE CRITICAL PERIOD HYPOTHESIS FOR L2 ACQUISITION: DOES THE EVIDENCE SUPPORT ITS EXISTENCE?

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Opaque Segholates Revisited: The Glottal Stop in Standard Modern Hebrew Phonology

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Abstract. In this project, I will address the debatable phonemic status of the glottal stop /ʔ/ in the phonological inventory of Standard Modern Hebrew speakers through an investigation of apparent opacity in /ʔ/-final segholate nouns. The glottal stop alternates with Ø in Modern Hebrew, is never produced in codas and rarely produced elsewhere. Some researchers propose that its realization may be the result of historical influence rather than productive phonological rules. Pertinent to this debate is the underlying representation of Modern Hebrew segholate nouns; a nominal class with a unique stress pattern. These nouns are typically analyzed with a triconsonantal root template, but those with /ʔ/-final roots do not surface with final /ʔ/ in their singular forms. This phenomenon is problematic for Standard Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky 1993), and calls into question the strategy with which speakers deduce the underlying forms of neutralized segments. I conducted an elicitation task in which four native speakers were asked to produce a total of twenty novel, /ʔ/-final words: ten 3fs verbs and ten plural segholate nouns. The results provide evidence that, while the glottal stop retains its phonemic status in Modern Hebrew, speakers prefer to realize underlying final glottal stops as a glottalization period in nouns, and to assume underlying final /j/ over final /ʔ/ in verbs. Additionally, although the participants consistently posited a triconsonantal root for verbs, they exhibited only a weak preference for a third root consonant in nouns, indicating that this template may not be obligatory for Modern Hebrew nominals.

Plain English Abstract. The phonemic status of the glottal stop /ʔ/ in Standard Modern Hebrew is debatable. While historically underlying, the glottal stop is never produced in codas and rarely elsewhere. Some researchers propose that its realization may be the result of historical influence rather than productive phonological rules. Whether the glottal stop is underlying in Modern Hebrew segholate nouns, a nominal class with a unique stress pattern, is pertinent to this wider debate. Glottal stop-final segholate nouns in Modern Hebrew do not surface with final /ʔ/ in their singular forms, a phenomenon that is problematic for Standard Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky 1993), and raises the question: how do speakers assign the underlying forms of segments that do not surface? Four native speakers participated in an elicitation task in which they were asked to produce a total of twenty novel, glottal stop-final Standard Modern Hebrew words, all of which belonged to grammatical classes that typically require a three-consonant root. Ten of these novel words were verb forms with a transparent derivation, and ten were plural segholate nouns with opaque derivations. The results indicate that while the glottal stop retains its phonemic status, speakers preferred to assume an underlying final /j/ over final /ʔ/ in the verbs. Furthermore, speakers produced a glottal stop more frequently for the novel verb forms than the novel nouns, providing evidence that a two-consonant root may be allowed for Modern Hebrew nouns with an underlying glottal stop.

Keywords: Phonology; Phonological Theory; Modern Hebrew; Semitic Phonology; Abstract Representation; Optimality Theory

1 Introduction

1.1 A History of Modern Hebrew

The language of inquiry for this paper is Standard Modern Hebrew, the variety of Modern Hebrew used by the majority of native speakers. While Ancient Hebrew died out as a native language around the third century BCE, diasporic Jewish communities retained it as a lingua franca and liturgical language for over 1700 years. These diasporic communities developed different oral traditions during this time

period that established ‘grapheme-to-phoneme’ equivalence with distinct pronunciation rules (Blanc 1968). These oral traditions were derived from the Tiberian vocalization system, which emerged between 600-800 AD and likely reflects an older, orally transmitted pronunciation tradition (Bentur 1978). The 19th century Jewish Enlightenment in Europe saw the revival of Hebrew as a mother tongue by predominantly Ashkenazi, Slavic-speaking Jewish linguists. These linguists used the varying oral traditions, comparisons to other Semitic languages, and biblical transliterations with the goal of having each grapheme correspond to a single sound (Bentur 1978).

This attempt to ‘recover what was encoded orthographically’ was disrupted by the fact that the guttural sounds pronounced in the Tiberian vocalization system and the Sephardic and Yemenite oral traditions, namely /q/, /h/, and /ʕ/, were not accessible for Ashkenazi speakers (Bentur 1978). The early speakers of Standard Modern Hebrew (hereafter ‘Modern Hebrew’) were predominantly Ashkenazi; as such, the graphemes that previously represented /q/ and /k/ are generally both realized as [k], and the graphemes for /h/ and /ʕ/ are pronounced as [χ] and [ʔ] respectively (Bentur 1978). The pharyngeal pronunciations are retained by some speakers of Yemenite and Mizrahi origin, who also generally realize the rhotic consonant as an alveolar trill rather than a uvular approximant, often known as the ‘Mizrahi’ and ‘Yemenite’ Modern Hebrew dialects (Asherov & Cohen 2019). While the language family of Modern Hebrew is usually defined as Semitic, other linguistic scholars consider its diverse influences to have formed an Indo-European and Semitic hybrid (Brown et al).

Israeli high schools devote a considerable amount of time to standardizing students’ grammar in writing and speech production, and this prescriptivism is embedded in the fabric of Hebrew-speaking communities. This quote from Matras & Schiff (2005) conveys the depth of such standardization initiatives:

‘[There is] a strong prescriptivist tradition in institutions such as the Hebrew Language Academy, the mainstream public media, the school system and the enormous establishment entrusted with teaching Hebrew as a foreign language. This attitude is also self-imposed by academic circles and Hebrew language departments...with educational measures aimed at safeguarding ‘correct’ pronunciation.’ (147)

The cultural and academic emphasis on grammatical correctness is derived not only from a desire to standardize the national language, but from the aforementioned Tiberian vocalization system and the various diasporic oral traditions that developed from it. Throughout the rabbinic Talmud, there are explicit lessons on how to pronounce certain sound segments in specific contexts (Mizrahi 2016). While not the focus of this paper, the potential impact of exposure to orthography and religious Jewish education on Modern Hebrew phonology will be explored later in Section 4.5.

1.2 Status of the Glottal Stop

The status of the glottal stop /ʔ/ in Modern Hebrew has been the subject of linguistic debate. /ʔ/ also incorporates the previous placement of the pharyngeal fricative /ʕ/, as the pronunciation of the grapheme that traditionally represented /ʕ/, *ayin*, has merged with that of *alef*, the grapheme for the glottal stop. /ʔ/ is never pronounced in codas and rarely elsewhere, which has led to the disintegration of certain minimal pairs such as [ha'raʁ] ‘the rabbit’ and [ʕar'av] ‘Arabia’, now both /ar'av/ (Matras & Schiff 2005). Furthermore, Berman (1997) notes that the usage of glottal stops in onsets, the most common realization, is declining. Because of this phenomenon, Asherov & Cohen (2019) claims that the

occurrences of the glottal stop, which are rare in both cautious and typical speech, can be characterized as instances of insertion in order to rectify syllables without onsets. Similarly, Bentur (1978) attributes existing actualizations of the glottal stop to the influence of orthography and the Tiberian vocalization system, in which the glottal stop was phonemic and fully realized, on the revival of Modern Hebrew. Bentur asserts that given that /ʔ/ is ‘totally absent’ in verbs in informal speech, it is not underlying in verbal paradigms but appears in free variance.

Nonetheless, there is good reason to consider the glottal stop a part of Standard Modern Hebrew speakers’ phonemic inventory. In the *Encyclopedia of Hebrew Language and Linguistics*, Bolozsky observes that the glottal stop is occasionally used to assert distinctions in minimal pairs and in stressed syllables. For example, [am'arti qar'ʔa, 'lo qar'a] “I said ‘she read’, not ‘(she’s) cold’” (Bolozsky 2013). While the glottal stop is also used to reinforce strongly stressed syllables in languages such as English, in which /ʔ/ is not phonemic, the fact that its (optional) realization creates minimal pairs such as [qar'ʔa] ~ [qar'a] is evidence of its status as a phoneme in Modern Hebrew. Bolozsky also cites an experiment by Farrar & Hayon (1980) in which they ascertained that Modern Hebrew speakers posit underlying glottal stops even when they are not present phonetically. They propose that to do this, speakers use other phonetic cues such as length of vocalic nucleus in ʔVC syllables, variations in the pitch and amplitude of said vocalic nucleus, a period of laryngealization, and the length of the consonant before what would have been a glottal stop. Farrar & Hayon propose that these phonetic cues are allophones of a /ʔ/ phoneme (Farrar & Hayon 1980). By the same token, Rabin (1972) proposes that the omission of glottal stops and pharyngeals has led to the formation of two new vowel phonemes depending on whether the first or second vowel is stressed, as well as the insertion of glides [w] and [y] in certain contexts as in /ʃmu'ʕa/ > ʃmu'wa. These phenomena evidence the status of /ʔ/ as a phoneme, as the new vowels and glide insertions can be considered allophones.

1.3 Opaque Segholate Nouns

Modern Hebrew segholates are nouns with penultimate stress and an exceptional vowel pattern, named as such after the Biblical Hebrew vowel diacritic ‘seghol’, which represents /ε/. While most C-final nouns in Biblical Hebrew have final stress, Yeverchayahu & Bat-El (2020) attributes penultimate stress in segholates to the deletion of final vowels during the historical development of Pre-Hebrew into Biblical Hebrew (for example, /'dɪʃna/ ‘fat ashes’ became /'deʃen/).

Hebrew is non-concatenative with templatic morphology; noun and verb classes are composed of three-consonant roots inserted into templates that can be appended by affixes. An un-affixed word consists of three morphemes: the triconsonantal root (base morpheme), the vowel pattern, and the prosodic template (McCarthy 1981). Each noun class, or *mishkal*, has its own, distinct morphology that includes a set of configurations, inflectional paradigms (possessive forms, plural forms, etc.), and sometimes affixes. As such, Yeverchayahu & Bat-El (2020) ascribe the divergent stress patterns of segholate nouns to Co-phonology theory (Orgun 1996), an Optimality Theory analysis in which different classes of words have different constraint rankings.

Segholate nouns in Biblical Hebrew and Modern Hebrew are typically analyzed as having the prosodic template CVCC due to the structure of plurals and possessives in their inflectional paradigms. Morpho-phonological alternations such as [ˈzεrεm ~ zεrεm'im] are the reason this template is postulated, because there is no phonological motivation for the ε ~ ɔ alternation (Yeverchayahu & Bat-El 2020). As such, the plurals are usually analyzed as having the template CVCɔC, and the singular and possessive forms start as CVCC and surface according to the phonotactic constraints of the language.

This analysis breaks down when it comes to segholate nouns with the triconsonantal root C-C-?. The singular forms of these nouns are opaque in Modern Hebrew due to phonological constraints that prohibit certain consonant clusters and delete /ʔ/ at the end of a word. For example, the Modern Hebrew noun [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’ or ‘grass’ is usually analyzed using the following derivation:

UR: /deʃʔ/
Vowel Epenthesis: deʃeʔ
ʔ-Deletion: deʃe
SR: deʃe

This derivation is opaque, as the reason for [e] insertion is not apparent based on the surface form [ˈdeʃe]. Speakers need to somehow posit the intermediate form [deʃeʔ] in order to relate the input and non-faithful output (McCarthy 1999). As with [ˈzɛrɛm], the inflectional paradigm for this noun includes the plural [deʃaˈʔot] ‘lawns’ and possessive [diʃˈʔo] ‘his lawn’, which has led to the traditional analysis of a CVCC underlying representation shown above. It is important to note that the pronunciation of /ʔ/ in the plural and possessive inflectional forms of the segholates is rare and optional; [deʃaˈʔot] ‘lawns’ sometimes surfaces as [deʃaˈot] (Asherov & Cohen 2019). Given that the underlying /ʔ/ never surfaces in the singular form [ˈdeʃe], how do speakers psychologically access the glottal stop to produce the plural and possessive inflections?

There are several different analyses proposed to account for these opaque segholate noun paradigms. Yeverechyahu & Bat-El (2020) assert that the prosodic template for Biblical Hebrew segholate nouns is not CVCC, as previously assumed, but CVCVC, and the CVCʔC plurals and CVCC possessives are just ‘lexically specific configurations’ for plurals and possessives in segholate inflectional paradigms. This means that the input for Modern Hebrew [ˈdeʃe] is actually /deʃeʔ/, leading to a transparent derivation in which the word-final glottal stop is deleted. Sympathy Theory (McCarthy 1999) can also account for this data, proposing that there exists a selector constraint MAX_V that selects for faithfulness violations between the output and a ‘failed’ or ‘sympathetic’ candidate, which in this case is [ˈdeʃeʔ]. The winning candidate [ˈdeʃe] is influenced not only by the input /deʃeʔ/, but by an obligation to remain faithful to the sympathetic candidate [ˈdeʃeʔ], thus realizing the epenthesized vowel [e]. It is also possible that the glottal stop is not underlying in the segholates, but rather a segment inserted as a result of a productive rule to ‘repair[s] onsetless syllables’ in the plural and possessive inflections (Asherov & Cohen 2019).

Finally, as discussed in Section 1.2, the phonemic status of the glottal stop in Modern Hebrew is debatable. The modern realization of the glottal stop in the plural and possessive segholate inflections may not be the result of a productive phonological process; rather, these forms may be a memorized group of lexically specific configurations.

1.4 Guttural-Final Transparent Verb Paradigms

Modern Hebrew verbs with triconsonantal roots are inflected based on gender and number in the present and imperative tense, and additionally inflected for person in past and future forms (Sumner 2003). According to Sumner (2003), these three consonants are always pronounced and written orthographically. However, for verbs with the triconsonantal root C-C-?, the final /ʔ/ is not phonetically realized in all conjugations. For example, the verb /likro/ ‘to read’, has the triconsonantal root k-r-?. The past-tense, third-person, masculine singular form (hereafter ‘3ms’) [karˈa] ‘[he] healed’ forms a minimal pair with the past-tense, third-person, feminine singular form (hereafter ‘3fs’) [karˈʔa] ‘[she]

healed.’ In typical Modern Hebrew verb paradigms, the 3ms form ends with the third root consonant. Modern Hebrew never realizes /ʔ/ in codas; therefore, the final glottal stops in 3ms forms of C-C-ʔ verbs are deleted.

Per Section 1.2, all realizations of [ʔ] are rare and optional in Modern Hebrew, leading to the disintegration of these minimal pairs. However, an experiment by Semiloff-Zelasko (1975) found strong evidence for the phonemic status of glottal stops in these C-C-ʔ verbs; even if the /ʔ/ in 3fs forms is not phonetically present, speakers still use other phonetic cues such as laryngealization and the duration of the medial root consonant to designate a verb form as feminine or masculine. As in Farrar & Hayon (1980), the laryngealization period and shortening of the medial consonant may function as allophones of the underlying glottal stop.

2 Novel Words and Phonological Abstractness

2.1 Productive vs. Idiosyncratic Alternations

The realization of borrowed and novel words by speakers of a language provides insight into speakers’ knowledge of the phonotactics of their language. These new words are typically changed to conform to the speakers’ phonemic inventory, and the ways they are produced can reveal the extent to which a morphophonemic alternation is memorized or stored as a productive, systematic rule (Berko 1958). An alternation is the result of a productive rule if the rule applies wherever the structural description is met.

Bolozsky (2009) cites the phenomenon of Modern Hebrew spirantization, in which underlying stop consonants alternate with fricatives after vowels, as an example of an alternation that is memorized rather than productive. He claims that due to the merging of certain stop phonemes in Modern Hebrew, this process is not productive but rather an idiosyncratic ‘generalization’ made by speakers based on the frequency at which these fricatives appear in specific surface contexts. Bentur (1978) similarly notes that, for example, the underlying /k/ represented orthographically as כ *kaf* alternates with the fricative /x/ represented orthographically as כּ *khaf*, while the underlying /k/ represented by the grapheme ק *qof*, which was once /q/, does not undergo spirantization (Bentur, 25). In other words, spirantization does not apply every time the structural description is met (underlying /k/ following a vowel), but only when the underlying /k/ is represented orthographically as כ *kaf*. As such, Bolozsky proposes that second language learners of Hebrew should not be taught about spirantization as a ‘pseudo-phonetic process’, but as an individually memorized class of exceptions (Bolozsky 2009).

Along the same vein, Semiloff-Zelasko (1975) maintains that the phonemic status of both the glottal stop and the pharyngeal fricative /ʕ/ are retained in Modern Hebrew phonology because different phonological rules are applied to the contexts in which they appear underlyingly. Both Mizrahi Modern Hebrew (see Section 1.1) and Biblical Hebrew apply the historical rule of lowering to non-low vowels before word-final pharyngeal consonants. These distinctions are preserved in surface realizations by speakers of Standard Modern Hebrew: ‘know (ms)’ is [jodea] due to the historical presence of word-final /ʕ/, while ‘read (ms)’ is [kore] due to the word-final /ʔ/. However, Bolozsky (2009) places these distinctions in the same class of idiosyncratic, memorized exceptions as spirantized obstruents. Classifying these phenomena as memorized rather than productive means that one would expect loan or novel words to not exhibit spirantization when obstruents come before vowels, or lowering when non-low vowels occur at the ends of words before neutralized pharyngeals.

2.2 The Example of Dutch Neutralized Voicing

In *Predicting the Unpredictable: Interpreting Neutralized Segments in Dutch*, Mirjam Ernestus and R. Harald Baayen conducted a production task with the goal of understanding how speakers assign underlying representations to segments in neutralizing positions. Just as /ʔ/ is neutralized in the singular forms of Modern Hebrew segholates, the voicing specification for word-final obstruents is nondistinctive in Dutch. Obstruents are voiced in Dutch before voiced stops, and voiceless elsewhere. This leads to the dissolution of minimal pairs when [t] and [d] both appear at the ends of words, as in the following example:

verwijd niet → [verweit nit] ‘widen not’
verwijt niet → [verweit nit] ‘reproach not’

The only way a Dutch speaker would know that [verweit nit] has an underlying /d/ is if they also know the morphologically related form [verveiden]. Ernestus & Baayen (2003) presented Dutch speakers with novel words ending in obstruents that were neutralized for voice in an attempt to understand the strategy with which speakers posit underlying forms for abstract segments. They propose four potential strategies:

- (1) Speakers assume that underlying forms are the same as surface forms. If they hear a voiced obstruent, they interpret its underlying representation to be voiced as well.
- (2) Speakers randomly assign underlying forms; they will choose [+voice] for ½ of the novel underlying forms, and the other ½ will be underlyingly [-voice].
- (3) Speakers decide underlying forms based on whichever phoneme is less marked in the phonology of their language; if the voiced variant has a stronger position in the phonology, speakers will posit a majority of the novel underlying forms to be voiced.
- (4) Speakers decide underlying forms based on the distribution of voiced and voiceless underlying forms among existing, phonologically similar morphemes in the language; they will assign voicing based on the voicing shared by similar words in the lexicon.

Ernestus & Baayen (2003) found Hypothesis (4) to be true for their participants: the percentage of participants that selected voiceless underlying representations was proportional to the percentage of phonologically similar existing words with voiceless-final underlying obstruents. For example, the word [marx] was interpreted as /mary/ by all of the participants, because nearly all word-final velar fricatives in Dutch are underlyingly voiced.

It is important to note that the phenomenon of neutralized, word-final glottal stops in Modern Hebrew may have a different explanation. While all Dutch stops have a voiced and voiceless phoneme, and therefore speakers posit underlying stops for all stop-final words with neutralized voicing, there is a possibility that speakers do not posit underlying final glottal stops in the Hebrew segholates, and that surface realizations of glottal stops in the plural and possessive forms are simply the result of a productive process to provide an onset between two vowels (see Section 1.3).

2.3 Evaluating the Hypotheses of Sumner (2003)

In *A psycholinguistic approach to abstractness: The case of Hebrew*, Meghan Sumner attempts to analyse how speakers conceive of glottal stops in Modern Hebrew opaque segholate singular forms and

transparent 3fs verb forms through proposing three hypotheses. The first is an ‘abstract’ analysis in which all segholate inflections come from the traditional input CVCC, as in /deʃʔ/, and all verb inflections also contain an underlying /ʔ/ as in /karaʔ/. The second, ‘concrete’ analysis states that while all transparent verb inflections contain an underlying /ʔ/, speakers are unable to access an underlying /ʔ/ in the opaque segholate singular forms. This ‘concrete’ explanation posits two separate underlying forms for the singular and possessive/plural forms of segholates; i.e., [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’ is underlyingly /deʃe/, while [diʃˈʔo] ‘his lawn’ is underlyingly /deʃʔ/. Note that in this paper, I will proceed with the assumption that all words in an inflectional paradigm have the same underlying representation.

The third hypothesis proposes that the noun and verb forms in which a glottal stop is surface-realized are not the result of a productive process, and the respective surface representations of these forms are equivalent to their underlying representations (Sumner 2003). This would mean that the underlying form of both [deʃe] ‘lawn’ and [diʃˈʔo] ‘his lawn’ is /deʃe/, and the phonetic realization of /ʔ/ in [diʃˈʔo] is memorized by speakers.

Sumner conducted a phonological priming experiment with an auditory lexical decision task in order to test whether speakers experience phonological priming when noun or verb forms proposed to have an underlying glottal stop (but realized without the glottal stop) precede words with pronounced glottal stops. She tested three subject groups: literate adult speakers, literate teenage speakers of Modern Hebrew, and illiterate adult speakers, and found that while all three experienced some degree of priming, both the teenage literate speakers and the illiterate adult speakers exhibited less priming than the literate adults. This suggests both a potential influence of orthography on speaker’s phonemic inventories and a generational decline in phonetic realizations of the glottal stop.

3 Method: Elicitation Task

3.1 Research Questions

My research attempts to address two main questions: (1) What is the status of the glottal stop in the phonological inventories of Modern Hebrew speakers? (2) How do native speakers of Modern Hebrew interpret the underlying forms of /ʔ/-final segholate nouns? These questions follow from the previous experiments by Sumner (2003) and Ernestus & Baayen (2003) discussed in Section 2.

I conducted an elicitation task with four native speakers of Modern Hebrew. I first constructed ten (10) novel, triconsonantal, /ʔ/-final roots, and converted each into two (2) novel words: one singular segholate noun and one infinitive verb. The segholate noun forms followed the CeCe template of [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’, and the infinitive verb forms followed the CeCaCe template of [lɛraˈpe] ‘to heal’. Four native speakers of Modern Hebrew listened to recordings of five novel singular segholate nouns and five novel infinitive verbs. The recordings were of another native speaker, who produced ten novel singular segholate nouns and ten novel infinitive verbs within novel carrier sentences. These speakers were then provided with further carrier sentences that required them to produce the plural forms for the segholate nouns, and the 3ms and 3fs forms for the verbs in order to fill in a blank space within the sentence. Examples will be provided in Sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.3. Participant responses were all recorded in a small, empty classroom on a laptop using Praat software (Boersma & Weenink 2022) and analyzed for the realization of glottal stops.

All participants were volunteers. While the speaker who produced the experimental stimuli was female, the four participants were all male. This gender difference was not intentional; due to time constraints and difficulty in recruitment, I was only able to control for the age range (18-31 years old).

This was the main and only study I conducted on this topic; however, given the small scale and possibility for further work (see Section 4), this investigation could serve as a pilot study for future experiments.

3.2 Hypotheses

There are three possible hypotheses for this experiment. In this section, I outline each potential outcome and its implications. I predict that one of the following is true:

- (1) The glottal stop retains its status as a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers require a triconsonantal root for both nouns and verbs.
- (2) The glottal stop retains its status as a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers require a triconsonantal root for verbs but not for nouns.
- (3) The glottal stop is not a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers do not require a triconsonantal root for verbs or nouns.

Hypothesis (1) predicts that speakers will produce glottal stops for all/the majority of the 3fs verbs, and all/the majority of the plural segholate nouns. This outcome implies that when speakers hear the singular segholate noun [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’, they posit an underlying final glottal stop. Given that the novel nouns were all phonologically similar to the existing morpheme [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’, and the verb forms were all phonologically similar to the existing morpheme [lɛrɐˈpe] ‘to heal’, this outcome is the most similar to Hypothesis (4) in Ernestus & Baayen (2003), which states that speakers assign underlying forms based on the distributions of phonologically similar words in their mental lexicons.

Hypothesis (2) predicts that speakers will produce glottal stops for all/the majority of the 3fs verbs, but a minority/none of the plural segholate nouns. This outcome implies that when speakers hear the singular segholate noun [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’, they do not assume an underlying final glottal stop. It further suggests that the existing realizations of glottal stops in the plural and possessive segholate forms, such as [deʃaˈʔot] ‘lawns’, are either (a) not the result of a productive rule but rather a memorized group of exceptions, or (b) the result of a productive process to provide syllable onsets (see Section 1.3). The analysis that speakers require a triconsonantal root for verbs but not nouns is supported by Sumner (2002), which states that while borrowed verbs have to adapt into one of the seven templatic verb class patterns (known as *binyanim*), borrowed/new nouns do not necessarily adhere to existing patterns.

Hypothesis (3) predicts that speakers will produce glottal stops for a minority/none of the 3fs verbs and a minority/none of the plural segholate nouns. This outcome implies that when speakers hear the infinitive verb [lɛrɐˈpe] ‘to heal’, they do not assume an underlying final glottal stop. Additionally, as in hypothesis (2), they do not assume an underlying final glottal stop for [ˈdeʃe] ‘lawn’. It further suggests that the existing realizations of glottal stops in 3fs verbs, such as [ripˈʔa] ‘[she] healed’, as well as the existing realizations of glottal stops in the plural and possessive segholates, such as [deʃaˈʔot] ‘lawns’, are either (a) not the result of a productive rule but rather a memorized group of exceptions, or (b) the result of a productive process to provide onsets (see Section 1.3). This is the least likely outcome, as the triconsonantal template is generally accepted as obligatory for Modern Hebrew verbs.

3.3 Procedure

I first constructed ten novel C-C-ʔ roots and turned each into one infinitive verb and one segholate singular noun. Specifically, each triconsonantal root ended in the letter א *alef*, which historically

represented /ʔ/. Each verb had the vocalic pattern CaCe as in [lerape] ‘to heal’, and each noun had the vocalic pattern CeCe as in [deʃe] ‘lawn’ (see Table 1 for novel nouns; Table 2 for novel verbs).

A 22-year-old female, adult, native Modern Hebrew speaker was recorded producing all ten verbs and nouns. For each novel verb, the speaker was recorded saying the sentence ‘I want [infinitive V]’. For each novel noun, the speaker recorded the sentence ‘The [singular N] is green’. The non-participant speaker was also recorded producing the same two constructions with the existing noun [deʃe] and existing verb [lerape], which serve as controls. Participants were asked to produce the plural forms of the segholate nouns, and then the 3ms and 3fs forms of the verbs. Each participant received five novel segholate nouns and five novel verbs so that each novel C-C-ʔ root was tested twice as a noun and twice as a verb. Participant responses were recorded using Praat software.

Table 1: *Novel Nouns in Elicitation Task*

/CeCeʔ/ Uninflected
/ʃetseʔ/
/ʃezeʔ/
/tetseʔ/
/peneʔ/
/ʃekeʔ/
/zeʃeʔ/
/seʃeʔ/
/geteʔ/
/regeʔ/
/ʃegeʔ/

Table 2: *Novel Verbs in Elicitation Task*

/CaCeʔ/ Infinitive	Past, Sg Masc	Past, Sg Fem
/leʃatseʔ/	/ʃitsa/	/ʃitsʔa/
/leʃazeʔ/	/ʃiza/	/ʃizʔa/
/letatseʔ/	/titsa/	/titsʔa/
/lepeneʔ/	/pina/	/pinʔa/
/leʃakeʔ/	/ʃika/	/ʃikʔa/
/lezaʃeʔ/	/ziʃa/	/ziʃʔa/
/lesaʃeʔ/	/siʃa/	/siʃʔa/
/legateʔ/	/gita/	/gitʔa/
/lerageʔ/	/riga/	/rigʔa/
/leʃageʔ/	/ʃiga/	/ʃigʔa/

3.3.1 Participants

There were four participants between 18-31 years old, all men and all native speakers of Modern Hebrew. Two participants had lived their entire lives in Israel, and crucially, went through formal

secondary education in Hebrew in Israeli high schools. The other two participants were both born in Israel and moved to the U.S. before the age of twelve; therefore, they experienced most of their formal education in English in the U.S.

Bentur (1978) attributes the realization of guttural consonants in Modern Hebrew to morphophonemic alternations that are orthographically encoded due to historical changes, but not the result of productive rules. She proposes that C-C-ʔ verbs in Modern Hebrew actually have biradical C-C roots, and the /ʔ/ is inserted in free variance due to the influence of orthography and speakers' exposure to Biblical Hebrew (see Section 1.1). While this was not the focus of my study, I was interested to see if I would observe any differences in the way the participants who attended high school in Israel produced glottal stops in both the nouns and verbs compared to those who went to high school in the U.S. I noted participants' self-reported levels of religious education for this same reason. Participants were asked to self-identify with respect to religious levels, but this measurement typically includes both formal religious schooling and family observance of Judaism. As stated above, this information is not the central focus of my study and thus can be found in Appendix 1.

3.3.2 *Novel Nouns*

Each participant first listened to the speaker produce the sentences 'The lawn is green. The __ are green' in Hebrew. I then asked them to fill in the blank in the second sentence with the plural form for 'lawn'. The segholate, singular noun, [ˈdeʃe] 'lawn', was pronounced in the first sentence. The adjective [jiruˈkim] 'green' in the second sentence was masculine and plural, indicating that the elicited plural form should be masculine and plural. While [ˈdeʃe] is typically pluralized with a feminine suffix, as in [deʃaˈʔot], I requested a masculine plural form because this is the default for Hebrew speakers pronouncing novel nouns without prior knowledge of grammatical gender (Berent et al. 1999). As with the verbs, the plural forms were in medial position in each sentence so that their production would not be isolated, and therefore more informal.

After providing the existing singular form example, which served as a control, I gave two more novel noun examples so that participants would understand how to respond. These two examples were drawn from the five novel noun forms that the participant did not receive. After the examples, I conducted this same elicitation task for five nouns. Table 3 provides a sample elicitation task using the existing control noun:

Table 3: *Sample Noun Elicitation Task*

Novel Noun (Uninflected)	Non-Participant Speaker Recording	Elicited Sentences	Participant Response
(1) [ˈdeʃe] 'Lawn.'	[haˈdeʃe jarok] 'The lawn is green.'	[ha __ jiruˈkim] 'The __ are green.'	[hadeʃaˈʔim jiruˈkim] 'The lawns are green.'

3.3.3 *Novel Verbs*

Each participant first listened to the recorded speaker produce the sentence 'I want [to heal]' in Hebrew'. I then elicited the 3ms and 3fs forms of [leraˈpe] 'to heal' by asking the participant to fill in the blank in the Hebrew sentences: 'Yesterday, he __. Yesterday, she __'. The verbs were placed in the final

position of each sentence so that their production would not be isolated, and therefore more natural and conversational.

Following the existing verb example, I then provided each participant with two example novel verbs so that they would understand how to respond. Just as with the noun task, these were drawn from the five novel verb forms that the participant did not receive. After the two examples, I conducted this same elicitation task for five verbs. Table 4 below provides a sample elicitation task using the existing control verb:

Table 4: *Sample Verb Elicitation Task*

Example Verb (Infinitive)	Non-Participant Speaker Recording	Elicited Sentences	Participant Response
[lera'pe] 'To heal.'	[a'ni ro'tse lera'pe] 'I want to heal.'	[et'mol 'hu __] 'Yesterday, he __.'	[et'mol 'hu ri'pa] 'Yesterday, he healed.'
		[et'mol 'hi __] 'Yesterday, she __.'	[et'mol 'hi rip'ʔa] 'Yesterday, she healed.'

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Defining Glottal Stops

The glottal stop /ʔ/ is produced by closing the vocal folds and entirely obstructing airflow in the glottal tract. Farrar & Hayon (1980) found that other phonetic cues, such as a period of laryngealization or irregular voicing, may also constitute allophonic realizations of glottal stops for Modern Hebrew speakers.

On a waveform, voicing irregularity between vowels is indicated by a sudden decrease in amplitude, while on a spectrogram, this can be seen through an irregular voicing bar and the disappearance of formants. The four participants produced periods of irregularity of varying durations, and I divided these durations arbitrarily into three main categories: irregular periods that lasted between 0 and 0.01 seconds were defined as having no glottalization; irregular periods between 0.01 and 0.05 seconds were defined as glottalization; and irregular periods lasting more than 0.05 were defined as full glottal stops. Figures 1, 2, and 3 respectively, provide examples of each category.

Figure 1: NO GLOTTAL; Participant 1; Noun 4; [pena'im].

Figure 2: GLOTTALIZATION; Participant 2; Noun 6; [zefa'im].

Figure 3: FULL GLOTTAL STOP; Participant 2; Verb 7; [siʔa].

4.2 Noun Results

For the control segholate plural [deʃaʔot] ‘lawns’, two participants produced full glottal stops, and two participants produced a period of glottalization. Therefore, for the control plural form, all participants posited a final, third consonant. This serves as an important point of comparison for the novel plural forms.

There were twenty (20) productions of the ten novel segholate nouns. Of these twenty productions, seven (7) were classified as having no glottalization; eight (8) were classified as producing glottalization; and five (5) were categorized as full glottal stops. In other words, of the twenty possible instances for glottal stops to occur, full glottal stops were only realized 25% of the time. Glottalization was the most common realization at 40%, followed by no glottalization at 35%. These results are shown in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Results for Each Novel Noun

Singular Noun	No Glottal	Glottalization	Full Glottal Stop
[deʃe] (control)		2	2
1. [ʃetse]			2
2. [ʃeze]	1	1	
3. [tetse]	1		1
4. [pene]	1	1	
5. [ʃeke]		1	1

OPAQUE SEGHOLATES REVISITED: THE GLOTTAL STOP IN STANDARD MODERN HEBREW
PHONOLOGY

6. [zeʔe]		2	
7. [seʔe]	2		
8. [gete]	1	1	
9. [rege]	1	1	
10. [ʔege]		1	1

These results also varied slightly depending on the background of each participant. This is purely a numerical observation; statistical tests would not yield results due to the small sample size. Participants 2 and 4, who experienced all of their formal education in Israel, produced either a full glottal stop or a glottalization period for 70% of the novel plural nouns. Participants 3 and 4, who both attended high school (and beyond) in the United States, produced either a full glottal stop or a glottalization period for 60% of the novel 3fs verbs.

Further, the realization of a glottalization period appears to be arbitrary and not based on the preceding consonant. Each novel plural form was elicited from two participants; nouns (1) through (5) were given to Participants 1 and 4, and nouns (6) through (10) were given to Participants 2 and 3. There does not appear to be consistency between the results of Participants 1 and 4, or the results of Participants 2 and 3, which suggests that speakers produced glottal stops at random and not based on phonological context. Table 6 below displays the novel noun results for each participant.

Table 6: *Noun Results by Participant Background*

Singular Noun	Participant 1 U.S. High School Strong religious background	Participant 2 Israeli High School Strong religious background	Participant 3 U.S. High School Less religious background	Participant 4 Israeli High School No religious background
[deʔe] (control)	Full Glottal	Glottalization	Full Glottal	Glottalization
1. [ʔetse]	Full Glottal	—	—	Full Glottal
2. [ʔeze]	None	—	—	Glottalization
3. [tetse]	None	—	—	Full Glottal
4. [pene]	None	—	—	Glottalization
5. [ʔeke]	Full Glottal	—	—	Glottalization
6. [zeʔe]	—	Glottalization	Glottalization	
7. [seʔe]	—	None	None	

8. [gete]	—	None	Glottalization	
9. [rege]	—	None	Glottalization	
10. [ʃege]	—	Glottalization	Full Glottal	

4.3 Verb Results

For the control 3fs verb form [rip'ʔa] ‘[she] healed’, two participants produced full glottal stops, and two participants realized a period of glottalization. Therefore, for the control 3fs form, all participants posited a final, third consonant. This serves as an important point of comparison for the novel plural forms.

All participants assumed a final, third consonant for all of the novel 3fs verbs. Of the twenty (20) productions of novel 3fs verb forms, none were produced without either glottalization or the insertion of another consonant where the glottal stop would have been. One (1) realized a glottalization period, and four (4) produced a full glottal stop. The other fifteen (15) novel forms were produced with the insertion of the consonant [t] where the glottal stop was expected. This means that 0% of the productions had no glottalization or [t] insertion; 5% exhibited glottalization; 20% realized full glottal stops; and 75% showed [t] insertion. The instances of [t] insertion will be analyzed further in Section 4.4.

If we ignore the fifteen (15) instances of [t] insertion, of the five (5) non-insertion cases, four (4) realized a full glottal stop and one (1) resulted in glottalization. This alone is telling: there were no instances of a novel 3fs verb form without three consonants, and a full glottal stop is the preferred realization of an underlying glottal stop (as opposed to glottalization, which was preferred for the nouns). These results are displayed in Table 7 below:

Table 7: Results for Each Novel Verb

Infinitive Verb	No Glottal	Glottalization	Full Glottal Stop	[t] Insertion
[lerape] (control)		2	2	
1. [leʃat̪se]				2
2. [leʃaze]				2
3. [letat̪se]		1		1
4. [lep̪ane]				2
5. [leʃake]			1	1
6. [lezafe]			1	1
7. [lesafe]			1	1
8. [legate]				2

OPAQUE SEGHOLATES REVISITED: THE GLOTTAL STOP IN STANDARD MODERN HEBREW
PHONOLOGY

9. [lerage]			1	1
10. [leʃage]				2

As with the nouns, the results for the U.S.-educated and Israel-educated participants varied. Between the ten (10) total productions by Participants 1 and 3, who were educated in the U.S., one (1) was a full glottal stop and one (1) resulted in glottalization. Between the ten (10) total productions by Participants 2 and 4, who were educated in Israel, three (3) were full glottal stops and one (1) resulted in glottalization. Unsurprisingly, the participants educated in Israel produced more glottal stops in the novel 3fs verb forms. Table 8 below displays the novel verb results for each participant.

Table 8: *Verb Results by Participant Background*

Infinitive Verb	Participant 1 U.S. High School Strong religious background	Participant 2 Israeli High School Strong religious background	Participant 3 U.S. High School Less religious background	Participant 4 Israeli High School No religious background
[lerape] (control)	Full Glottal	Glottalization	Full Glottal	Glottalization
1. [leʃatse]	[t]			[t]
2. [leʃaze]	[t]			[t]
3. [letatse]	[t]		Glottalization	
4. [lepape]	[t]			[t]
5. [leʃake]	Full Glottal			[t]
6. [lezaʃe]		Full Glottal	[t]	
7. [lesafe]		Full Glottal	[t]	
8. [legate]		[t]		[t]
9. [lerage]		Full Glottal	[t]	
10. [leʃage]		[t]	[t]	

4.4 Epenthetic [t]

As stated above, 75% of the twenty (20) total novel verb productions realized the insertion of [t] where the final glottal stop was expected. An example waveform for [t] insertion is shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: [t] Insertion; Participant 2; Verb 8; [gite'ta].

It is important to note that there does not appear to be a specific phonological context (for example, the preceding consonant) that determined when speakers inserted [t]. Different speakers made different assumptions regarding the underlying forms of the same novel verbs. For example, Participant 2 pronounced the 3fs form of novel verb 9 as [rig'ʔa], with a full glottal stop, while Participant 3 pronounced the same 3fs form as [rig'ta], with epenthetic [t]. Novel verbs 3, 5, 6, 7, and 9 each had one speaker choose to insert [t], and one speaker choose to produce glottalization or a full glottal stop. The fact that five (5) out of ten (10) novel verb forms exhibited diverging results with respect to how speakers choose to analyse them indicates that epenthetic [t] is not limited to a specific phonological environment.

The most likely explanation for [t] insertion in the 3fs verbs is that speakers posited an underlying final /j/ instead of final /ʔ/ or a biradical C-C root. There are certain verb templates that insert [-t] in 3fs forms as a part of their inflectional morphology. Weak verbs (verbs with final root consonants that are not surface realized in certain paradigms) with final root consonant 'yod exhibit obligatory [t] insertion in the 3fs form. For example, the verb /lena'kot/ 'to clean' has the triconsonantal root n-k-j. The singular, masculine, past-tense form is [nik'a] '[he] cleaned', while the feminine is [nik'ta] '[she] cleaned' (Sumner 2002).

According to Berman (1981), children natively acquiring Modern Hebrew overapply this [t] insertion to words that are historically root-final /ʕ/, now merged with /ʔ/. For example, the verb for 'to swallow' has the triconsonantal root b-l-ʕ. While the 'correct' 3fs form is [bal'ʔa] '[she] swallowed', children frequently pronounce it as [bal'ta] instead. Berman interprets this non-normative usage as children processing these 'defective' inflections in which the final consonant is elided as still being triconsonantal, and notes that high school Hebrew grammar classes are actively trying to 'eradicate' these common, deviant patterns.

This phenomenon likely explains the instances of [t] insertion produced by the participants. This is in line with my results; Participant 3, who was educated in the U.S. (and whose grandmother is a Hebrew teacher), initially produced the control 3fs form for [lera'pe] 'to heal' as [rip'ta]. While he

changed his response to [rip'ʔa] after some deliberation, this indicates that there is some ambiguity as to whether speakers posit final /ʔ/, even in existing verbs. He later asked whether the verb root for novel verb 9 [lera'ge] ended with an *ayin* before answering. I did not give a response, but he insisted that this knowledge changes whether the novel 3fs form is [rig'ta] (if *ayin*) or [rig'ʔa] (if *alef*).

Speakers assumed final /j/ rather than /ʔ/ when they heard the infinitive novel verbs either because /j/-final verb roots are more common than /ʔ/-final in Hebrew, or because speakers find it easier to pronounce epenthetic [t] than [ʔ] in onsets. Regardless, these results illuminate participants' reluctance to posit a glottal stop as the final consonant in verb forms.

4.5 Hypotheses Revisited

I have slightly revised the predictions made by my three hypotheses to account for the widespread phenomenon of [t] insertion in the novel 3fs verbs. Given that the [t] insertion is likely a result of speakers preferring underlying final /j/ to underlying final /ʔ/ in verb roots (see Section 4.4), these revisions do not change the significance of each potential outcome with respect to speakers' preferences for a triconsonantal root in Modern Hebrew.

- (1) The glottal stop retains its status as a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers require a triconsonantal root for both nouns and verbs.
- (2) The glottal stop retains its status as a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers require a triconsonantal root for verbs but not for nouns.
- (3) The glottal stop is not a full phoneme in Modern Hebrew, and speakers do not require a triconsonantal root for verbs or nouns.

I found hypothesis (2) to be the most true; there is definitely a discrepancy in participants' capacity to deduce underlying final consonants in the /ʔ/-final verbs compared to the /ʔ/-final segholate nouns. The results indicate that while speakers still prefer a three-consonant root for both verbs and nouns, their preference may be significantly weaker for nouns. When speakers do posit underlying final /ʔ/, they prefer to realize it as a glottalization period in nouns and a full glottal stop in verbs. Additionally, speakers appear reluctant to posit final /ʔ/ in the obligatorily triconsonantal verbs, preferring to assume underlying final /j/ instead.

Speakers assumed that 35% of the novel plural nouns did not have a third consonant, compared to none of the novel 3fs verbs. This demonstrates a clear disparity in the strength of speakers' requirement for a triconsonantal root between nouns and verbs, as predicted by hypothesis (2). These results are illustrated in Table 9 below:

Table 9: *Overall Noun and Verb Results*

Outcome	Novel Plural Nouns	Novel 3fs Verbs
Full Glottal Stop or Epenthetic [t]	25%	95%
Glottalization Period	40%	5%
No Glottal Stop or Epenthetic [t]	35%	0%

While a majority of the novel plural nouns were realized with either a full glottal stop or a glottalization period (thus qualifying as a third consonant), 65% is a significantly weaker majority than the 100% outcome for the verbs. Additionally, it is worth noting the discrepancy in how posited underlying glottal stops were surface-realized between the nouns and verbs: 40% of speakers produced a glottalization period instead of a glottal stop in the plural nouns, compared to 5% of the 3fs verbs. As discussed in Section 4.3, of the five (5) verbs that did not exhibit epenthetic [t], four (4) were realized with a full glottal stop rather than glottalization. I have assumed that a glottalization period functions as an allophone of an underlying glottal stop in Hebrew (Farrar & Hayon 1980); however, it is still important to acknowledge this stark contrast.

4.5.1 *Impact of Orthography*

Given that Bentur (1978) asserts that access to orthography has an impact on Modern Hebrew speakers' linguistics knowledge and that /ʔ/-final verbs in Modern Hebrew actually have biradical C-C roots, I wanted to test whether participants who have had more contact with Hebrew orthography and grammatical prescriptivism in the classroom would produce more glottal stops (see Section 1.1). According to Bentur, participants should demonstrate a preference for a triconsonantal root in the novel verb forms, and the participants who attended Israeli high schools should assume underlying glottal stops more often (see Section 1.1).

Israel-educated participants did appear to assume underlying final /ʔ/ more often in both nouns and verbs. While both subject groups always assumed a triconsonantal root in verb forms, the U.S.-educated participants accepted a two-consonant root in nouns 40% of the time, compared to 30% for those educated in Israel. The difference in glottal stop production (10% for both nouns and verbs) is very slim; however, the U.S.-educated participants both still had significant access to Hebrew orthography.

Participant 3 went to high school in the U.S., but his grandmother is a Hebrew language teacher, and Participant 1, who also went to high school in the U.S., frequently reads novels in Hebrew. A more robust experiment dedicated to the specific influence of Israeli high schools' corrective grammatical curricula with respect to glottal stop realization and triconsonantal root preference (see Section 1.1) is needed to test this hypothesis. The results broken down into the two subject groups are shown below in Table 10. Note that 'Glottal' includes glottalization as an allophone of a full glottal stop (see Section 4.5).

Table 10: *Overall Results by Participant Background.*

Outcome	Participants 1 & 3 U.S. High School	Participants 2 & 4 Israeli High school
Novel Plural Nouns	60% Glottal	70% Glottal
Novel 3fs Verbs	20% Glottal	30% Glottal

5 Conclusion

This paper intended to address two research questions: (1) Does the glottal stop have phonemic status in the phonological inventories of Modern Hebrew speakers? (2) How do native Modern Hebrew speakers deduce the underlying forms of /ʔ/-final nouns and verbs? A production task was conducted with four native speakers of Modern Hebrew, who were asked to produce ten (10) novel /ʔ/-final 3fs verbs and ten (10) novel /ʔ/-final singular segholate nouns. The results provide evidence that while the glottal stop retains its phonemic status in Modern Hebrew, speakers prefer to realize underlying final glottal stops as an allophonic glottalization period in nouns, and to assume underlying final /j/ over underlying final glottal stops in verbs. Additionally, although speakers require a triconsonantal root for verbs, they exhibit only a weak preference for a third root consonant in nouns, indicating that this template may not be obligatory for nominals.

The scope of this study was not equipped to investigate the potential impact of Israeli institutions' robust, prescriptivist grammatical curricula and/or the influence of exposure to Biblical Hebrew and a religious educational background; however, results indicate that this is a subject worthy of further research in the future.

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7 Appendix: Participant Background Information

Table 11 below details participant background information with respect to age, gender, age of Hebrew acquisition, place of education, and self-reported religious exposure level. Any potentially relevant additional information is also included.

Table 11: Participant Background Information

Background	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Age	22	31	21	20
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Male
Ages of Acquisition (FL = ‘First	FL: Hebrew; From birth	FL: Hebrew; From birth	FL: Hebrew; From birth	FL: Hebrew; Russian; From birth

Language')	SL: English; Started Age 6	SL: English; Starting 2nd grade	SL: English; Starting 2nd grade	SL: English; Starting 2nd grade
Education	Israel: 1st grade U.S: 2nd grade and above	Israel: All levels of education	Israel: Grades 1-6 U.S.: 7th grade and above	Israel: All levels of education
Religious Background	Strong	Weak	Strong	None
Additional Information	Frequently reads books in Hebrew.	Learned English in school and through English language media.	Doesn't read books in Hebrew; Grandmother is a Hebrew language instructor.	Learned English in school and through English language media.

About the Author

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Relative Clauses in Reading Schemes: How does Children’s Comprehension Align?

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Abstract: This project investigates the extent to which the Oxford Reading Levels Scheme reflects children’s grammatical comprehension with regard to relative clauses. Two key factors are considered: embeddedness and focus. The project adopts two methodologies. Firstly, 40 reading scheme books are analysed, and any relative clauses are coded for embeddedness and focus. This demonstrates that the reading scheme is increasing complexity with level, signified by a higher number of relative clauses, and a greater diversity of them at higher levels. Secondly, an experimental study is conducted with 25 five- and six-year-old participants, in which they are provided with a sentence including a relative clause, and are asked to indicate which of three images matches the sentence. The relative clauses are manipulated according to their embeddedness and focus, to observe if these factors result in differences in comprehension. It is concluded that children comprehend object-embedded, subject focus (OS) relative clauses most easily, followed by subject-embedded, subject focus (SS), object-embedded, object focus (OO) and subject-embedded, object focus (SO). Collectively, these findings indicate that the use of OS and OO relative clauses in the scheme is reflective of children’s comprehension, but further integration of SS and SO clauses may benefit children’s comprehension abilities. This research is significant for children who have limited exposure to reading outside of school, to aid their grammatical development.

Plain English Abstract: This project investigates the extent to which one UK reading scheme reflects children’s grammatical comprehension with regard to four distinct types of relative clause. The project adopts two methodologies. Firstly, all relative clauses were extracted from a sample of 40 reading scheme books. These relative clauses were then coded according to their type. This analysis demonstrates that the reading scheme is increasing in complexity with level, signified by a higher number of relative clauses, and a greater diversity of them at higher levels. Secondly, an experimental study is conducted with 25 five- and six-year-old participants, in which they are provided with a sentence including a relative clause, and are asked to indicate which of three images matches the sentence. They are tested on all four relative clause types, and the data shows that manipulating the clause type alters their understanding of the sentence. When the data from both stages of the project are compared, it suggests that there is a correlation between children’s comprehension and frequency in the books for two of the relative clause types, but not for the remaining two. This research is significant for children who have limited exposure to reading outside of school, to aid their grammatical development.

Keywords: relative clauses; child language development; comprehension; reading schemes

1 Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to determine whether a reading scheme is reflective of children’s comprehension of relative clauses. To achieve this, three research questions are proposed: (1) What is the distribution of relative clauses across the reading scheme? (2) What, if any, are the differences in children’s comprehension of different types of relative clause? (3) Is there a correlation between the reading scheme data and the comprehension data?

Within this study, grammatical comprehension and complexity of the Oxford Owls reading scheme is observed and compared through the lens of relative clauses (RCs). RCs provide information about the noun phrase (NP), such as “that was covered in sprinkles” in “the ice cream, that was covered in sprinkles, began to melt”. They were chosen as the focus of this study as the ability to manipulate RCs

into several forms (Brown, 1971; Sheldon, 1977; de Villiers et al., 1979) provides abundant opportunity for a comparative project such as this one. Although it is thought that children have a basic understanding of RCs by the age of five (Kidd, 2011), they are not explicitly taught until year five, when children are aged nine to ten (National Curriculum, 2013). This may therefore suggest that other linguistic input, such as a reading scheme, plays a part in RC acquisition.

At this stage, it is important to speak to the theoretical assumptions made in this article. The scope of this study is a descriptive comparison of the Oxford Owls scheme and RC comprehension, and does not extend to the critical examination of theoretical standpoints regarding the driving forces of language acquisition/development. Nevertheless, it must be acknowledged that the motivation for the study is grounded in the assumption that environmental factors, namely the exposure to a range of reading materials, play some role in children's language development. Thus, suggestions are made as to how the RCs in scheme could be altered to benefit children's comprehension of them; further investigation would of course be required to cement these.

1.1 Reading Schemes

Learning to read is a primary focus in a child's first years at school. The National Curriculum in England states that reading provides students with an opportunity 'to develop culturally, emotionally, intellectually, socially, [and] spiritually' (2013, p. 13). Across the UK, reading schemes are used to track children's reading progress throughout primary school (Oxford Owls, 2022). Studies have shown that children who spend more time reading outside of school have a higher level of reading proficiency, whereas those who read less receive lower reading scores (Anderson et al., 1988; Greaney, 1980)¹⁴.

Investigations into the adequacy of reading schemes have largely been vocabulary based. For example, studies by Hay and Spencer (1998) and Stuart et al. (2003) found that reading schemes develop from easily identifiable words to those that cannot be sight read. Although this is important, there has been a neglect of similar studies focusing on grammatical structures, which are an equally vital part of language development. The only reference to explicit grammar teaching in the year one English programme of study is through affixes (National Curriculum, 2013). The curriculum also states that children's overall language comprehension skills '[draw] from linguistic knowledge' (2013, p. 14) and can be developed by 'reading and discussing a range of stories' (2013, p. 14). This places further importance on the reading scheme to expose children to various grammatical structures, which it is thought will subsequently benefit their comprehension skills.

Within reading schemes, book bands are used to indicate the level that a child is working at. All schemes must match each of their books to one of these bands. In addition to this, some schemes choose to implement their own levels, to create greater distinction within the bands. One such scheme is Oxford Owls, the scheme used in this project¹⁵. In an email response, the Oxford Owls editorial team from the Oxford University Press (OUP) stated that in advancing to a new level, children will encounter 'incremental changes to test difficulty based on a range of features' (2022). Sentences that include a RC are introduced at Oxford level three, when children are four and five years old (OUP editorial team, 2022). However, it should be noted that at this level, 'multi-clause sentences [...] account for just 4%

¹⁴ It is important to recognise that a child's language environment is not necessarily reflective of their social class, and to acknowledge recent work in the US which challenges the idea that children from working-class families show linguistic deficits (e.g., Johnson, 2015). Nevertheless, reading schemes are accessible to all children in the UK through their school, and must therefore provide a level ground to support and encourage language development regardless of the child's language background.

¹⁵ For a visualisation of the Oxford Reading Levels, please see the following link:
<https://cdn.oxfordowl.co.uk/2019/07/19/13/52/18/160/OxfordLevelsAndBookBands.png>

of the total average' (OUP editorial team, 2022). Moreover, information supplied to authors of scheme books directs them to include 'longer and more complex sentences' (Bickler et al., 2003, p. 97) with each level, so it is likely that more RCs are included in higher level books.

To date, only one study can be found accounting for the frequency of RCs in reading schemes. Jardine (1992) aimed to establish the opportunities provided in reading schemes to gain familiarity with a variety of clause types. Across three schemes, RCs accounted for less than 6% of all clause types. Furthermore, RCs occurring after the verb were twenty-five times more frequent than those occurring before the verb. Jardine concluded that the schemes could be integrating more complex clause types to support children's language development. The present study builds on this by providing a more in-depth examination of relative clauses in a reading scheme, and mapping this to children's RC comprehension.

1.2 Relative Clause Comprehension

Two factors are considered in the literature of children's comprehension of RCs: embeddedness and focus. Embeddedness refers to the position of the RC within the sentence (de Villiers et al., 1979). Sheldon (1977), for example, would call a RC *subject-embedded* if it is embedded in the subject NP, and *object-embedded* if in the object NP, as in (1) and (2):

- (1) Subject-embedded: 'The boy that saw the girl hit the man.' (Sheldon, 1977, p. 306)
 (2) Object-embedded: 'The boy hit the man that saw the girl.' (Sheldon, 1977, p. 306)

However, the literature presents some variation when defining these terms. This is evident in example (3) below (Tavakolian, 1978), which indicates that it may not be as straightforward as *subject-* versus *object-embeddedness*. Here, *object-embedded* is not only used for direct objects, but prepositional objects too:

- (3) Object-embedded: 'The lion stands on the duck that bumps into the pig' (Tavakolian, 1978, p. 49)

Further variation in terminology is found in De Villiers et al.'s (1979) paper, where they refer to subject-embedded RCs as *centre-embedded*, and object-embedded RCs as *right-branching*. The tree diagrams in Figures 1 and 2 demonstrate this¹⁶, for two of de Villiers et al.'s example sentences (1979: 500). In Figure 1, the subject-embedded RC breaks up the main clause, 'the cat chased the rat', therefore appearing central in the sentence structure:

¹⁶ The tree diagrams within this paper were created using TreeForm software (Derrick & Archambault, 2010).

Figure 1: Subject-embedded/centre-embedded relative clause.

Contrarily, the object-embedded RC in Figure 2 follows the main clause, ‘the cat bit the dog’, and branches to the right:

Figure 2: Object-embedded/right-branching relative clause.

These diagrams also suggest that an important distinction between subject- and object-embedded RCs is the depth at which the RC is embedded. The object-embedded clause in Figure 2 is embedded deeper in the sentence structure than the subject-embedded clause in Figure 1. This is visualised by it being further down the branches of the tree. Since English has subject-verb-object word order, subject-embedded RCs generally come before the verb, and object-embedded ones follow. Therefore, those preceding the verb, and consequently interrupting the main clause, can be termed *subject-embedded*; those following are *object-embedded*. Because of this link, and the fact that the majority of literature adopts this terminology, it is also used throughout this paper.

A large proportion of the literature provides evidence suggesting that children initially find object-embedded RCs easier to comprehend. Menyuk (1971, p. 139) concluded that ‘operations which disturb the order of SV or SVO appear to be later acquisitions than those which do not’, telling us that subject-embedded RCs, those that interrupt the main clause such as the example in Figure 1, may be more challenging for children. Supporting evidence comes from Gaer’s (1969) experimental study, in which children aged three to six were shown an image and asked if a given sentence matched correctly. The results showed that children, on average across the ages, understood 66% of object-embedded RCs, in contrast to 61% of subject-embedded RCs. This difference was significant in children aged four, five,

and six. Gaer thus concluded that children find object-embedded RCs easier to comprehend than their subject-embedded counterparts.

In contrast, Lahey's (1974) study found that object-embedded RCs were more difficult for five-year-old children to understand. This study pioneered a new methodology in the study of RC comprehension, the act-out procedure, where children were given a set of toys and asked to act out sentences. This may produce more reliable results than a picture-cued comprehension task, as there are 'no constraints on a child's interpretation' (de Villiers et al., 1979, p. 501). The main focus of this study, however, was on prosody, not embeddedness, so the differing findings may be resulting from less control over extraneous variables. De Villiers et al. (1979) also suggest the conflicting research may be due to studies failing to account for focus alongside embeddedness.

The second factor, *focus*, can be defined as 'the role that the head noun plays in the relative clause' (de Villiers et al., 1979, p. 500)¹⁷. The literature centres on two categories: subject focus and object focus. To determine the focus of a RC, we can look at which element is missing from it. Consider example (4):

(4) The girl that cuddled the cat loved linguistics.

The RC in this sentence, 'that cuddled the cat', is missing a subject. It can therefore be said that the 'relativised [noun phrase] is a subject' (Sheldon, 1977, p. 306) and the RC has subject focus. In (5), below, 'that the cat cuddled' is missing an object; we do not know what the cat cuddled. This RC has object focus.

(5) The girl that the cat cuddled loved linguistics.

A notable study on the effect of focus on RC comprehension was conducted by Brown (1971). Children aged three to five were asked to indicate which of two pictorial stimuli matched a sentence. Although embeddedness was also investigated, focus was the only syntactic variable producing a significant effect. The children produced more correct answers for subject focus RCs than object focus, regardless of the embeddedness of the clause.

The typological model of the Accessibility Hierarchy (Keenan & Comrie 1977) can be linked to the focus of RCs¹⁸. As previously demonstrated, NPs of various types can be relativised, or *focused*. Between languages, there are differences as to which NP positions can be focused. For example, as Song (2002, p. 732) states, 'there are no languages in their sample that cannot relativize on subject although there are languages which can relativize only on subject'. The hierarchy is as follows (where > indicates 'more accessible than'):

Subject > Direct Object > Indirect Object > Oblique > Genitive > Object of
Comparison
(Keenan & Comrie, 1977, p. 66)

¹⁷ It is acknowledged that in recent literature this distinction is known as type of extraction: *subject-extracted* and *object-extracted*. However, *focus* is used in this paper to align with the previous relevant studies.

¹⁸ Other explanations have been proposed. Lau and Tanaka (2021) provide a good summary.

A language that can place focus on a certain NP position is expected to do the same for all preceding positions in the hierarchy. For instance, if a genitive (possessor) can be focused, it is assumed that subjects, direct objects, indirect objects, and obliques can be too.

Whilst this may not immediately elicit connections to child comprehension, there is a growing body of research examining the link between typological models and first language acquisition (Song, 2002; Slobin & Bowerman, 2007)¹⁹. Some studies have suggested that the Accessibility Hierarchy is reflected in the order of which children acquire RCs (De Villiers et al., 1979; Romaine, 1984). Whilst comprehension projects have not explored all NP positions, the hierarchy gives a basis to Brown’s findings that RCs with subject focus were more easily comprehended than those with object focus.

There is an increasing body of research accounting for both features simultaneously. This research discusses four RC types: subject-embedded, subject focus (SS); subject-embedded, object focus (SO); object-embedded, subject focus (OS); and object-embedded, object focus (OO). Table 1 provides an example for each of these types:

Table 1: *Examples of SS, SO, OS and OO relative clauses (de Villiers et al., 1979, p. 500).*

SS	The cat <u>that bit the dog</u> chased the rat.
SO	The cat <u>that the dog bit</u> chased the rat.
OS	The cat bit the dog <u>that chased the rat</u> .
OO	The cat bit the dog <u>that the rat chased</u> .

Research controlling both features has resulted in several conflicting conclusions. Table 2 shows the different difficulty rankings attested in six studies:

Table 2: *Relative clause difficulty rankings concluded from different studies (where > means easier than, and = means equal to).*

Order of difficulty (left=easiest):	Evidenced in:
OS > SS > OO > SO	Smith, 1974.
SS > OS > SO > OO	Tavakolian, 1978.
OO > OS > SO > SS	Romaine, 1984.
OS = SS > OO > SO	De Villiers et al., 1979.
SS > OS > OO > SO	Brown, 1971.
SS > OO > OS > SO	Sheldon, 1977.

There is not one RC type that has consistently been found to be easiest for children to comprehend. However, in four out of six of these studies, the subject focus RCs made up both of the two easiest types. Additionally, only one of the studies found the most difficult type to have subject focus. Regarding embeddedness, the SS type was found easiest in half of the investigations. Despite this, the most difficult RC type in the majority of studies was SO, the other subject-embedded clause. Collectively, this suggests focus may be of more importance than embeddedness in children’s RC

¹⁹ The strongest version of the Accessibility Hierarchy would somewhat counter claims that additional reading input would benefit children’s comprehension. However, these two ideas are not completely incompatible; many factors may be involved.

comprehension. Considering the results from the individual study of each feature, it appears that OS RCs are likely to be the easiest for children to comprehend. The wide range of results may arise from the studies adopting different methodologies, and working with children of different ages and socio-economic backgrounds.

Another direction of research determines whether children's comprehension of RCs is influenced by the inclusion or omission of a relative pronoun. In English, the relative pronouns are *who*, *whom*, *whose*, *which*, and *that* (Aarts, 2014). In RCs with object focus, the relative pronoun is not essential (Trask, 2000), as demonstrated in (6).

- (6) (a) The flowers that the woman grew were pink.
 (b) The flowers the woman grew were pink.

Alternatively, subject focus RCs must include the relative pronoun, as in (7), except in examples such as (8) that contain an auxiliary; in these cases the sentence is still grammatically correct when the pronoun and auxiliary are omitted (Trask, 2000).

- (7) (a) The woman that grew the flowers was happy.
 (b) *The woman grew the flowers was happy.
 (8) (a) The woman that is growing the flowers is happy.
 (b) The woman growing the flowers is happy.

Beaumont's (1982) study investigated the comprehension of RCs in seven-year-olds, based on the inclusion or omission of the pronoun. It was concluded that the inclusion of the pronoun was beneficial in the comprehension of object focus RCs; children understood an average of 1.53 out of 2 object focus RCs including the pronoun, which reduced to 0.79 when the pronoun was removed. However, this effect was not observed in the subject focus RCs. Straying from comprehension, a case study by Slobin and Welsh (1973) discovered that their two-year-old subject found it more difficult to repeat RCs that did not include a relative pronoun than those that did.

1.3 Hypotheses

Considering the background on reading schemes, and the previous literature on comprehension, the research questions can be addressed by a number of hypotheses. Although the main focus of the study is the four RC types, questions regarding relative pronouns are also included, which will contribute to answering the overarching research question of whether the reading scheme is reflective of children's RC comprehension.

RQ1: What is the distribution of relative clauses across the reading scheme?

Hypothesis (1): The reading scheme will increase in relative clause complexity with level.

(1a): There will be an overall increase in number of relative clauses.

(1b): There will be greater diversity of relative clauses at higher levels, in terms of the four types, and the use of relative pronouns.

RQ2: What, if any, are the differences in children's comprehension of different types of relative clause?

Hypothesis (2): The hypothesised hierarchy from easiest to comprehend to most difficult is OS > OO = SS > SO.

(2a): Children will show higher levels of comprehension when tested on object-embedded relative clauses (OS and OO) than subject-embedded relative clause (SS and SO).

(2b): Children will show higher levels of comprehension for relative clauses with subject focus (OS and SS) than object focus (OO and SO).

Hypothesis (3): Children will show lower levels of comprehension for relative clauses omitting the relative pronoun.

RQ3: Is there a correlation between the reading scheme data and the comprehension data?

Hypothesis (4): The use of relative clauses in the reading scheme will reflect children's comprehension levels. This means there will be more of the relative clauses they have good comprehension of, and less of those that they do not comprehend as easily.

2 Reading Scheme Analysis

An in-depth book analysis was conducted to propose an answer to research question (1). This section covers the methodology adopted, and the analysis and discussion of subsequent data.

2.1 Methodology

2.1.1 Materials

This step involved the analysis of 40 books from the Oxford Reading Levels. The sample includes five books each from levels five to twelve, which covers years one to three and thus children aged five to eight. Although this goes beyond the age of the experimental age group (five to six (§3.1.2)), I continued the analysis to level twelve to identify patterns in the emergence of RC types; only analysing the two levels for year one children would not provide opportunity to determine if the scheme was increasing in complexity. Analysing eight levels was the reason why only five books were sampled from each. The data collection process was done manually, so this ensured an accurate sample, whilst remaining realistic about time restraints.

The majority of books were sourced from two locations: a local primary school, and The University of Sussex's Education Department. Six additional books were randomly purchased. Whilst the sample took advantage of easily accessible books, it works well: all the books are matched to an Oxford Reading Level and, to my knowledge, are all currently used in schools. A full list of the books can be found in Appendix one. A preliminary analysis was conducted on five books at level four, which involved reading the books and noting any RCs. As none were found, these books are not included in the final sample.

2.1.2 Procedure

The data collection process began with the counting of all RCs in the 40-book sample. The number of NPs in each book was also counted. This includes proper and common nouns, alongside pronouns such

as *one* and *everything*. Personal pronouns and demonstrative pronouns were not included in this count, as they were not thought to contain RCs in this register of children’s literature. This was confirmed through a check of all recorded RCs.

Next, it was noted if each RC contained a relative pronoun. Each RC was then manually coded according to its embeddedness and focus features. The number and proportion of each RC type was determined for each level. The coding system was inspired by the previous literature on children’s comprehension of RCs, to ensure the results could be compared with the following experimental activity (§3), as summarised in Table 3:

Table 3: *Book analysis coding system.*

	Embeddedness	Focus
Subject	The RC is embedded in the subject (and precedes the verb).	The RC relativises a subject.
Object	The RC is embedded in the direct object or prepositional object (and follows the verb).	The RC relativises a direct object or prepositional object.

This system produces the four RC types: subject-embedded, subject focus (SS), subject-embedded, object focus (SO), object-embedded, subject focus (OS), and object-embedded, object focus (OO). Initially, all RCs that followed the verb were to be classified as object-embedded, thus including those embedded in grammatical constituents other than the direct or prepositional object²⁰. To maintain consistency between features, the object focus category also included the alternative constituents. However, initial analyses suggested that these categories were too large, and thus the methodology was adapted to ensure accurate analysis. Since the object categories in the comprehension study (upcoming in §3) were limited to direct and prepositional objects only, it was decided that the book analysis would also adopt this system. Because of this, 54% of the 159 recorded RCs could not be classified into one of the four categories. As analysis was also conducted on embeddedness and focus independently, there are differing total values for the two features: 81 (51%) RCs could be analysed for embeddedness, and 143 (90%) for focus. Whilst this reduces the data sample significantly, it is important to ensure an accurate and direct comparison can be drawn between the two stages of the study. There is certainly scope for further study to address RCs embedded in/relativised by the additional constituents. Throughout the analysis and discussion, where *other* is mentioned, this refers to RCs that did not meet the criteria for *subject* and/or *object* in terms of embeddedness and/or focus. For instance, RCs that were object embedded, but had ‘other’ focus, were not included. RCs that were not embedded in a sentence were also marked as ‘other’ for embeddedness. Additionally, 21 RCs were not embedded in a sentence, such as (9):

(9) ‘Someone who didn’t wipe their feet!’ (Level 8: Hunt, 1990. *The Flying Carpet*)

Such cases could therefore not be categorised into one of the four SO, SS, OS or OO types, and also not analysis for embeddedness. They are, however, still included in the analysis of focus.

²⁰ This included subject predicative complements, existential sentences, pseudo-clefts, and adverbials.

Examples of the four RC types, taken from the books, are given in (10)-(13):

- (10) SS: 'Though anybody who wants to listen to horrid animal noises must be mad' (Level 11: Coldwell, 2010. *Amy the Hedgehog Girl*).
- (11) SO: 'The vase you're throwing balls at is worth seven hundred pounds!' (Level 7: Hunt, 1988. *The Old Vase*).
- (12) OS: 'He even loved doughnuts that had nothing special about them at all' (Level 10: Murtagh, 2017. *Dragon Doughnuts*).
- (13) OO: 'They finally found the bit they were looking for' (Level 10: Bradman, 2010. *Cuckoo Trouble*).

2.1.3 Data analysis

The first stage of analysis was to calculate the percentage of NPs containing a RC, for each book and then for each level, and the scheme overall. Both mean and median rates were observed. The mean was initially beneficial to identify any trends in the data, but the variability within levels meant further analysis was necessary. For example, within the level five books, four contained no RCs, and one contained four. Due to the small sample size, it wouldn't be justified to class this as an outlier, but calculating a median ensured the data was represented accurately.

To prepare the data for quantitative analysis, the number of each RC type was counted for the entire sample, and each level. As some of the analysis required a relative measure, a percentage was calculated to show the proportion of all RCs made up by each type; further percentages were then calculated for each level of the reading scheme. Embeddedness and focus were also considered separately, so equivalent calculations were made of subject- and object-embedded RCs, and then subject and object focus RCs. Finally, the number of RCs containing, and omitting, the relative pronoun, were counted, and relative percentages were calculated.

2.2 Analysis and Discussion

In the 40 books analysed, 8,186 NPs were recorded, 159 of which contained a RC. Across levels, this meant the average percentage of NPs including a RC was 2%. As Figure 3 shows, however, the higher-level books contain higher numbers of RCs than lower levels.

Figure 3: *The mean and median percentage of noun phrases containing a relative clause at Oxford Reading Levels 5–12, with range bars showing the ranges.*

Whilst the error bars display considerable variation within each level, there remains a strong positive correlation between reading level and percentage of NPs including a RC. A Spearman’s Rho Correlation shows this to be a statistically significant²¹ finding: for the mean, $r_s=0.833$, $p=0.010$; for the median, $r_s=0.976$, $p<0.001$.

²¹ All statistical tests were conducted using SPSS.

2.2.1 *Relative Clause Types*

Figure 4 shows the frequency of each of the four RCs types across levels:

Figure 4: *The distribution of SS, SO, OS, and OO relative clauses across Oxford Levels 5–12.*

The higher levels demonstrate a greater variety of RCs, however only levels ten and eleven have examples of all four types. Object-embedded RCs, OS and OO, appear first, and remain predominant in all levels except seven. The subject-embedded RCs, SO and SS, are introduced at levels seven and nine respectively, but neither are consistently common across levels. Since some levels have very few RCs (levels six, seven, and eight have only two each), it is therefore useful to also examine the distribution of types across the levels as a whole. This data is shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: *The distribution of SS, SO, OS, and OO relative clauses within Oxford Levels 5–12 (N= 73).*

RCs coded as OS were most common across the levels, followed by OO, SS, and finally SO. Object-embedded RCs make up a majority of 81%. There also appears to be a preference for subject focus RCs; 55% of RCs have this feature.

Observing embeddedness and focus individually may further support these patterns. Object-embedded RCs are more common at all levels, except level seven in which there is an equal number of subject-embedded RCs (Figure 6). This trend is most prevalent in level twelve, where there are over six times as many object-embedded RCs as subject-embedded RCs.

Figure 6: *The number of subject- and object-embedded relative clauses across Oxford Levels 5–12.*

Overall, object-embedded RCs accounted for 80% of all recorded RCs, with subject-embedded RCs accounting for the remaining 20%. This finding is proved statistically significant with a Spearman’s Rho Correlation ($r_s=0.696, p=0.003$).

In relation to focus, the data is not as clear. Levels six, seven, eight, and twelve have a higher number of object focus RCs, whereas levels five, nine, ten and eleven have a more subject focus RCs, as pictured in Figure 7:

Figure 7: The number of subject and object focus relative clauses across Oxford Levels 5–12.

Insight into the distribution of the two focus types for all levels collectively is therefore necessary to determine which is more frequent. The data shows that subject focus accounts for more RCs (59%) than object focus (41%), by 18%, although this is not statistically significant (Spearman’s Rho Correlation, $r_s=0.041, p=0.880$).

Following the analysis of features both collectively and individually, it can be concluded that object-embedded, subject focus RCs, OS, are most frequent in the books, and SO is the least. This supports the first hypothesis, ‘the reading scheme will increase in relative clause complexity with level’, as there is a general increase in the number of RCs with level, and more RC types are included at higher levels.

2.2.2 Relative Pronouns

The analysis of relative pronouns begins with the SO and OO RCs, as these are the categories in which the pronoun is consistently optional. This reveals that there is an overwhelming tendency to omit the relative pronoun. In 100% of the SO clauses, no relative pronoun was recorded. In the OO RCs, only 14% of them included a relative pronoun. As the SO and OO types were less frequent in the books, a

further calculation was made including the SS and SO clauses, to put the results into perspective. In the RCs that fit into the four specific categories, there were nearly twice as many RCs including a relative pronoun (66%) than omitting it (34%).

To address if RCs omitting the relative pronoun become more frequent at higher levels, Figure 8 was created. This shows the percentage of all RCs at each level including and omitting the relative pronoun.

Figure 8: *The percentage of relative clauses at Oxford Levels 5–12 including and omitting the relative clause.*

Although the majority of levels contain more RCs including the pronoun, there is not a pattern regarding the emergence of those omitting the pronoun; it appears quite coincidental. This provides an uncertain answer to hypothesis (1b), that higher levels will integrate more diversity relating to the use of pronouns. However, these figures work with a very small sample size, and so further research with a larger sample would be necessary to provide a more accurate representation.

3 Comprehension Experimental Study

To address research question (2), an activity was conducted with 25 five- and six-year-olds to determine their comprehension of the different RC types.

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Materials

The first step in the activity design was to generate the sentences. These were based on the same definitions as used in previous literature, with RCs embedded in the subject being labelled *subject-embedded*, and those in the object, *object-embedded*. A similar distinction was made between *subject* and *object* focus. To remain consistent with previous studies (Tavakolian, 1978), the *object* categories also included prepositional objects, giving the sentences more diversity and making them more engaging for the children. Eight sets of sentences were created. Each set consisted of one control sentence, containing no RC, and one sentence containing each of the RC types. For the SO and OO types, a no pronoun option was also included. Each set of sentences contained the same nouns and the same verbs. Animals, such as *sheep*, *dogs* and *cats* were chosen as the nouns for all sentence sets as they are easily recognisable for the children. Likewise, the chosen actions, including *jumping*, *standing*, and *barking*, could be clearly illustrated, to reduce ambiguity.

Whilst Lahey's (1974) act-out procedure is thought to be 'methodologically the most sound' (de Villiers et al., 1979: 503), this required adaptation due to ethical complications associated with the recording of children. Without such recordings, the results would lack physical evidence. Thus, a picture-cued comprehension task, inspired by Brown (1971) and Gaer (1969) was developed. Three options were given instead of two, to counter Gaer's (1969) limitation of children having a 50/50 chance of being correct each time, which could skew results.

Each test sheet consisted of the three images displayed below a written sentence, as in Figure 9:

Figure 9: Example comprehension test sheet.

For each test sentence, one image included an animal not mentioned, one was the correct answer, and one showed a slight alteration depending on the RC type. For example, in Figure 9, the difference between the second and third images is which animal is wearing the hat.

From the previously created eight sentence sets, four groups of materials were formed. Each consisted of ten sentences: two controls, and two of each of the RC types. The material groups contained

a range of nouns and verbs to ensure that one particular stimuli, or set of nouns/verbs, was not producing a certain effect. In the SO and OO conditions, one sentence of each type included the relative pronoun, and one omitted it; this is the reason behind having two subsets, as the sentence including the pronoun alternated. An example group of stimuli sentences is given in Table 4:

Table 4: *Example group of materials.*

	Set 1a	Set 1b
SS	The cow that jumped over the cat stood on the table.	The cow that jumped over the cat stood on the table.
	The dog that barked at the sheep wore the hat.	The dog that barked at the sheep wore the hat.
SO	The horse that the goat sat on ate the grass.	The horse the goat sat on ate the grass.
	The pig the mouse sprayed rolled in the mud.	The pig that the mouse sprayed rolled in the mud.
OS	The rabbit sang to the chicken that flapped over the cat.	The rabbit sang to the chicken that flapped over the cat.
	The donkey jumped over the dog that wore the scarf.	The donkey jumped over the dog that wore the scarf.
OO	The frog taught the cake that the fish baked.	The frog taught the cake the fish baked.
	The snake hissed at the tower the fox built.	The snake hissed at the tower that the fox built.
Control	The cat jumped over the cow.	The cat jumped over the cow.
	The dog barked at the sheep.	The dog barked at the sheep.

3.1.2 *Participants*

A small pilot was conducted to confirm that the methodology was appropriate, and to determine if any changes needed to be made before beginning the main study. The participants were five L1 English-speaking children, aged five to seven, living locally. The participants in the main study were 25 five- and six-year-olds: twelve girls and thirteen boys. This age was chosen to ensure the children were independent readers, but still developing their grammatical knowledge. All participants were L1 English speaking pupils of a Year One class of a primary school in a working-class area of Devon. Please note this data collection process abided by the ethical policy of the University of Sussex and was fully approved by the ethics board. Prior to beginning the activity, I explained the process to each child and made sure they were aware they did not have to complete the task, and that it was not a test.

3.1.3 *Procedure*

After a brief acquainting period, the activity began. Each sentence was read aloud, and the child was asked to indicate which picture matched, by ticking the corresponding box. If the correct box was ticked, it was taken that the child comprehended the sentence. It is acknowledged that the sentences were both

written and read aloud, meaning conclusions cannot be drawn specific to reading or listening comprehension. Initially the sentences were to be read aloud; the children would not have the sentence written in front of them. However, when I conducted the experiment (Spring 2022), Covid-19 remained a concern, and so I wore a mask and sat at a distance from the children to minimise risk to both me and the children²². Alongside classroom noise, this raised doubt on whether the children would be able to hear me. Thus, it was decided for both written and oral stimuli to be included.

After completing the activity with the first pilot participant, a small change was made. Two additional test stimuli were added to the beginning of the study, to act as a buffer, ensuring the children understood the task. The data from these was not recorded for analysis. The pilot confirmed that this activity was appropriate for five- and six-year-old children. The data of three pilot participants who were this age (and were not the first pilot participant) was included in the overall data sample. Following the pilot, there were no additional changes made to the experimental paradigm, the children were not tested twice, and no data analysis was conducted on the pilot data alone. The remaining pilot participants were seven years old, and so their data was not included.

Children in the main study were individually called out to a table just outside the classroom to complete the tasks, throughout the afternoon of a normal school day. The process took five minutes per child, meaning their learning was minimally disrupted.

3.1.4 Data analysis

Prior to analysis, all data was input onto a spreadsheet. The number of correct responses to each sentence type were recorded for each child. The data of any participants who got one, or both, of the control sentences wrong, was discarded, as it could not be confirmed that they fully understood the task. This meant that data from seven participants was not analysed. For the remaining children, a mean average was generated for the number of correct responses to each RC type, including the no pronoun conditions. Additional calculations were made to determine the percentage of participants getting each number of RC types correct. For example, the raw data was input into the following formula to determine what percentage of participants answered correctly to all four subject-embedded RCs.

$$\frac{\text{Number of participants getting all subject – embedded RCs correct}}{\text{Total number of participants}} \times 100$$

Similar calculations were made for the number of participants getting three, two, one, and zero answers correct, and this was repeated for all RC types.

3.2 Analysis and Discussion

Overall, children correctly understood an average of 1.46 out of two RCs per type ($SD = 0.65$), demonstrating that by the age of five or six, they have a good comprehension of these clauses.

²² I also only went into the school after confirming I was Covid-negative.

3.2.1 *Embeddedness*

Table 5 shows the distribution of answers for subject- and object-embedded RCs. For example, 5% of participants correctly responded to only one of the subject-embedded RCs, meaning they incorrectly responded to the remaining three.

Table 5: *Percentage of participants who gave each number of correct responses, comparing subject- and object-embedded relative clauses (N= 21).*

Embeddedness type	Number of correct responses (percentage of participants)				
	0	1	2	3	4
Subject	5%	5%	38%	24%	29%
Object	0%	5%	14%	38%	43%

Notably, 43% of participants correctly comprehended all four of the object-embedded RCs, in contrast to only 29% correctly responding to all of the subject-embedded RCs. Furthermore, only 19% of children got fewer than three object-embedded RCs correct, as opposed to 48% for subject-embedded. These percentages suggest that children found object-embedded RCs easier to comprehend than subject-embedded RCs. This is supported by the data in Figure 10, which shows the average number of correct answers for each embeddedness type.

Figure 10: *The average number of correct responses for subject- and object-embedded relative clauses (max. 2), with standard error bars (subject-embedded = 1.222–1.444; object-embedded = 1.511–1.679).*

Children’s scores for object-embedded RCs ($M=1.595$, $SD=0.544$) were 0.27 higher than subject-embedded ($M=1.333$, $SD=0.721$) RCs. An independent t-test does not show this as statistically

significant ($t(82)=-1.879, p=0.064$), and therefore cannot provide support for hypothesis (2a) 'Children will show higher levels of comprehension when tested on object-embedded relative clauses (OS and OO) than subject-embedded relative clauses (SS and SO)'. Nevertheless, the finding is suggestive of a difference in understanding in line with this hypothesis. A potential explanation for this stems from Menyuk's (1971) observation (§1.2) that clauses which disrupt the SVO word order are acquired later than clauses that don't. The Anti-Interruption Hypothesis (Slobin, 1971) argues that this disruption is what makes subject-embedded clauses harder for children to comprehend.

3.2.2 Focus

Almost half of the children got all four subject focus RCs correct, as Table 6 shows. For object focus, only 14% answered all questions correctly.

Table 6: Percentage of participants who gave each number correct responses, comparing subject and object focus relative clauses ($N= 21$).

Focus type	Number of correct responses (percentage of participants)				
	0	1	2	3	4
Subject	0%	0%	14%	38%	48%
Object	0%	14%	33%	38%	14%

Furthermore, 47% of participants got fewer than three object focus RCs correct, compared to 14% for subject focus RCs. This implies that subject focus was easier for the children to comprehend, which is supported by the data displayed in Figure 11:

Figure 11: The average number of correct responses for subject and object focus relative clauses (max. 2), with with standard error bars (subject focus = 1.586–1.748; object focus = 1.154–1.370)

The number of correct responses was 0.4 higher for subject focus ($M=1.667$, $SD=0.526$) compared to object focus ($M=1.262$, $SD=0.701$). An independent t-test shows this as significant ($t(82)=$, $p=0.004$).

This conclusion is in line with the Accessibility Hierarchy (Keenan & Comrie, 1977), and Brown’s (1971) finding that subject focus RCs were easier for children to comprehend (§1.2). The findings thus support hypothesis (2b), ‘children will show higher levels of comprehension for relative clauses with subject focus (OS and SS) than object focus (OO and SO)’. Collectively, these results support a proposition by Slobin (1971), which suggests that subject focus RCs are easiest to comprehend because the underlying word order stays constant, unlike in object focus RCs.

3.2.3 Combined Relative Clause Types

Considering the features together, the OS type elicited the highest average number of correct responses, as displayed in Figure 12:

Figure 12: The average number of correct responses for the four relative clause types (max. 2), with standard error bars (SS = 1.490–1.748; SO = 0.887–1.209; OS = 1.613–1.815; OO = 1.345–1.607)

The OS type is closely followed by SS, then OO, and finally SO. The two subject RCs have the highest comprehension levels, suggesting that focus may be of more importance in RC comprehension than embeddedness. An ANOVA shows the differences in number of correct responses between RC types to be significant ($F=4.951$, $p=0.003$). A post-hoc Tukey analysis revealed that the significant differences were between SS and SO ($p=0.016$), and SO and OS ($p=0.003$). The SO RC therefore produced significantly lower correct responses than SS and OS, but not OO. Additionally, the correct responses were significantly higher for subject focus than object focus ($F=8.970$, $p=0.004$), but the embeddedness distinction was not statistically different ($F=3.531$, $p=0.064$). These findings provide further evidence for focus having a superior effect to embeddedness.

The hypothesised hierarchy of the RC types children would find easiest to comprehend is compared to the experimental findings in Table 7:

Table 7: *Hypothesised and concluded hierarchy of ease.*

Hypothesised hierarchy:	OS > OO = SS > SO
Concluded hierarchy:	OS > SS > OO > SO

Children’s comprehension matched most of the hypothesised hierarchy. The only difference is a specification between OO and SS; the latter is shown to be easier. The suggested explanation of focus being more important in comprehension than embeddedness would fit this conclusion. Additionally, whilst no significant difference was identified between OO and SO, the conclusion that OO is easier to comprehend than SO is drawn from the raw data, in addition to the previous findings of object focus being easier comprehend than subject focus.

3.2.4 *Relative Pronouns*

The final variable to consider is the role of the relative pronoun. The SO and OO categories were first compared collectively, as the SS and OS sentences did not have a ‘no pronoun’ condition. The results of this show that there is an increase in comprehension of 0.02 for the no pronoun condition (0.64) in comparison to the pronoun condition (0.62). However, this is not a large enough difference to conclude that the inclusion or omission of the pronoun has an impact on comprehension. A different pattern emerges when analysing SO and OO RCs separately, as in Figure 13.

Figure 13: *The average number of correct responses for SO and OO relative clauses separately, dependent on the inclusion or omission of a relative pronoun (max. 1), with standard error bars (SO pronoun = 0.510–0.728; SO no pronoun = 0.318–0.540; OO pronoun = 0.510–0.728; OO no pronoun 0.779–0.935).*

The children found SO RCs easier to comprehend when they included the relative pronoun; the average score for this condition was 0.19 higher than the omitted condition. Contrarily, comprehension levels of OO RCs were higher when the relative pronoun was missing, by an average of 0.24. In fact, OO RCs with an omitted pronoun elicited the joint highest percentage of correct responses, with 86% of prompts receiving a correct response. This directly contrasts Beaumont's (1982) findings that this type was most difficult for children (§1.2). The difference between the SO no pronoun ($M = 0.429$, $SD = 0.507$) and the OO no pronoun ($M = 0.857$, $SD = 0.359$) conditions is statistically significant for this sample of children ($t(40) = -3.162$, $p = 0.003$). However, this cannot be generalised as the investigation of pronouns was a secondary objective of my study and consequently each child was only tested on two RCs without a pronoun: one SO and one OO.

To determine the overall effect of the pronoun, average scores were taken from all RCs with a relative pronoun: this consisted of all SS and OS RCs, alongside the SO and OO RCs that retained the pronoun. This was compared to the SO and OO no pronoun condition (Figure 14):

Figure 14: *The average percentage of correct responses for relative clauses including and omitting the relative pronoun, with standard error bars (pronoun = 68.19%–77.05%; no pronoun = 56.80%–71.77%).*

This shows that comprehension was 9% higher for RCs including a relative pronoun than those omitting it. Unlike the other figures, this displays percentages of correct answers, because the conditions were not equal in size. Children were only tested on two RCs without a pronoun, as opposed to six which included the pronoun. Considering all relative pronoun related data, it is therefore not accurate to confirm hypothesis (3), ‘children will show lower levels of comprehension for relative clauses omitting the relative pronoun’, however there is evidence of a slightly higher understanding of RCs that include the pronoun. To determine if these results withstand, the study would need repeating with additional control of relative pronouns.

4 Comparative Discussion

To determine if the reading scheme is reflective of children's RC comprehension and thus answer the overarching research question, the findings of both methodologies need to be compared.

In the book data, object-embedded RCs were four times as common as subject-embedded RCs (§2.2.1). In the comprehension activity, children found the object-embedded RCs easier to understand, with an average score 0.27 higher than subject-embedded RCs (§3.2.1). This demonstrates that, in terms of embeddedness, the scheme books are reflective of children's comprehension. To include a more challenging element that may benefit children's comprehension, the scheme could start integrating more subject-embedded RCs at an earlier level.

A similar correlation is evident between the RC frequencies and comprehension scores in terms of focus. In the comprehension activity, children produced 20% more correct responses for subject focus RCs than object focus RCs (§3.2.2). Subject focus RCs were also 18% more frequent than object focus RCs in the analysed books (§2.2.1). This highlights that the scheme appears to be mirroring children's comprehension abilities.

A Spearman's Rho Correlation was conducted to see if this reflection remains when RC features are combined to produce the four types. This used the total frequencies of each RC across all studied levels, and the average number of correct comprehension responses, as displayed in Table 8:

Table 8: *The frequency of each relative clause type compared to the mean number of correct responses.*

	SS	SO	OS	OO
Frequency	8	6	32	27
Mean number of correct responses (max. 2)	1.62	1.05	1.71	1.48

This was not shown to have a statistically significant correlation ($r_s=0.800$, $p=0.200$). However, the reason for this is evident in Figure 15:

Figure 15: Average number of correct responses for each relative clause compared to the frequency of each type within Oxford Levels 5–12. The line represents what would be the overall trend, excluding the SS clauses.

There is a positive correlation shown for the OS, OO, and OS RC types. Yet, the SS type does not follow this trend. Children demonstrated strong comprehension of this type, so it was expected that they would be more frequent in the reading books than was found. The reading scheme could apply this finding by including a higher number of SS RCs in their books to act as consolidation. This imbalance between frequency and comprehension level could suggest that the reading scheme does not have a major influence on children’s comprehension of RCs. If this was the case, the comprehension scores would be considerably lower for SS clauses. This is, however, a very ambitious claim to make, as there are multiple factors that could be influencing children’s comprehension. It would be useful for any replications of this study to record children’s linguistic environments at home, to see if this trend differs between those reliant on these schemes for a high proportion of their reading exposure, and those receiving additional reading stimuli.

Putting the SS outlier aside, a connection is established between the RC types that children are exposed to, and their comprehension of them. For the SO, OO, and OS types, the more frequent they are in the books, the higher the average number of correct responses. Despite correlation not equating to causation, it may be beneficial to include additional SO clauses in the scheme, as these had the lowest comprehension levels. If higher frequencies are the cause of increased comprehension, this will provide more opportunities for children to develop their understanding. Alternatively, in the case that the scheme is not responsible for any comprehension effects, including more SO RCs will still act as consolidation.

The final feature to consider is the relative pronoun. Both sets of data were somewhat inconclusive. RCs including the relative pronoun were 32% more frequent in the book data than those without, and also elicited a slightly increased comprehension performance. Within the SO and OO categories, only 14% included a relative pronoun. This is reflected in the OO comprehension condition, where results were significantly higher when the pronoun was excluded. However, for SO RCs, the

omission of the relative pronoun reduced correct responses. The inconsistency in these results makes it difficult to determine the relationship between the books and comprehension regarding relative pronouns. As stated, this was a secondary objective of the study, so further research may clarify results.

5 Conclusion

In answer to the main research question, the Oxford Reading Levels 5–12 are largely reflective of five- to six-year-old children's comprehension of RCs. Despite this, the results must remain situated in my data, and therefore cannot be generalised to all children, such as speakers of another language or of a different age, or to any other reading scheme.

As predicted, the analysed books increase in RC complexity with level, signified by the overall increase of RCs, and the increased diversity of RC types at higher levels. In terms of comprehension, the hypothesis was also supported, with children understanding object-embedded and subject focus RCs more easily than subject-embedded and object focus RCs respectively. This is realised in the concluded hierarchy of OS > SS > OO > SO. Although the findings regarding pronouns were not explicit, RCs without pronouns were still evident in the books, and children did demonstrate a good level of understanding.

The general alignment of the RCs in the reading schemes with the comprehension results shows that the scheme is providing RC complexity at a level appropriate for the children; this means they are provided with enough examples of the types they already understand in order to consolidate their knowledge, whilst also integrating types they do not yet fully grasp, to develop their comprehension. This is definitely the case for the OS and OO types, however it remains arguable if additional sentences with SO and SS RCs should be included in the scheme books. For children without a rich linguistic environment at home, this addition would ensure that they are being exposed to an adequate variety of RC types, to extend their grammatical development.

It is necessary to acknowledge the overarching limitations of this study to understand the restrictions of its application. Firstly, it is not certain that the children have read the particular books that were analysed; therefore, if data was collected from those that they had read, the conclusions may be different. Additionally, it may have been more beneficial to have analysed a greater number of books from fewer levels, to achieve more accurate averages. However, the variation within levels should not be so great that the sample is not representative. Another limitation is that the statistical tests, whilst verifying connections, should not be taken as the sole reason for a conclusion, because of the small sample sizes.

Whilst this study has been successful, the constraints of an undergraduate project have resulted in multiple remaining questions. Consequently, there are many avenues for further research that may answer these. If there was a greater interest in children's comprehension of RCs, there is space for further investigation on the effect of relative pronouns. In particular, it would be useful to test whether comprehension levels are dependent on which relative pronoun is used; are there differences between *who*, *that*, and *which*, for example. Additionally, a more extensive review of whether the inclusion of a pronoun in different RC types aids comprehension, would be beneficial to evaluate the findings of this project.

To give the conclusions of this study more context, future research could investigate adults' comprehension of these RC types, to establish what the goal is for children, and at what age they tend to reach adult-like competence. Similarly, an analysis of literature written for adults would be useful to put the numbers of RCs in the reading scheme books into context.

RCs were used in this study as a way of determining grammatical complexity. Thus, future projects could investigate other grammatical structures in reading schemes to increase reliability; if similar trends are found with structures such as anaphora, inflectional morphology, or tense changes, this would support that grammatical complexity is increasing as a whole, rather than just for RCs.

This study was inspired by the literature regarding children's sentence comprehension abilities, and expanded to observe the reading scheme, so the categories were based on previous research, which is not completely reflective of the RCs found in scheme books. If a future comparative project was to be conducted, it would be essential to ensure the experimental sentences are realistic of what children are exposed to in their reading. This would likely involve testing children on RCs embedded in and focused on SPCs, adverbials, and existential sentences, alongside any additional categories evidenced in the books. A wider sample of books is likely to reveal more RC types, so future comparative studies should conclude analysis of the books, before using their results surrounding RCs to determine their experimental conditions. This would ensure direct comparisons can be drawn.

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7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix One: Book Data Sources

Level 4 (preliminary analysis):

- Burchett, J., and Vogler, S. 2009. *The Play Park*. Oxford: University Press.
- Burchett, J., and Vogler, S. 2011. *Tom, Dad and Colin*. Oxford: University Press.
- Hunt, R. 1997. *Everyone Got Wet*. Oxford: University Press.

Hunt, R., and Young, A. 2010. *No Tricks, Gran!* Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R., and Young, A. 2010. *Painting the Loft*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 5:

Donaldson, J. 2006. *The Cinderella Play*. Oxford: University Press.
Donaldson, J. 2013. *Best Friends*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
Doyle, M. 2010. *Silly Jack and the Dancing Mice*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
Hawes, A. 2010. *Make a Wind Vane*. Oxford: University Press.
Llewellyn, C. 2009. *On the Wing*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 6:

Brandon, T. 2009. *Max the Detective*. Oxford: University Press.
Burchett, J., and Vogler, S. 2012. *Swoopie Mischief*. Oxford: University Press.
Donaldson, J. 2006. *Tara's Party*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1988. *The Dump*. Oxford: University Press.
Llewellyn, C. 2009. *Turn it Off!* Oxford: University Press.

Level 7:

Hunt, R. 1987. *Red Planet*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1987. *The Broken Roof*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1988. *The Old Vase*. Oxford: University Press.
Morgan, M. 2009. *Tiger's Discovery*. Oxford: University Press.
Rayner, S. 2009. *Hide and Cheat*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 8:

Burchett, J., and Vogler, S. 2010. *Attack of the Centipede*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1990. *The Flying Carpet*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1990. *The Rainbow Machine*. Oxford: University Press.
Hunt, R. 1990. *Victorian Adventure*. Oxford: University Press.
Poulton, M. 1988. *The Emergency*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 9:

Morgan, M. 2009. *The Deadly Boomslang*. Oxford: University Press.
Oakden, D. 1988. *Danger at Sea*. Oxford: University Press.
Penrose, J. 2008. *Pirates*. Oxford: University Press.
Poulton, M. 1988. *The Photograph*. Oxford: University Press.
Powling, C. 2009. *The Thing in the Cupboard*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 10:

Blank, A. 2009. *Human Body Adventures*. Oxford: University Press.
Bradman, T. 2010. *Cuckoo Trouble*. Oxford: University Press.
Bradman, T. 2010. *Underwater Adventure*. Oxford: University Press.
Middeton, H. 2009. *Let's Form a Band!* Oxford: University Press.
Murtagh, C. 2017. *Dragon Doughnuts*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 11:

- Cartwright, P. 2010. *Awesome Animal Adventures*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
 Coldwell, J. 2014. *Amy the Hedgehog Girl*. Oxford: University Press.
 Ralphs, M. 2014. *Space Jump*. London: Collins.
 Sparkes, A. 2014. *Scratch's Bad Reputations*. Oxford: University Press.
 White, D. 2017. *Teeny Tiny Aliens and the Great Big Pet Disaster*. Oxford: University Press.

Level 12:

- Bradman, T. 2014. *Making a Stand*. Oxford: University Press.
 Clarke, Z. 2015. *Big Weather*. Oxford: University Press.
 Gates, S. 2014. *The Lie Detector*. Oxford: University Press.
 Gowar, M. 2008. *A Matter of Life and Death*. Oxford: University Press.
 Knapman, T. 2017. *Extinct*. Oxford: University Press.

7.2 Appendix Two: Full List of Test Sentences

Set	Clause type	Sentence	
1	SS	The cow that jumped over the cat stood on the table.	SS1
	SO	The cow that the cat jumped over stood on the table.	SO1
		The cow the cat jumped over stood on the table.	SO1
	OS	The cat jumped over the cow that stood on the table.	OS1
	OO	The cat jumped over the table that the cow stood on.	OO1
		The cat jumped over the table the cow stood on.	OO1
Control	The cat jumped over the cow.	Control1	
2	SS	The dog that barked at the sheep wore the hat.	SS2
	SO	The sheep that the dog barked at wore the hat.	SO2
		The sheep the dog barked at wore the hat.	SO2
	OS	The dog barked at the sheep that wore the hat.	OS2
	OO	The dog barked at the hat that the sheep wore.	OO2
		The dog barked at the hat the sheep wore.	OO2
Control	The dog barked at the sheep.	Control2	
3	SS	The goat that ate the grass sat on the horse.	SS3
	SO	The horse that the goat sat on ate the grass.	SO3
		The horse the goat sat on ate the grass.	SO3
	OS	The goat sat on the horse that ate the grass.	OS3
	OO	The goat sat on the grass that the horse ate.	OO3
		The goat sat on the grass the horse ate.	OO3
Control	The goat ate the grass.	Control3	
4	SS	The pig that rolled in the mud sprayed the mouse.	SS4

	SO	The pig that the mouse sprayed rolled in the mud.	SO4
		The pig the mouse sprayed rolled in the mud.	SO4
	OS	The mouse sprayed the pig that rolled in the mud.	OS4
	OO	The pig rolled in the mud that the mouse jumped in.	OO4
		The pig rolled in the mud the mouse jumped in.	OO4
	Control	The pig rolled in the mud.	Control4
5	SS	The chicken that flapped over the cat sang to the rabbit.	SS5
	SO	The chicken that the rabbit sang to flapped over the cat.	SO5
		The chicken the rabbit sang to flapped over the cat.	SO5
	OS	The rabbit sang to the chicken that flapped over the cat.	OS5
	OO	The chicken flapped over the cat that the rabbit sang to.	OO5
		The chicken flapped over the cat the rabbit sang to.	OO5
	Control	The chicken sang to the rabbit.	Control5
6	SS	The donkey that wore the scarf jumped over the dog.	SS6
	SO	The dog that the donkey jumped over wore the scarf.	SO6
		The dog the donkey jumped over wore the scarf.	SO6
	OS	The donkey jumped over the dog that wore the scarf.	OS6
	OO	The donkey jumped over the scarf that the dog wore.	OO6
		The donkey jumped over the scarf the dog wore.	OO6
	Control	The donkey wore the scarf.	Control6
7	SS	The frog that baked the cake taught the fish.	SS7
	SO	The fish that the frog taught baked the cake.	SO7
		The fish the frog taught baked the cake.	SO7
	OS	The frog taught the fish that baked the cake.	OS7
	OO	The frog taught the cake that the fish baked.	OO7
		The frog taught the cake the fish baked.	OO7
	Control	The frog taught the fish.	Control7
8	SS	The snake that built the tower hissed at the fox.	SS8
	SO	The fox that the snake hissed at built the tower.	SO8
		The fox the snake hissed at built the tower.	SO8
	OS	The snake hissed at the fox that built the tower.	OS8
	OO	The snake hissed at the tower that the fox built.	OO8
		The snake hissed at the tower the fox built.	OO8
	Control	The snake built the tower.	Control8

About the Author

Rebecca Hunt graduated with a first-class degree in English Language and Linguistics from the University of Sussex in July 2022. This article is developed from her undergraduate dissertation, which was prompted by her keen interest in both structural linguistics and child language development. She then went on to complete her MA in Applied Linguistics and TESOL, graduating in January 2024. Her interests have since shifted slightly, and she is now in the first year of her PhD at Sussex, focusing on grammaticalisation in Cameroon Pidgin English.

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This Paper is Organized as Follows: Lexical Bundles in Computer Science Academic Texts Produced by Novice and Expert Writers

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Abstract. Conventional academic writing in English is crucial for scholars seeking publication in peer-reviewed international journals. English for Academic Purposes (EAP) materials often use a “one-size-fits-all” approach that does not cater to disciplinary variation or learner needs (Murray, 2016). Lexical bundles (LBs), defined as recurrent continuous sequences of words, are essential building blocks of academic discourse (Biber et al., 2002). While much research has been done on LBs in academic contexts (Neely & Cortes, 2009; Cortes, 2013; Staples et al., 2013; Gil & Caro, 2019), to the best of our knowledge, few studies have compared the use of LBs in texts produced by expert writers (EWs) and novice writers (NWs) to inform the design of EAP materials. This study explores two corpora: (i) a corpus of 170 undergraduate theses written in English by Brazilian undergraduates in Computer Science and (ii) a corpus of 581 published research articles of the same discipline. The primary focus of the study is the introduction section, wherein the goal is to extract, categorize, and compare the most frequently occurring 4-, 5-, and 6-word transparent bundles based on their rhetorical function. The results reveal four trends: (a) both groups of writers do not use LBs to realize certain steps; (b) both groups use LBs similarly; (c) NWs use LBs that EWs do not, and (d) EWs use LBs that NWs do not. These findings can inform the design of EAP materials that cater to the disciplinary variation and learner needs of different academic contexts.

Plain English Abstract. Academic writing in English is essential for scholars who want to publish their work in respected international journals. Most materials that teach English for Academic Purposes (EAP) do not take into account the specific needs of different academic fields or learners. In this study, we focus on a particular aspect of academic writing, which is the use of lexical bundles (LBs). LBs are common phrases or word sequences that are frequently used in academic writing (Biber et al., 2002). We analysed two sets of texts: undergraduate theses in Computer Science written in English by Brazilian students and published research articles in the same discipline. We extracted, categorized, and compared LBs used in the introduction sections of these texts written by expert writers and novice writers. Our goal was to discover which LBs were used most often and for what purpose. Our findings showed that both expert and novice writers did not use LBs as much as they could have in certain instances. However, both groups used LBs in a similar way for most of their writing. We also found that novice writers used some LBs that expert writers did not, and vice versa. These findings can help create better materials for teaching EAP, which can better serve the needs of learners across different academic disciplines.

Keywords: lexical bundles; English for academic purposes; academic writing; communicative functions.

1 Introduction

Academia widely recognizes English as the predominant language of communication, thereby placing substantial pressure on scholars across diverse fields to publish their research in this language to attain global recognition. According to Hyland and Shaw (2016, p. 5), English is a “near-universal academic lingua franca,” and its widespread use cannot be ignored by academics worldwide, who must read, write, and publish in an additional language. Although the reasons behind English's dominance in

academia can be debated as “the result of a conspiracy orchestrated by political and economic interests or the legacy of US and British colonialism” (Hyland, & Shaw, 2016, p. 5), the effects are undeniable. This reality requires academics to invest additional time and effort in mastering the language, on top of their research responsibilities.

In an effort to expand their involvement in research communities at an early stage, Brazilian computer science undergraduates are increasingly writing their undergraduate theses in English. This genre, also referred to as “final paper” in English and “*Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso*” or “*TCC*” in Portuguese, comprises the majority of available undergraduate theses written in English on Lume, one of the largest open-access digital repositories in the world, maintained by the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul.

The majority of universities in Brazil require senior-year undergraduate students to produce a thesis as a prerequisite for earning their bachelor's degree. The purpose of producing this genre is to acquaint students with research methods and writing techniques while also providing them with a comprehensive understanding of a topic they select. The organizational pattern of an undergraduate thesis in Brazil mirrors that of a research article, consisting of an introduction, methodology, results/discussion, and conclusion.

Genres are shaped by the discourse communities they are rooted in, which share a common set of communicative events aimed at achieving specific communicative goals (Swales, 1990). According to Biber and Conrad (2019), genres can be compared based on various situational characteristics such as participants and communicative purposes. It is essential to explore the situational characteristics of the introductions of undergraduate theses to facilitate proper comparisons, especially since the understanding of this genre can vary across cultural contexts.

The objective of our study is to analyse the writing style of computer science undergraduate theses written in English and compare it to that of established researchers who publish in peer-reviewed journals. Our methodology involves a comparison of the introduction sections of Brazilian undergraduate theses and research articles, which both follow the expected conventional rhetorical organization of reviewing previous research, identifying a research gap and stating how the present study addresses that gap (Biber & Conrad, 2019). Furthermore, the introduction section of the two genres conforms to the purpose of providing a rationale for the work and attracting interest to the topic and the reader (Swales & Feak, 2012). Hence, due to those similarities, the comparative approach adopted in this study seems well-suited to our goal of highlighting differences in writing style between newcomers to the scientific community in this field of study and experienced researchers in the same area.

There are, however, notable distinctions in terms of participants and relationships within the two genres being discussed. Senior-year undergraduates, who are novices in the discourse communities of researchers in their field, produce undergraduate theses, whereas more experienced researchers²³ publish their work in peer-reviewed journals. The target audience for these written academic genres also varies slightly. Readers of undergraduate theses generally expect a more extensive and comprehensive discussion of the research topic compared to readers of research articles. Both genres are accessible online, with undergraduate theses being published in Lume as open-access documents. It

²³ In this study, we draw a comparison between the papers produced by *more experienced writers* and those written by *undergraduate students*. The term *more experienced writers* refers to authors who have advanced beyond the undergraduate level, consistent to our survey of the journal from which we source our data. This group comprises, for example, individuals who are either pursuing their Master's or PhD degrees or are already serving as instructors or professors. Given that these authors are subjected to a rigorous peer-review process prior to the publication of their work, a hallmark of a reputable journal, we believe that the research articles examined from this group align with the objectives of our study.

is worth noting that both genres undergo a peer-review process before publication to ensure adherence to conventions of discourse and scientific rigor. In the case of undergraduate theses, they undergo committee review before being included in the open institutional repository.

While many recent studies have examined the language used in academic texts written in English, focusing on the significance of lexical bundles (LBs) across various genres such as research article introductions (Cortes, 2013), bachelor dissertations written in English as a second language (L2) (Gil & Caro, 2019), academic lectures (Neely & Cortes, 2009), and proficiency tests (Staples et al., 2013), there remains a scarcity of research comparing the use of LBs in texts produced by expert and novice writers aiming at informing the design of discipline-specific English for Academic Purposes (EAP) materials.

In our study, we build upon the work of Moreno and Swales (2018, p. 77), who identified a “function-form gap” that can be bridged by identifying significant text items or patterns in a specific rhetorical context. LBs have been studied in EAP corpus-based research, but simply relying on frequency data can result in meaningless strings (Swales, 2019). Our research combines Swalesian genre analysis and corpus linguistics in an attempt to bridge the form-function gap while comparing LBs used by EWs and NWs in computer science, revealing differences and identifying language elements that are worth teaching. Therefore, the present study aims to address gaps in current research by extracting, categorizing, and comparing the most frequent 4-, 5-, and 6-word transparent bundles according to their rhetorical function in two corpora, to later propose pedagogical implications.

One corpus investigated contains introduction sections of undergraduate theses written in English by Brazilian computer science senior-year undergraduates, and the other contains introductions of published research articles written by professional academics in the same field. These bundles will then be compared and studied in relation to their rhetorical function proposed by Cortes (2013), which is based on the work of Swales (1990; 2004). Finally, we draw conclusions and concrete pedagogical applications based on our analyses. More specifically, this study seeks to answer three research questions:

- (1) To what extent do the patterns of LBs used by undergraduate theses writers differ from those used by experienced academic researchers in published research articles?
- (2) How do these differences relate to the merged rhetorical framework proposed by Cortes (2013), and what implications can be drawn for understanding the conventions of academic discourse in Computer Science?
- (3) In light of these findings, what pedagogical applications can be recommended for teaching English for Academic Purposes (EAP) to students in computer science?

1.1 Corpus linguistics and EAP

EAP instructors often lack direct exposure to the professional contexts and disciplines of their students, which may hinder their intuitive understanding of language use in specialized domains. As Sinclair (1991) noted, relying solely on human intuition can be a poor guide to understanding how language functions in real-world situations. In fact, Nesi (2013, p. 407) suggested that such instructors “may not have much intuitive understanding of the way language is used in certain specified domains.”

Corpus Linguistics is used in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and English for Academic Purposes (EAP) to examine language features, including register, lexicogrammar, and phraseology

within corpora. This approach offers valuable insights into language use in specific contexts and helps identify the linguistic patterns of academic disciplines and professions. By using specialized corpora, targeted language instruction can be developed to better prepare students for their chosen fields of study (Bennet, 2010). As highlighted by Nesi (2013), using corpora to inform the development of pedagogical materials has numerous benefits. Researchers can compare the language found in specialized corpora with that presented in non-corpus-based or non-corpus-informed textbooks, identify discrepancies, and update instructional materials to accurately reflect the language students are likely to encounter in their areas of study.

In EAP, corpus-based discipline-specific materials are increasingly essential (Hamp-Lyons, 2011). To the present, many EAP instructors rely on generic, “one-size-fits-all” materials that are designed for use in a wide range of academic contexts and not tailored to the specific needs of a particular discipline or field (Murray, 2016). As Hyland (2016, p. 20-21) observes, “disciplines are largely created and maintained through the distinctive ways in which members jointly construct a view of the world through their discourse.” Therefore, it is crucial to highlight the distinct lexical, grammatical, and rhetorical resources needed to create specialized knowledge within each discipline.

In order to address the gap in existing EAP materials that fail to provide such targeted resources, corpus-based analyses offer valuable insights for developing materials that are closely aligned with the language demands of specific disciplines. By examining language use in specialized corpora, one can identify patterns of vocabulary, grammar, and discourse that are characteristic of particular academic fields. Such insights can inform the development of materials that more accurately reflect the language use in those fields, thereby improving EAP instruction and enhancing learners' ability to succeed in their academic pursuits.

1.2 Lexical Bundles and Swalesian Genre Analysis

Lexical bundles (LBs), as defined by Biber et al. (2002, p. 443), are recurring sequences of words that become “prefabricated chunks,” easily retrievable from a writer's or speaker's memory, and used as building blocks for constructing texts. The significance of such units in indicating “competent participation in a given community” (Hyland, 2008, p. 5) is increasingly acknowledged and supported by empirical evidence. Hence, it seems crucial for scholars aiming to publish their work in peer-reviewed international journals to familiarize themselves with LBs and incorporate them in their academic writing. The use of LBs in academic writing not only enhances the coherence and fluency of the text but also reflects the writer's familiarity with the conventions of their field and their ability to communicate their ideas effectively.

Rhetorical moves, as defined by Swales (2004), are discursal or rhetorical units that perform coherent communicative functions in a given discourse. The concept of moves originates from genre analysis, which was developed by Swales (1981; 1990; 2004) to address the need for teaching ESL students how to enhance their reading and writing skills in academic settings. In his work, Swales (1990) expands upon the concept of discourse community as sociorhetorical networks that emerge to pursue shared objectives and fulfil specific criteria, which encompass common goals, participatory mechanisms, information exchange, community-specific genres, specialized terminology and expertise. Genre, for Swales (1990, p. 58), is conceptualized as “a class of communicative events, the members of which share some set of communicative purposes.” By studying the discourse community's genres and their communicative purposes, Swales identifies moves as fundamental units of discourse that serve specific communicative functions in a given genre.

According to Biber, Connor, and Upton (2007, p. 9), the concept of "moves" refers to the fundamental components of texts, acting as building blocks. These moves, in turn, are comprised of "steps," which are described as "multiple text fragments" (Moreno & Swales, 2018, p. 40) and serve the specific purpose of the move they belong to (Biber, Connor & Upton, 2007). A step, as a text fragment, plays a crucial role in introducing new propositional meaning essential for advancing the text and achieving the intended purpose of the genre. Competent readers of a genre recognize the significance of a step, enabling them to infer a specific communicative function without broad generalizations (Moreno & Swales, 2018). Functioning as a smaller functional text within a move, a step acts as an elaborator, operating at a more detailed level than the move itself (Al-Shujairi & Al-Manaseer, 2022).

LBs, rhetorical moves, and steps play crucial roles in academic writing. LBs contribute to the fluency and coherence of the text, while a framework of rhetorical moves and their corresponding steps help structure and effectively present information within specialized discourse. These elements indicate the writer's level of engagement within the discourse community relevant to the text. Therefore, it is relevant to understand and employ conventional LBs, moves, and steps to produce academic writing pieces that showcase the writer's competence and expertise in their field of study.

Swales and Feak's (2012, p. 331) influential textbook, *Academic Writing for Graduate Students*, highlights how research paper introductions serve as a response to two types of competition: competition for readers and competition for research space. They introduce the create-a-research-space (CARS) model framework from Swales (1990) to help learners understand this pattern. However, in 2004, Swales himself suggested an update to this widely circulated model. He cautioned against its improper rigidity and mechanistic application, emphasizing the importance of contextualizing its use within specific disciplinary and cultural contexts.

Cortes (2013) presents a novel approach that relates LBs to move analysis by integrating two frameworks developed by Swales (1990; 2004). Specifically, for Move 1, "establishing a territory", Cortes (2013) utilizes the steps introduced by Swales in 1990, while for Move 2 and 3, she selects the steps introduced in Swales' 2004 work. A summary of the moves and steps used by Cortes (2013) can be found in Table 1. The merging of the two frameworks allows for a more nuanced and comprehensive analysis of the connection between moves and steps with LBs in academic writing, therefore, contributing to a better understanding of the communication patterns within specific discourse communities.

Table 1: *Moves and steps in research article introductions (Cortes, 2013, p. 37, adapted from Swales, 1990, 2004)*

Move 1 Establishing a territory
Step 1 Claiming centrality
Step 2 Making topic generalizations
Step 3 Reviewing items of previous literature
Move 2 Establishing a niche
Step 1A Indicating a gap or
Step 1B Adding to what is known
Step 2 Presenting positive justification
Move 3 Presenting the present work
Step 1 Announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively
Step 2 Presenting research questions or hypothesis
Step 3 Definitional clarifications
Step 4 Summarizing methods
Step 5 Announcing principal outcomes
Step 6 Stating the value of the present research
Step 7 Outlining the structure of the paper

Overall, Swales (1981; 1990; 2004) developed a text analysis method that helps English language learners improve their research article reading and, most importantly, writing skills. This approach has been widely used by researchers to uncover the generic rhetorical structure of different genres. However, there is a research gap observed by Moreno and Swales (2018, p. 41) referred to as the “function-form gap.” This gap can be bridged by identifying the most significant text items or patterns (form), such as lexical bundles, in a specific rhetorical context (function), i.e., a move and step, that aid readers in interpreting a particular communicative function with accuracy. As Moreno and Swales (2018) argue, this objective is relevant to all text fragments that realize a significant communicative function, except for cases where the function is not linguistically indicated, such as implicit causal logical functions.

Swales (2019) notes that LBs have become a prevalent topic in EAP corpus-based research, particularly for larger corpora where there is a preference for four-word bundles. However, simply relying on frequency data to generate LBs lists may result in meaningless strings that are of “little meaning or use to English language teachers and learners” (p. 77). In contrast, Simpson-Vlach and Ellis’s (2010) study on academic formulas list went beyond to employ a mixed methodology that included frequency data, statistical measures, and polling of EAP teachers and testers, showing potential pedagogical value, according to Swales (2019). Unlike studies that “provide frequency data without any consideration of possible or potential pedagogical uptake” (Swales, 2019, p. 77), our research aims to combine Swalesian genre analysis and corpus linguistics to compare LBs used by EWs and NWs in computer science, revealing differences between the writing of the two groups, identifying what is worth teaching, and proposing concrete pedagogical applications to our findings.

All in all, the introduction section of Brazilian undergraduate theses and research articles adheres to the established rhetorical organization. Rhetorical moves, as defined by Swales (2004), are

coherent communicative units that contribute to the overall structure of the discourse. Within these moves, steps act as essential building blocks, consisting of multiple text fragments that serve specific purposes within the move (Biber, Connor & Upton, 2007). Steps play a crucial role in introducing new propositional meaning and establishing textual progression. Thus, recognizing the significance of steps allows competent readers to infer the specific communicative function they serve (Moreno & Swales, 2018). To accurately interpret communicative functions, it is essential to bridge the gap between form and function by identifying significant text items or patterns within a specific rhetorical context (Moreno & Swales, 2018). Readers can rely on elements such as LBs, which are recurring word sequences serving as prefabricated chunks. LBs enhance the fluency and cohesion of the discourse, acting as fundamental building blocks for constructing texts (Biber et al., 2002). By recognizing and utilizing these linguistic patterns, readers can better understand and engage with the intended meaning and purpose of the text, while writers can demonstrate competent participation within a given community (Hyland, 2008).

2 Methodology

The primary objective of this study was to enhance the development of discipline-specific EAP materials. To achieve this, two corpora were compiled to extract LBs and categorize them according to the rhetorical functions they convey. The quantitative analysis was conducted using SketchEngine (Kilgarriff et al., 2014) and the qualitative analysis involved manual categorization of transparent LBs, which will be explained in this section.

LBs are textual segments identified using software based on their frequency and dispersion, irrespective of their idiomaticity and structural status (Biber et al., 2021). LBs play a significant role in language instruction, not only in constructing grammatically correct sentences but also in employing “well-established lexical expressions in appropriate contexts” (Biber et al., 2021, p. 982). Furthermore, when considering terminology studies (Krieger & Finatto, 2004), LBs relate to the phraseology present in diverse genres within specialized discourse. It can be contended that LBs function as phraseological components and consequently, contribute to the formation of a stereotyped linguistic structure, leading to an autonomous semantic interpretation of the meanings derived from the structure's constituents.

This study draws on two corpora of introduction sections, one comprising undergraduate theses by novice writers (NWs) and the other consisting of published research articles authored by more experienced researchers and hence expert writers (EWs), both from the field of computer sciences. The data were collected with the aim of contrasting the results and identifying the differences in the use of LBs across the two groups.

To create the Corpus of Computer Sciences Final Paper Introductions from Lume (CorCompInt-Lume), all undergraduate theses written in English under the “Computer Science - Undergraduate degree” collection on Lume were located through website filters for subject (Computer Science), language (English) and genre (undergraduate thesis) and, subsequently, downloaded²⁴. The introduction sections were then manually identified, copied, and pasted into a Word document (Microsoft, 2022). After that, the data was cleaned to remove any elements that did not pertain to the section's prose or reflect the students' writing skills, such as page numbers, titles, subtitles, graphs, tables, images, captions, formulas, footnotes, and block quotes.

²⁴ Obtaining consent from the students was not necessary for the process, as all undergraduate theses made available on Lume are open-access and covered under the Creative Commons BY-NC-SA 2.5 Deed.

The Corpus of Computer Sciences Introductions from PLOS One (CorCompInt-PLOS), consisting of text produced by expert writers (EWs), was generated using AntCorGen (Anthony, 2022), a freeware program that facilitates the creation of section- and discipline-specific corpora from peer-reviewed, open-access articles published in international peer-reviewed journals available on the PLOS One platform. Subsequently, both corpora were uploaded to and compiled on Sketch Engine (Kilgarriff et al., 2014). Table 2 displays the number of tokens, types, and texts in each corpus used in this study.

Table 2: *Corpora metadata*

Corpus	Number of tokens	Number of types	Number of texts
CorCompInt-Lume	173,371	148,310	170
CorCompInt-PLOS	646,236	532,235	581

Three criteria were considered for the extraction of n-grams using Sketch Engine (Kilgarriff et al., 2014): (i) the extension of the word sequences (n-gram length), (ii) their raw frequency in the corpus (minimum frequency), and (iii) the number of texts in which the sequences occurred in the corpora (dispersion). For CorCompInt-Lume, the extraction criteria were as follows n-gram length of 5, 6, and 7; minimum frequency of 6; and dispersion of 3. Given the larger size of CorCompInt-PLOS, we employed a more conservative approach to extract a similar number of LBs as we did from CorCompInt-LUME. This allowed us to compare only the most frequent LBs. Thus, for CorCompInt-PLOS, the extraction criteria were as follows: n-gram length of 5, 6, and 7; minimum frequency of 15; and dispersion of 8.

The total number of LBs meeting the described criteria in CorCompInt-Lume was 125 and in CorCompInt-PLOS, 120. However, due to the objectives of this study, we worked with a subset of LBs that met the established criteria and were easily classified as transparent lexical bundles. These so-called transparent lexical bundles contained a semantically significant collocation node (Frankenberg-Garcia et al., 2019).

The two authors collaborated to manually categorize the LBs into the merged Swalesian framework for moves and steps proposed by Cortes (2013; see Table 1). The most significant functions conveyed by the chosen bundles were prioritized, and the categorization was performed by associating LBs with specific steps based on their collocation nodes. LBs that could not be clearly linked to certain steps were disregarded. This methodological decision was made because we believed it would be more useful and pedagogically beneficial to concentrate on bundles that were transparent in conveying rhetorical functions. While acknowledging that less transparent bundles, such as discourse organizers that occur across sections and moves, and stance bundles that express the authors' opinions are also important (Hyland, 2008), we delimited our scope and left them for further research.

Overall, this study followed a corpus-driven approach to the data in which we combined a bottom-up corpus linguistics methodology with a top-down move-analysis approach. First, two corpora were designed and compiled, then 4-, 5- and 6-word bundles were extracted, analysed and sorted. Then, the transparent LBs were categorized into each step of an introduction. Finally, we observed four trends in our data, which are explored in the section below, to later assess pedagogical implications.

3 Results and discussion

This study aims to compare the use of LBs in Computer Science by NWs and EWs to gain insights into the pedagogical applications of language data, which can then inform the development of discipline-specific EAP materials. In this context, NW refers to writers of undergraduate theses who are Brazilian undergraduate students of computer science, while EW refers to other researchers in the same field who have published papers in journals from the PLOS One platform.

Figure 1 shows the total number of LBs extracted from each corpus, along with the number of LBs selected for this study from each corpus. A total of 245 LBs were extracted, with 125 from CorCompInt-Lume and 120 from CorCompInt-PLOS. In selecting bundles for the study, 61 LBs (48.8%) were chosen from CorCompInt-Lume, and 42 LBs (33.6%) were chosen from CorCompInt-PLOS²⁵. These selected bundles are referred to as transparent lexical bundles because they allow for more accurate identification of the rhetorical function they realize. We classified the transparent lexical bundles based on the primary moves and steps conveyed by them, as outlined in the merged framework proposed by Cortes (2013). This classification was made by observing the collocation nodes and their immediate context.

Figure 1: Total and transparent numbers of LBs.

Four trends were identified when comparing the data extracted from both corpora. First, both groups of writers showed a lack of use of LBs to realize certain steps. Second, there were instances of similar and/or identical use of LBs by both groups of writers. Third, NWs used some LBs that EWs did not use. Finally, there were some LBs used by EWs that were not used by NWs.

The first trend observed in the data appears to reveal that none of the transparent LBs expressed six steps from the merged Swalesian framework by Cortes (2013). These six steps include "making topic generalizations" (M1 - S2), "reviewing previous literature" (M1 - S3), "adding to existing knowledge" (M2 - S1B), "presenting research questions or hypotheses" (M3 - S2), "providing definition clarifications" (M3 - S3) and "summarizing research methods" (M3 - S4). These findings raise the question of whether these steps are not typically expressed using a formulaic structure or whether they are not present in written works within this discipline. While it is reasonable to assume that certain steps

²⁵ See Appendices for the raw frequency, normalized frequency and document frequency of transparent lexical bundles extracted from CorCompInt-PLOS and CorCompInt-Lume.

may not be realized through formulaic language, caution should be exercised when interpreting this result due to the limitations of our samples.

Table 3 shows that NWs and EWs use similar or identical LBs for the steps of "indicating a gap" (M2 - S1A) and "outlining the structure of the paper" (M3 - S7). When it comes to expressing the function of M2 - S1A, both groups of writers tend to use the 4-word bundle *best of our knowledge*, as illustrated in examples 1 and 2. The group of transparent LBs that express the function of "outlining the structure of the paper" (M3 - S7) is the most frequently used in both corpora. This indicates that M3 - S7 is not only reliant on formulaic language but is also an obligatory rhetorical step of papers in computer science.

Ex. 1. 'To the best of our knowledge, no full multi-objective linear model for UTRP has been published before.' (CorCompInt-Lume)

Ex. 2. 'To the best of our knowledge, it is the first attempt to combine these two methods to improve the performance of NER on Chinese EMR.' (CorCompInt-PLOS)

Table 3: *Similar and/or identical use of LBs by NWs and EWs*

Rhetorical structure		CorCompInt-Lume	CorCompInt-PLOS
		Lexical bundles	Lexical bundles
M2 - S1A	Indicating a gap	best of our knowledge the best of our knowledge the best of our	the best of our knowledge the best of our best of our knowledge To the best of To the best of our knowledge To the best of our
M3 - S7	Outlining the structure of the paper	is organized as follows work is organized as work is organized as follows This work is organized This work is organized as this work is organized of this work is organized as this work is organized as follows this work is organized as of this work is organized This work is organized as follows The remainder of this The remaining of this is structured as follows document is organized as rest of this work remainder of this work is remainder of this work	is organized as follows paper is organized as paper is organized as follows this paper is organized of this paper is organized this paper is organized as follows this paper is organized as of this paper is organized as The remainder of this The remainder of this paper remainder of this paper The remainder of this paper is remainder of this paper is the paper is organized of the paper is organized the paper is organized as follows the paper is organized as of the paper is organized as

remainder of this work is organized	the structure of the
document is organized as follows	The rest of the paper is
This work is divided	The rest of the paper
the organization of the	rest of the paper is
The remainder of this work is	rest of the paper
The remainder of this work	rest of this paper
The rest of this work is	The rest of this
The rest of this work	The rest of this paper
rest of this work is organized	remainder of this paper is organized
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	The remainder of the

While the term "paper" was exclusively employed to describe texts in CorCompInt-PLOS (as in example 3), NWs in CorCompInt-Lume referred to their written pieces as "work" (as in example 4) or "document" (as in Example 5). This divergence in terminology could potentially be attributed to the distinct genres produced by each group. Despite this difference, in both corpora, writers employ the same pattern of construction, which might characterize it as a lexical frame, i.e., "discontinuous sequences in which words form a 'frame' surrounding a variable slot" (Gray & Biber, 2013, p. 109), as suggested in Table 4.

Ex. 3. 'This paper is organized as follows: section State of the art introduces the state of the art about characterization methodology and selection of simulation intervals.' (CorCompInt-PLOS)

Ex. 4. 'This work is organized as follows: in chapter 2 the MOSFET technology is reviewed, and the FinFET architecture detailed, along with comparisons.' (CorCompInt-Lume)

Ex. 5. 'The remainder of the document is organized as follows: In Section 1.1 a formal definition of the problem is given.' (CorCompInt-Lume)

Table 4: Lexical frame "The * of this * is * as follows"

The	*	of	this	*	is	*	as	follows
	remainder			paper		organized		
	rest			work		structured		
				document				

The third trend in comparing LBs reveals a difference in their use by NWs to realize the steps of “presenting positive justification” (M2 - S2) and “announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively” (M3 - S1). In contrast, EWs do not use any transparent LBs to express these two functions. This finding is displayed in Table 5 and suggests that NWs may be oversimplifying a construction that is more complex and less formulaic than what is employed by EWs.

NWs tend to use certain bundles, such as *The goal of this work is* (example 6) and *objective of this work is*, to perform the obligatory step of announcing the current research. In contrast, looking at the noun word list of CorCompInt-PLOS in Sketch Engine (Kilgarriff et al., 2014), the most frequent words used by EWs that relate to this step are “purpose” (202.71 occurrences PMW) and “goal” (184.14 occurrences PMW), neither of which appear in the n-grams list that meet our criteria for LBs in this corpus.

Table 5: LBs used by NWs, but not used by EWs

		CorCompInt-Lume
	Rhetorical structure	Lexical bundles
M2 - S2	Presenting positive justification	a better understanding of the a better understanding of better understanding of the
M3 - S1	Announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively	goal of this work goal of this work is goal of this work is to The goal of this objective of this work is objective of this work is to objective of this work The main objective of The main goal of The goal of this work is The goal of this work main objective of this work main objective of this work is main objective of this The main objective of this The main objective of this work This work focuses on the focus of this

Ex. 6. ‘The goal of this work is to present concrete benchmark results of different libraries, APIs, platforms, and implementation techniques for the matrix decomposition problem, and further analysis into the ways that such tools improve (or not) the efficiency of the implementation for similar problems.’ (CorCompInt-Lume)

Table 6 highlights LBs used by EWs but absent in the use of NWs when performing the steps of "claiming centrality" (M1 - S1), "announcing principal outcomes" (M3 - S5), and "stating the value of the present research" (M3 - S6), according to the established cut off points. Surprisingly, only four LBs were found in this category: *plays an important role*, *results show that the*, *the results of the* and *contributions of this paper*, all of which are exemplified below.

This fourth trend suggests that NWs may not be familiar with the formulaic nature of the phraseology used to fulfil the rhetorical functions of these three steps. This finding underscores the necessity of explicit instruction on the use of LBs in academic writing and highlights the potential benefits of providing NWs with access to formulaic language resources to enhance their proficiency in constructing texts that fulfil the rhetorical steps in a formulaic manner within the computer science field.

Table 6: *LBs used by EWs, but not used by NWs*

Rhetorical structure		CorCompInt-PLOS Lexical bundles
M1 - S1	Claiming centrality	plays an important role
M3 - S5	Announcing principal outcomes	results show that the the results of the
M3 - S6	Stating the value of the present research	contributions of this paper

Ex. 7. ‘Software development effort estimation plays an important role in the software engineering field.’ (CorCompInt-PLOS)

Ex. 8. ‘The results show that the hybrid model proposed in this paper has higher prediction accuracy than other models.’ (CorCompInt-PLOS)

Ex. 9. ‘Specifically, we use reverse annealing to explore local minima near an initial state defined by the results of the previous iteration of the algorithm.’ (CorCompInt-PLOS)

Ex. 10. ‘The contributions of this paper are listed as follows.’ (CorCompInt-PLOS)

In conclusion, the analysis of the data extracted from both corpora revealed four distinct trends. Firstly, both groups of writers exhibited a lack of using specific lexical bundles (LBs) to realize certain steps. Secondly, there were instances of similar or identical use of LBs by both groups. Thirdly, NWs used LBs that were not utilized by EWs. Lastly, there were LBs used by EWs that were not employed by NWs. These findings indicate potential differences in the usage and understanding of LBs between the two groups. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of explicit instruction and access to formulaic language resources to enhance academic writing proficiency, particularly within the computer science discipline.

4 Pedagogical implications

The main contribution of this paper is to inform EAP material designers of relevant linguistic features in a specialized genre. Incorporating the findings discussed in the section above into the design of EAP materials is essential for enabling NWs to produce more formulaic and conventional texts. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of their research being recognized within the specific disciplinary community of computer scientists.

In Brazil, there is a rising demand for the creation of resources that cater to the needs of the expanding community of emerging researchers in computer science. This is evident due to the notable inclination among undergraduate students in this discipline to actively engage in research communities through the English language from the early stages of their academic journey. A significant indicator of this trend is the growing number of students choosing to compose their undergraduate theses in English. As previously noted, the most extensive collection of English-language undergraduate theses on Lume is centred around this particular field.

Despite the significance of corpus linguistics in identifying patterns in authentic language use and advocating for the integration of corpus data into EAP classes, its actual implementation in classrooms globally is still in the early stages. A host of challenges, including time constraints, large numbers of students in class, and technological barriers have been recognized as impediments to its widespread adoption (Kavanagh, 2021). Moreover, many educators lack a basic understanding of the underlying principles of corpus linguistics. Additionally, a significant number of papers in this field often leave readers in the dark about potential classroom applications of the extracted data, as they do not propose any tasks or activities that incorporate the findings.

Previous studies that investigated the pedagogical work with LBs, found that these units are not easily acquired in the short term (Cortes, 2007). However, once students become proficient in using them, there is a positive impact on their writing grades (Kazemi et al., 2014). Therefore, we now move on to suggest a task based on our results that can enlighten EAP material designers and instructors to work with data extracted from our corpora.

Figure 2: Tasks.

The framework below presents moves and steps that can occur in the introductions of research articles.

Table 1: Moves and steps in research article introductions (Cortes, 2013, p. 37, adapted from Swales, 1990, 2004)

	<p>Move 1 Establishing a territory</p> <p>Step 1 Claiming centrality</p> <p>Step 2 Making topic generalizations</p> <p>Step 3 Reviewing items of previous literature</p> <p>Move 2 Establishing a niche</p> <p>Step 1A Indicating a gap or</p> <p>Step 1B Adding to what is known</p> <p>Step 2 Presenting positive justification</p> <p>Move 3 Presenting the present work</p> <p>Step 1 Announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively</p> <p>Step 2 Presenting research questions or hypothesis</p> <p>Step 3 Definitional clarifications</p> <p>Step 4 Summarizing methods</p> <p>Step 5 Announcing principal outcomes</p> <p>Step 6 Stating the value of the present research</p> <p>Step 7 Outlining the structure of the paper</p>
<p>(a) Based on your prior experience with texts in your field, mark with a check (✓) which moves and steps you believe are obligatory in computer science research.</p> <p>(b) Match the concordance lines (Screenshots 1, 2 and 3) with the steps from the framework you think the authors are conveying with the formulaic language in red.</p>	
<p>Screenshot 1: <i>KWIC "plays an important role"</i></p> <p>Move ()</p> <p>Step ()</p>	
<p>Screenshot 2: <i>KWIC "results SHOW that the"</i></p> <p>Move ()</p> <p>Step ()</p>	
<p>Screenshot 3: <i>KWIC "contributions of this paper"</i></p> <p>Move ()</p> <p>Step ()</p>	

Figure 2 presents tasks that exemplify indirect data-driven learning (Johns, 1990), where students are presented with concordance lines extracted beforehand by the teacher, allowing them to analyse and

draw conclusions independently. The primary objective of the tasks is to enhance learners' rhetorical awareness, perception of disciplinary variation, and recognition of formulaic language. This is achieved specifically by introducing and highlighting LBs used by EWs that are absent in NWs writing so that these linguistic features can become a part of the repertoire of the latter group.

5 Conclusion

This study aimed to compare the usage of 4-, 5-, and 6-word bundles between two distinct corpora: one composed of texts written by NWs (CorCompInt-Lume) and another containing texts written by EWs (CorCompInt-PLOS). The former comprises introduction sections of undergraduate theses produced by novice writers in the field of computer science from Brazilian universities. The latter consists of introduction sections from research articles published in PLOS One, written by experienced writers in the same field. In total, 245 LBs were extracted, and 42% of them were classified based on the rhetorical functions they linguistically realize. The goal was to use language data extracted from a corpus to inform the design of discipline-specific EAP materials, aiming to address the specific needs of students rather than relying on generic "one-size-fits-all" EAP resources widely available.

Upon contrasting the two corpora, four distinct trends emerged in the use of LBs. These trends are as follows: (i) both groups of writers showed a lack of LBs usage to realize certain rhetorical functions expressed; (ii) both groups of writers demonstrated similar and/or identical usage of LBs; (iii) NWs utilized LBs that EWs did not use; and (iv) EWs used LBs that were not used by NWs.

The first trend in the data may not be the primary concern for EAP material designers who are aiming to teach conventional language chunks. This is because our results yielded no LBs that clearly realize some steps. In fact, our results suggest a lack of formulaic structures in realizing the following steps: "making topic generalizations" (M1 - S2), "reviewing previous literature" (M1 - S3), "adding to existing knowledge" (M2 - S1B), "presenting research questions or hypotheses" (M3 - S2), "providing definition clarifications" (M3 - S3), and "summarizing research methods" (M3 - S4). The non-identification of LBs in these steps within the scope of our study does not necessarily imply their absence in the texts. Despite their unconventional realization through LBs in our corpora, the emphasis on these steps in teaching the rhetorical structure of research articles should persist, remarking that some steps do not seem to follow a formulaic pattern in the field of computer science.

Still regarding the first trend, it is worth mentioning that our results do not merge with those of Cortes (2013), who investigated LBs in a corpus of research article introductions across thirteen disciplines, being computer science one of them. The author did find LBs that express the six steps previously mentioned. This discrepancy might indicate that our results corroborate the fact that disciplinary variation exists and that a closer look at a discipline-specific sample can reveal different patterns.

As per the second trend, both groups of writers showed similar and/or identical usage of LBs in realizing the rhetorical functions related to "indicating a gap" (M2 - S1A) and "outlining the structure of the paper" (M3 - S7).

The third and fourth trends in the data highlight the teaching gap - the areas in which EAP professionals should pay close attention while making decisions about what to bring into their classrooms. The third trend indicates that NWs may oversimplify a construction that experienced writers build in a more complex and less formulaic manner. These constructions are responsible for "presenting positive justification" (M2 - S2) and performing the rhetorical function of "announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively" (M3 - S1). In contrast, the fourth trend suggests that

NWs may not be aware of the formulaic nature of the phraseology used to perform the rhetorical functions of "claiming centrality" (M1 - S1), "announcing the principal outcomes" (M3 - S5) and "stating the value of the research" (M3 - S6).

To bridge the function-form gap and support the development of effective academic writing skills, EAP material designers should focus on addressing the third and fourth trends identified in the data. The third trend highlights the oversimplification of certain steps by NWs in "presenting positive justification" (M2 - S2) and "announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively" (M3 - S1). The fourth trend reveals NWs' lack of awareness of formulaic phraseology that could improve the construction of their research text by conventionally expressing the steps of "claiming centrality" (M1 - S1), "announcing principal outcomes" (M3 - S5), and "stating the value of the present research" (M3 - S6).

In contrast, the second trend, which describes the similar and/or identical use of LBs by both groups of writers, should not be the main concern of EAP instruction. While it is important for students to acquire these LBs through exposure to high-standard works, it may be worth considering lexical and frequency discrepancies based on the specific goals of the lesson.

When designing materials, it is important to consider the language elements where NWs differ from EWs. By analysing the written production of both groups, for example, if NWs already demonstrate proficiency in employing certain linguistic constructions, it may be unnecessary to design instructional materials that solely target those aspects. Instead, instructional efforts should be directed toward identifying and addressing the distinctive language patterns exhibited by NWs compared to their expert counterparts. This approach allows for more targeted and effective instruction that addresses the specific linguistic needs and challenges faced by NWs, facilitating their development toward higher levels of writing proficiency.

It is also important to note that the lexical differences observed in the study may be related to the fact that we compared the introduction sections of two different genres: undergraduate thesis and research articles. For example, LBs containing the words "work" and "document" were exclusively found in CorCompInt-Lume, while LBs with the word "paper" were exclusively found in CorCompInt-PLOS. This highlights the importance of considering genre-specific language use when designing EAP materials.

This research is not without its limitations. The main one is that our samples, which are rooted in different genres and sourced from only two databases: PLOS One and Lume. Further research is needed to explore the relationship between LBs and moves and steps from other sources, genres and sections of computer science academic texts, beyond the scope of this study.

The results presented in this paper could be valuable for future research aimed at developing an automated method for classifying LBs in different sections, building upon the foundation established by the present study. By incorporating machine learning techniques, an automatic classification system for LBs could be developed, facilitating more efficient analysis and interpretation of these linguistic units.

Furthermore, it is crucial to consider alternative approaches for studying LBs in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of these units. It is also important not to overstate the significance of conducting discipline and section-specific studies. Investigating LBs that are more recurrent in certain disciplines and specific sections of research articles holds immense value. This is particularly true when it comes to informing the design of EAP writing materials. These discipline and section-specific studies will contribute significantly to enhancing our understanding of the utilization of

formulaic language in academic writing and its role in disciplinary variation, especially in shaping the development of targeted EAP writing resources.

6 References

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6 Appendices

6.1. Appendix One: Raw frequency, relative frequency, and document frequency of transparent lexical bundles extracted from CorCompInt-PLOS

Lexical bundle	Raw frequency	Relative frequency	Document frequency
is organized as follows	110	170.21645	110
paper is organized as	98	151.64739	98
paper is organized as follows	97	150.09996	97
this paper is organized	42	64.99174	42
the best of our knowledge	42	64.99174	40
the best of our	42	64.99174	40
best of our knowledge	42	64.99174	40

THIS PAPER IS ORGANIZED AS FOLLOWS: LEXICAL BUNDLES IN COMPUTER SCIENCE ACADEMIC
TEXTS PRODUCED BY NOVICE AND EXPERT WRITERS

of this paper is organized	41	63.44431	41
this paper is organized as follows	40	61.89689	40
this paper is organized as	40	61.89689	40
of this paper is organized as	39	60.34947	39
The remainder of this	38	58.80205	38
The remainder of this paper	35	54.15978	35
remainder of this paper	35	54.15978	35
The remainder of this paper is	33	51.06494	33
remainder of this paper is	33	51.06494	33
To the best of	31	47.97009	30
the paper is organized	30	46.42267	30
of the paper is organized	30	46.42267	30
To the best of our knowledge	29	44.87525	28
To the best of our	29	44.87525	28
the paper is organized as follows	29	44.87525	29
the paper is organized as	29	44.87525	29
of the paper is organized as	29	44.87525	29
the structure of the	27	41.7804	23
The rest of the paper is	26	40.23298	26
The rest of the paper	26	40.23298	26
rest of the paper is	26	40.23298	26
rest of the paper	26	40.23298	26
rest of this paper	25	38.68556	25
The rest of this	23	35.59071	23
The rest of this paper	22	34.04329	22
results show that the	22	34.04329	13
remainder of this paper is organized	22	34.04329	22
rest of this paper is	21	32.49587	21
rest of the paper is organized	21	32.49587	21
The rest of this paper is	20	30.94845	20
rest of this paper is organized	18	27.8536	18
is structured as follows	18	27.8536	18
contributions of this paper	18	27.8536	18
paper is structured as follows	17	26.30618	17
paper is structured as	17	26.30618	17
the results of the	16	24.75876	15
plays an important role	16	24.75876	15
The remainder of the	15	23.21133	15

2.2 Appendix Two: Raw frequency, relative frequency, and document frequency of transparent lexical bundles extracted from CorCompInt-Lume

Lexical bundle	Raw frequency	Relative frequency	Document frequency
is organized as follows	58	334.54269	58
work is organized as	39	224.95112	39
work is organized as follows	36	207.64718	36
This work is organized	20	115.35955	20
This work is organized as	18	103.82359	18
this work is organized	17	98.05561	17
of this work is organized as	17	98.05561	17
this work is organized as follows	17	98.05561	17
this work is organized as	17	98.05561	17
of this work is organized	17	98.05561	17
goal of this work	15	86.51966	14
goal of this work is	15	86.51966	14
This work is organized as follows	15	86.51966	15
goal of this work is to	13	74.98371	12
The goal of this	12	69.21573	12
objective of this work is	11	63.44775	11
objective of this work is to	11	63.44775	11
objective of this work	11	63.44775	11
The remainder of this	11	63.44775	11
The remaining of this	9	51.9118	9
is structured as follows	9	51.9118	9
The main objective of	8	46.14382	8
document is organized as	8	46.14382	8
rest of this work	8	46.14382	8
The main goal of	7	40.37584	7
The goal of this work is	7	40.37584	7
The goal of this work	7	40.37584	7
remainder of this work is	7	40.37584	7
remainder of this work	7	40.37584	7
remainder of this work is organized	7	40.37584	7
document is organized as follows	7	40.37584	7
This work is divided	7	40.37584	7
the organization of the	7	40.37584	7
The remainder of this work is	7	40.37584	7
The remainder of this work	7	40.37584	7
best of our knowledge	6	34.60786	6
the best of our knowledge	6	34.60786	6
the best of our	6	34.60786	6

a better understanding of the	6	34.60786	6
a better understanding of	6	34.60786	6
better understanding of the	6	34.60786	6
main objective of this work	6	34.60786	6
main objective of this work is	6	34.60786	6
main objective of this	6	34.60786	6
The main objective of this	6	34.60786	6
The main objective of this work	6	34.60786	6
This work focuses on	6	34.60786	6
the focus of this	6	34.60786	6
goals of this work	6	34.60786	6
The rest of this work is	6	34.60786	6
The rest of this work	6	34.60786	6
rest of this work is organized	6	34.60786	6
rest of this work is	6	34.60786	6
this document is organized as	6	34.60786	6
this document is organized	6	34.60786	6
are presented in Chapter	6	34.60786	5
presents an overview of	6	34.60786	5
of this document is	6	34.60786	6

About the Authors

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Design Statement

The front cover of this issue was designed by Laura Zabala (University of Buenos Aires) and the back cover was designed by Lydia Wiernik (University of Edinburgh)

Journal of the Undergraduate Linguistics Association of Britain

Front Matter	3
Articles	
<i>Complexity and the Phonological Turing Machine</i> LOUIS VAN STEENE, UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	11
<i>Positioning Theory as a Tool for Analysing Working Class Identities: Angela Rayner in Interview</i> GEORGIA JUCKES, UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM	33
<i>Influence of Different Walking Speeds on Speech</i> ADELA BARTLICK SALCEDO, UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	60
<i>Fostering Second Language Acquisition of Canadian Primary School Children: A Critical Evaluation of Vygotsky's Learning Theory in the French Immersion Programme</i> FANGQIAN GUO, UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	92
<i>Expertise, Credibility, Trust and Advice in Veterinarian-Client-Pet Health Communication on Reality Television</i> ELEONORA KACL, UNIVERSITY OF BASEL	98
<i>The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: Does the Evidence Support its Existence?</i> NICHOLAS CHAVEZ, METROPOLITAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF DENVER	124
<i>Opaque Segholates Revisited: The Glottal Stop in Standard Modern Hebrew Phonology</i> MADELEINE KOSTANT-GREELEY, UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, LOS ANGELES	135
<i>Relative Clauses in Reading Schemes: How does Children's Comprehension Align?</i> REBECCA HUNT, UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX	157
<i>This Paper is Organized as Follows: Lexical Bundles in Computer Science Academic Texts Produced by Novice and Expert Writers</i> WESLEY HENRIQUE ACORINTI & ANA ELIZA PEREIRA BOCORNY, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF RIO GRANDE DO SUL	189
Back Matter	212